

REORIENTING THE EMPATHY MACHINE:

FEELING-WITH THE OTHER IN CRITICAL VR DOCUMENTARY PRACTICE

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Statement of Originality

I, Tessa Ratuszynska Price, confirm that the research included within this thesis is my own work or that where it has been carried out in collaboration with, or supported by others, that this is duly acknowledged in the following and my contribution indicated.

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03/09/2024

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Instructions for Examiners

This exegesis includes images relating to work made throughout this research.

Within the sub sections relating to early experimental practice in Chapter 3, I have included hyperlinks to google drive folders which include further video and audio material which documents those experiments.

The practice based artefact of this research is *With These Hands*: a 17 minute interactive VR documentary, designed for a Oculus Quest 2 VR headset, and further requiring the user to be seated at a table or desk. At the beginning of Chapter 4, I include another hyperlink to a folder which includes the build for *With These Hands* and set-up instructions to load it onto the appropriate headset. If required, a pre-loaded Oculus Quest 2 headset can be provided on request. The at-home experience will not communicate the full experience of *With These Hands* however, which includes a corresponding installation. The linked folder also contains documentation of *With These Hands* in installation at IDFA 2022, and an in-headset video capture playthrough of the experience. This video however is not capable of accurately communicating the embodied experience, nor specifically can it render the scenes utilising camera passthrough.

The creative work submitted alongside this exegesis in the forms listed above can be viewed, listened to and experienced at any time during, before or after reading the corresponding chapters. However it is recommended that these materials are engaged with at the points in which the hyperlinks appear within the text.

All these resources are also available here:

[▶ REORIENTING THE EMPATHY MACHINE Practice Portfolio - Tessa Ratuszynska Price](#)

ABSTRACT

A decade ago, Virtual Reality (VR) unexpectedly emerged as a creative frontier for documentary. In VR, audiences feel present in documented places and alongside documented people, or may even experience more novel perspectives as ‘in-place-of’ or ‘in-the-body-of’ documentary contributors. These qualities of VR have been likened to Empathy - the ability to imagine the position and perspective of another, or ‘walk in their shoes’.

VR is perceived by its users less as a media experience, and more like a lived experience. This profoundly challenges VR documentary audiences' to retain a critical distance from represented environments, subjects and contributors. The simulative power of VR risks viewers overestimating their understanding of the content, and the subjective experience of represented individuals. At worst, it risks contributors' stories and bodies becoming empty vessels for the audience to inhabit, under the guise of ‘empathetic’ identification. Accordingly, VR makers have been urged to consider what might constitute ethical relations or ‘distances’ between audiences, and the stories and bodies of the contributors they represent.

This practice based research project approaches this question of ethical distances between VR makers, audiences, and contributors, through the production of creative artefact *With These Hands*. *With These Hands* is an interactive VR documentary made in consultation with survivor-led organisation SLEEC (Survivors Leading Essential Education and Change) which shares challenging, complex and lesser heard narratives of sexual assault and recovery. Through *With These Hands*, this research explores modes of visual representation and interaction design that might sustain the audience’s critical appreciation of documentary contributors' distinct subjectivity. Additionally, this research explores methods of collaborative production that might uphold ethical relations between VR makers and their contributors. Finally, in employing the descriptive methodology of Queer Phenomenology, it proposes how VR makers might feel out appropriate or ethical ‘distances’ in their own work.

CONTENTS

TITLE PAGE	1
STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY	2
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND THANKS	3
INSTRUCTIONS FOR EXAMINERS	6
ABSTRACT	7
List of Figures	10
List of Abbreviations	11
Glossary	12
1 INTRODUCTION	13
<i>“Dragged Slowly and Inexorably Forward”</i>	14
Background to Practice	15
Background to Inquiry: VR as an Empathy Machine	17
Focus of Inquiry: Gaps for Practice Based Research	22
Summary of Research	29
The RL of this VR Research	36
2 QUEER PHENOMENOLOGY AND ‘THE EMPATHY MACHINE’	38
<i>“A Profound Turning Away”</i>	39
Phenomenology and VR Research	41
Queer Phenomenology: Extension and Orientation	50
Critique of ‘The Empathy Machine’	52
Returning to Phenomenology: Empathy, Alterity and Ethical Representation of the Other	58
Boundaries for Practice	61
3 EXPERIMENTS WITH QUEER PHENOMENOLOGY	63
<i>The Climb</i>	64
Queer Phenomenology in Early Practice	65
Queer Phenomenology in Existing Practice	77
Turning Toward Embodiment: Early Technical Proposal for <i>With These Hands</i>	83

4 PRODUCTION OF WITH THESE HANDS	87
<i>Speaking, Listening and Turning Away</i>	88
Conceptual origins of With These Hands	90
4.1 Pre-Production	93
Workshop 1: Eyerolls, Empathy and Hands	96
Workshop 2: “We HATE consent forms”	101
Workshop 3: Story Sharing with Men, a contradiction in terms?	113
Revision of Technical Proposal for With These Hands	117
4.2 Production	124
<i>Peeling Skin</i>	125
Chris’ Story: ‘ <i>On The App</i> ’	131
Narora’s Story: ‘ <i>Blueberry Muffins</i> ’	140
SLEEC’s Story: ‘ <i>Hands Around A Coffee Cup</i> ’	151
The Voice Over: ‘ <i>Place Your Hands in Mine</i> ’	158
Working with Khora	173
4.3 Exhibition	176
User Testing at CSSS	177
Installation Design	182
Audience Reflections: “Thanks for the Touching Experience”	185
5 CONCLUSION	192
<i>“I always felt like I was working for you”</i>	193
Reflections on Proper Distance in <i>With These Hands</i>	194
Contribution to the field of VR documentary studies and ethics	212
Concurrent Movements in the field and further implications and recommendations of this research	215
BIBLIOGRAPHY	222
LIST OF XR WORKS	251
APPENDIX i - Timeline and Funding Summary	253
APPENDIX ii - Ethics Documents	256

List of Figures

- Image 1. - The author trying VR for the first time, 2015*
- Image 2. - A contributor turns away from the 360 camera, October 2019*
- Image 3. - 180 image of a rock face, August 2019*
- Image 4. - Still from 'Passing' WIP, November 2018*
- Image 5. - Still from 'The OH Expedition' WIP, October 2019*
- Image 6. - Photogrammetry of Moss Asset for With These Hands, October 2022*
- Image 7. - Workshop Responses, April 2022*
- Image 8. - 'On the App' Chris's 'Peeled' Skin Diffuse Map, August 2022*
- Image 9. - 'On the App' Storyboard 1, March 2022*
- Image 10. - 'On the App' Storyboard 2, August 2022*
- Image 11. - 'On the App' Hand Scanning Process, August 2022*
- Image 12. - 'On the App' Final Scene, November 2022*
- Image 13. - 'Blueberry Muffin' Storyboard and Creative Assets, March - November 2022*
- Image 14. - 'Blueberry Muffin' Final Scene, November 2022*
- Image 15. - 'Hands Around A Coffee Cup' Storyboard and Creative Assets, March - November 2022*
- Image 16. - 'Place Your Hands in Mine' Storyboard and Final Scene, March - November 2022*
- Image 17. - With These Hands Installation Design and Final Installation (Image Credit Jurre Rompa),
November 2022*
- Image 18. - With These Hands Press Material (Image Credit Ned Pooler), November 2022*

List of Abbreviations

2D	Two Dimensional - Possessing two spatial dimensions of width and height.
360	Three Hundred and Sixty Degree - Used to describe VR content that is made with multiple cameras shooting in all directions. This is stitched together to create a panoramic sphere of video or still image. This can also describe drawn or computer generated content that creates a panoramic sphere image or video, as opposed to a 3D virtual environment.
3D	Three Dimensional - possessing three spatial dimensions of width, height and depth.
3DoF	Three Degrees of Freedom - VR environments and headset technologies which permits audiences three degrees of movement freedom in 360 environments on the three rotational axes; pitch, roll, and yaw.
6DoF	Six Degrees of Freedom - VR environments and headset technologies which permits audiences six degrees of movement freedom in 3D virtual environments, including the three dimensions; width, height and depth as well as the three rotational axes; pitch, roll, and yaw.
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CGI	Computer Generate Images
HMD	Head Mounted Display - a device worn on the head for viewing XR content. Most HMD use small, near eye video displays. MR headsets project visuals onto near eye lenses.
NGO	Nongovernmental Organisation - advocacy or service organisations in the nonprofit sector e.g. The International Committee of the Red Cross
Normal Map	3D models are made up of multiple polygon configurations. Codified lighting uses the geometry of these polygons. Complex shapes use more polygons and therefore use more computational bandwidth. Normal Maps are part of a 3D models texture that can simulate the appearance of more complex surface texture, without adding to the underlying geometry or polygon count. (Adobe, n.d.)
Photogrammetry	A technique that uses 2D photographs to create detailed, textured 3D models.
POV	Point of View - refers to the perspective or way of looking at something, often used in literature, film, and social media. In specifically a VR context, it implies the work recreates the first person subjective perspective on the world, as through the eyes or inside the body/ mind of a represented character.

R&D	Research and Development.
Unity	A 2D and 3D games engine and development platform used primarily for creating video games, interactive applications, simulations, and immersive experiences. Unity can import and assemble assets, including video and CG made items and generate interactive elements using code.
VR	Virtual Reality - A computer-generated simulation of a three-dimensional image or environment that can be interacted with in a seemingly real or physical way by a person using a head mounted display. Alternatively, a user might engage with the simulation through another interface, such as a Cave Automatic Virtual Environment (CAVE) which is a room with projections of the environment on 3 or more of the 6 wall surfaces (See Grau, 2003). Virtual Reality is used in common parlance to include 360 video experiences, however this use is contested (Laurel, 2016).
MR	Mixed Reality - Like AR (Augmented Reality), Mixed Reality experiences blend the real world of the user with 3D or other digital assets through a camera, projections on lenses or audio.
XR	Extended Reality - a group term for VR, AR & MR technologies.

Glossary

Audience	Throughout this text I will refer to the person or people engaging with a virtual experience as the 'Audience'. This in part is due to my academic background in the visual arts where this nomenclature is readily accepted and even proffered as superior to alternatives like 'viewer' for artworks in which there is some expectation of conceptual or physical interaction with the work (see Tate, n.d.). Academics researching VR coming from other disciplines, like Games or HCI, might similarly feel comfortable to use 'Player' or 'User'. However, within the Interactive and Virtual Reality documentary literature, there have been many arguments made for alternative terms that recognise the immersive, interactive and co-creational potential of these art forms such as 'Immersant' (Davies, 2005) or 'Interactor' /'actant' (Gaudenzi, 2013) or 'Agent' (Laurel, 1991). However, 'Audience' in art theory is already used to conjure a more expanded relationship with an artwork beyond the sight dominated implications of 'Viewer'. Etymologically, 'Audience' itself implies an auditory relationship with artwork; as both a listening and hearing. Crucially however, it further implies a proximity to an artwork or other listeners that provides "opportunity of being heard" (Online Etymology Dictionary, n.d. -c). It is this relational experience with an artwork implied by Audience, combined with the reflections in this thesis on the relations between hearing, listening, touching and understanding that I suggest justify its use in the context.
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1 INTRODUCTION

Image 1 - The Author trying VR for the first time, 2015

“Dragged slowly and inexorably forward”

A conference room had been repurposed as a Virtual Reality cinema. On the walls were pinned promotional posters with images of a headset; sleek and futuristic and surrounded by mist. I had imagined VR would feel very high-tech, and was surprised the headset was just a phone in a plastic holder with an awkward velcro head strap. I held it to my face.

I was ‘walking’, or rather being dragged slowly and inexorably forward down a kind of ‘street’ in what I understood immediately to be a refugee camp. I had a slightly higher vantage point on this world than my body normally allows, and this, combined with the fact that when I looked down I had no body, gave me the impression I was a floating ghost. I knew this was a refugee camp based on images in the news. Plastic tarps were haphazardly shaped into small dwellings on either side of me, lining this ‘street’, a bare strip of dusty ground in between them. In my memory, this strip stretched out as far as I could see in front and behind me. Other people were walking the street, weaving in and out of the tarpaulins. I was experiencing at once many disparate sensations. Most pressingly, I was feeling a sense of amazement at how convincing the optical illusion was. I felt almost joyous at the sensation that I was actually in this place. This was juxtaposed with a more proprioceptive sensation that I was not physically walking down this street, but sat spinning in a conference room chair. In fact, when I peeked downward, I could still see that reality, beyond this virtual one, bleeding in through the gaps between the headset and my face. I also felt a little scared. I remember feeling like this was a strange place for me to be with no forewarning, and that if I ever were compelled to visit a refugee camp, I would do more to prepare than just turn up and walk the streets alone. I wondered if the people passing around me also felt scared, or if these streets would seem more banal to them. I had a sense that my horror at being suddenly, virtually, dumped in this place, while certainly not greater than the horror of actually living there, was considerably different. I didn't feel like I knew what it must be like for them. I felt like me, transported, dropped there and pushed along. It felt both exciting and unpleasant. No narration or voice over accompanied this 4 minute or so video, or if there was, the physical experience was so visceral that it occludes my memory of it. What I do remember was the sheer scale of this camp. My feeling present there allowing me to measure this scale - and the number of bodies living there - against my own.

A picture exists of me in the headset, as before I had 'gone in' to VR I had asked my housemate to take one because I thought it would look cool. I remember feeling it was strange to try and make a piece of work that was so dusty and serious in a device that felt so futuristic and plastic, and screen it in a venue that felt so corporate. It also seemed incongruous to make a piece of work about the terrible fact that millions live in such insecurity around the world inside this device that also felt so entertaining and amazing. When I came home I went on YouTube to see what else I could watch on its new 360 video feature¹. I found a lot of other documentaries about refugee camps and a lot of POV recordings of rollercoaster rides.

Background to Practice

When called to present parts of this PhD research in public forums I comfortably use the term 'documentary' when describing its practice artefact. It feels less comfortable, however, to describe myself as a 'documentarian'. In an academic setting, I might describe myself as an artist; at a film festival, as a researcher; in an artist talk I might say "I'm not really an artist, but a producer, I'm the one who brings things together". This resistance to definition is not, I hope, a form of imposter syndrome, but a more constructive resistance to a prescriptive definition of my practice, which is not one or the other of these interwoven activities nor an expertise in any, but a sum of their parts.

During my undergraduate degree in Fine Art and Art History, completed in 2014, my studio practice was predominantly multimedia installations. I was interested in autobiographical re-enactment, and the potential to restage my memories as 'reliveable' for audiences. Using projection mapping and sensory sculpture, I would create room scale vignettes audiences could move through or around, touch or be present within. My undergraduate thesis presented these works as a form of expanded documentary practice.

In 2015, I attended a Virtual Reality (VR) showcase and the work I experienced there remains prominent in my memory. I understood immediately that this medium was engaging with some of the same questions as my undergraduate work: what does the audience's feeling of 'being there' bring to the documentation of 'real' events? It also raised substantially more, like: What are the ethics of 'being there' when 'there' is not the maker's own memories shared, but the

¹ YouTube introduced its 360 video viewing and uploading feature in March, 2015 (Steele, 2015)

experience of someone else - a documentary subject? How do I, as an audience member, reconcile my pleasure in the illusion of presence in a place where I am not, when the place I am taken to is one where people are experiencing pain or suffering. *Especially* when, in such 'refugee' VR experiences², that pain and suffering is at least in part due to their actual presence in the place that I take pleasure in visiting virtually. In other words, how do I contend with my ability to remotely travel through the wonder of virtual reality, when the people's lives recorded therein are typified by their inability to travel freely and at will? Despite my ethical reservations about content, I was also inspired by this experience, the medium and how it made me feel. For the next 3 years I worked as a venue manager, producer and curator of VR events and exhibitions, and began experimenting and developing my own 360 filmmaking practice. However, I did not forget my first disquieting VR experience, nor the ethical questions it left me with.

This period, 2015 - 2018, was the era of 'The Empathy Machine'. This description of VR documentary, now much maligned (Robertson, 2017), abounded at festivals and exhibitions, and was often met, even then, with eyerolls from makers and audiences present. In remembering this moment I feel called to reference Sara Ahmed's suggestion that eyerolls are in fact a form of feminist pedagogy (Ahmed, 2023, pg 24). The original call for this practice based PhD in 2018 proposed the task of 'Exploring the Empathy Machine'³. Part of my desire to undertake this period of research was not only to progress my own VR documentary practice, but to attempt to understand the persistent 'stickiness' of 'empathy' to VR, despite observing this industry and audience resistance. Through practice, I hoped I might begin to answer some of my earlier questions, and to challenge the troubling dynamics implied in a 'machine' through which "we become more compassionate, we become more empathetic, we become more connected and ultimately, we become more human" (Milk, 2015).

Beyond my academic background, and skills as a maker and producer of VR, I bring to this PhD a wealth of exposure to trends in VR and XR documentary from my time as a curator and programmer. Working as a VR host⁴ and venue manager I have had the opportunity to train

² A genre that, as I will discuss, emerges alongside the developing medium.

³ (*Exploring the Empathy Machine: a practice-based investigation of the potential of Virtual Reality for the creation of immersive documentary experiences*, 2018)

⁴ Many terms are used to describe the person that on-boards and off-boards a VR user into an experience. For ease, I refer to them in all instances as 'hosts'.

hundreds of volunteers and usher collectively thousands audience members through VR experiences. In particular, in my work with leading UK VR cinema and research organisation Limina Immersive, and as producer and access support to VR artist and director Jane Gauntlett, there has been a focus on access, and supporting underrepresented audience demographics to experience VR for the first time. I have greatly benefited from observing these audiences around and inside of the VR headset, and have also often been the first person they speak to upon exiting. These countless impromptu conversations, although not conducted in an academic context, have been essential to my understanding of VR as a medium. Although I don't recount these interactions within this text, I do recite my own memories of various VR experiences and exhibitions over the past 8 years. My hope is that by including these in the text I can bring various voices into dialogue, from lay audience member to a more intentioned maker, and illustrate how these varying perspectives have informed my practice and my attention to audience and contributor duty of care.

Background to Inquiry: VR as an Empathy Machine

After decades of technological and conceptual development, in the last 10 years VR has become a commercial reality⁵, if not quite a commercial success⁶. As predicted, but never attained during earlier 'waves' of technological, commercial and academic attention, VR has been adopted in multiple industries; from gaming and communication, to manufacture and healthcare (Slater & Sanchez-Vives, 2016). More unexpectedly however, the last decade saw VR heralded as a frontier for documentary (Rose, 2018a).

An 'immersive' medium, VR uniquely explodes the 'frame' of traditional cinematic documentary making (Milk, 2015; Uricchio, 2016; Nash, 2020). The promise of VR immersion, and its affordances of presence, embodiment, agency and interactivity, is that audiences no longer *watch* a documentary through the window of the screen's frame, but *experience* it "first hand" (Peña et al, 2010). VR "feels like life..feels like truth" (Milk, 2015) and is therefore posed as a natural extension of a documentary tradition concerned with depicting truth, reality and

⁵ At point of writing Quest 2 headsets sell currently for just under £200 and Quest 3 just under £500 (*Meta Quest VR Headsets, Accessories and Equipment* | Meta Quest, n.d.).

⁶ There has been a notable gap between VR industry reported growth projections and the 'on the ground' experience of VR as yet to 'take off' or even as 'dead' (see Katatikarn, 2024; Whiteman, 2024; Zitron, 2023)

“actuality”⁷. A range of emerging VR technologies; from state of the art headset sensor systems to headsets made from cardboard and smartphones, 360 camera rigs, 3D capture technologies, games engine and CGI animated production were taken up by journalists, documentary makers and artists and turned toward representing the world's most urgent humanitarian issues. Commercial VR's emergence in 2015-2016 coincided with the “peak” of the “migration crisis” (European Parliament, 2017)⁸, and a large number of early works aimed to immerse viewers in the experiences of displaced people across the globe. Examples range from more traditional humanitarian media content, such the United Nations commissioned *Clouds Over Sidra* (2015), shot on location with 360 cameras, to fully animated and interactive experiences such as Aardman's docufiction *We Wait* (2016) in which audiences accompany a group of refugees on an ill fated night boat crossing into Europe. In many works of this moment, it is VR's ability to facilitate presence (the feeling of being-there) and/or co-presence (the feeling of being-with or meeting contributors, real or animated) that appears to most engage audiences (see Rose & Green, 2021), and is the main focus of ample hype for VR as a documentary medium (see Bishop, 2013 & Constantine, 2015). In his Ted Talk *How Virtual Reality Can Create the Ultimate Empathy Machine* (2015), Chris Milk somewhat defines this genre of VR content through reference to his own work *Clouds Over Sidra*, a 360 documentary in which audiences ‘meet’ 12 year old Syrian refugee, Sidra:

You're not sitting watching it through a television screen, you're not watching it through a window. You're sitting there with her. When you look down, you're sitting on the same ground that she's sitting on, and because of that, you feel her humanity in a deeper way. You empathise with her in a deeper way. (Milk, 2015)

Praise of VR's potential as a documentary medium has broadly referenced the histories of media witnessing, and proposed that VR enhances the audience's ability to ‘bear witness’ to distant suffering (Nash, 2018; Gregory, 2016). ‘Media witnessing’ has been variously conceptualised as a media form, and the moral justification or ‘moral affordance’ (Frosh, 2018 p. 4) of documenting distant suffering for more privileged audiences. In witnessing, audiences can no longer claim ignorance of events - “we cannot say we didn't know” - but further, are

⁷ John Grierson's famously vague definition of documentary as “the creative treatment of actuality” (Cousins & Macdonald, 2006).

⁸ I want to acknowledge here that the term ‘crisis’ is culturally loaded (The Elders, 2016) .

imbued with the “aching sense that something must be done” (Ellis, 2000, p. 11). By ‘bearing witness’ to these images we ‘pay heed’ to the significance of atrocities (Zelizer, 2022. p. 10), potentially developing a sense of responsibility as we ‘locate’ our ‘privileges’ “on the same map as their suffering” (Sontag, 2003 pg. 92) and further, might be compelled to share and speak about what has been seen (Tait, 2011; Boltanski, 2004). Presence - the feeling of ‘being there’ - is imperative to witnessing, as ‘to witness’ implies spatial and temporal proximity to an event, and direct, first hand experience of it. ‘Witnessing Media’ permit forms of ‘presence-at-a-distance’ (Peters, 2011, pg. 717) allowing audiences to feel in some way ‘close’ to an event in time or space (Frosh & Pinchevski, pg 13). Conversely, the more distant people are to an event in time and space, the more difficult it is to sustain a feeling of moral responsibility (Nash, 2020, pg 122). VR, in facilitating feelings of presence and co-presence in documented spaces and events far beyond traditional ‘framed’, ‘flat’ media, becomes a potentially powerful tool for ‘immersive witnessing’ (Gregory, 2016).

VR ‘feels’ like being geographically present in a documented space *and* simulates the live-ness of ‘meeting’ a documentary contributor. VR “produces an illusion of first hand, experiential knowledge” (Nash, 2022 p. 106), and VR audiences appear in reportage to “experience a story as if they lived it” (Google Media Lab, 2017)⁹. The promotion of VR on the basis it facilitates a ‘first hand’ experience of news events is congruous with growing public distrust of mainstream media and/or ‘fake news’ and a more general cultural trend toward ‘first person’ media which privileges autobiographical, subjective and emotional testimony over experts and abstracted authoritative voice overs (Dovey, 2000). Additionally, audiences’ *feelings* toward content become more important in their assessment of ‘truth’ in a culture of “growing epistemic suspicion” (Nash, 2020, p. 106; see also van Zoonan, 2012; Dahlgreen, 2018). A more extraordinary claim proposed by enthusiasts of VR for documentary, news and journalism is that VR presence not only grants audiences proximity to the ‘sights and sounds’ of the distant suffering of documented others, but possibly “the feelings and emotions that accompany the news” (de la Peña et al, 2010. P. 291).

VR technology can produce a sense of embodiment, or the ‘feeling of ownership’, of a virtually represented body (Slater et al, 2009b) and “transforms not only people's sensation of place and

⁹ To the extent that google media lab and others have proposed to replace the term ‘storytelling’ in reference to VR in favour of ‘storyliving’ (Google News Lab, 2017) or ‘storydoing’ (Allen, 2017).

reality, but also themselves” (de la Peña et al, 2010 p. 295). By ‘entering the body’ of a documentary subject one might further understand their experience by knowing “how they feel” (de la Peña et al, 2010, p. 298). To some, this novel form of ‘knowing’ the news or “embodied rhetoric” is *the* promise of VR journalism (de la Peña, 2015b). Even without a representational virtual body, VR experiences can invoke bodily responses - “a rush of adrenaline, racing heart-beat and tensing muscles” (Nash, 2020 p. 105) and as such it is a medium primed to communicate more embodied or experiential kinds of knowing (Rose, 2018b).

Preliminary surveys have sketched out a number of audience subject positions prevalent in VR documentary, from more observational ‘tourist’ like positions, to ‘witnessing’ an event such as *We Wait* (2016) or ‘encountering’ or ‘meeting’ a contributor and hearing their testimony, like *Clouds Over Sidra* (2015). There are also works in which audiences embody a documentary contributor, including work from VR pioneer Nonny de la Peña in which audiences ‘enter the body’ of an avatar representing a Guantanamo Bay detainee in a stress position (de la Peña et al, 2010). Alternatively, by using point of view 360 video, writer/ director Jane Gauntlett invites audiences to observe a dramatisation of the moments before and after an epileptic seizure as if ‘through her eyes’ in autobiographical documentary *Dancing with Myself* (2016). There are also works in which audiences are not embodied as contributor, but are encouraged to engage with the VR environment as imaginatively *in place* of the contributor. An example would be the Guardian’s *6X9: A Virtual Experience of Solitary Confinement* (2016) in which audiences hear the testimony of prisoners from within a virtual cell, whilst experiencing simulations of visual and auditory hallucinations¹⁰. Many works span multiple subject positions or feature moments of shift from one position to another. For example; one does have a virtual body in *We Wait* although are not cast specifically as a character (Steed et al, 2018); *Clouds Over Sidra* is at moments more observational, offering a ‘tourist’ gaze focusing on the refugee camp as a location, and in other scenes the user is addressed by or ‘meets’ Sidra (Nash, 2020); in it’s closing moments, *Dancing With Myself* shifts audiences from ‘inside’ Jane’s body at a restaurant table, to facing her across the table, as if in conversation with her.

¹⁰ Here I have broadly used the non-exhaustive subject positions outlined by Kate Nash (2020). However other surveys have been executed and divide subject positions further or in different arrangements for example if audience can make change in environments through interactivity or not (Bevan et al, 2019) or if audience see a ‘re-visualisation of testimony’ as much of de la Peña’s work might be categorised, or a more original piece of content designed to grant audiences a ‘Perspective Shift’, such as Gauntlett’s work (Limina Immersive & Tucker, 2018).

Beyond the capacity of traditional witnessing media, 'immersive witnessing' offers opportunities for 'self-other hybridity' with documented contributors (Nash, 2020 p. 115). Audiences are encouraged to feel 'closer' to documentary contributors, emotionally and through a shared direct experience. The work attempts to communicate more comprehensively the subjective experience of the contributor by immersing audiences in 'what it's like' in their environment, experience or body. The affordance of 'immersive witnessing', and its explicit focus on 'feeling', is that it might foster deeper forms of understanding between audiences and contributors than a 'windowed', two dimensional media can produce. Chris Milk enduringly claimed this made VR 'an empathy machine', in doing so cementing an almost indelible association between VR documentary and the amorphous pro-social phenomena of Empathy.

Empathy is commonly understood as "the ability to understand and share the feelings of another" (Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, n.d.) which might involve "imagining what it would be like to be in that person's position" (Cambridge Dictionary, n.d.) or more colloquially to 'put oneself in their shoes'. Beyond these common parlance definitions however, there is no refined academic consensus on a definition of 'Empathy' across sociological, psychological, neurological or other discourses (Pagotto, 2010; Batson 2009). Empathy is, therefore, not a distinct concept, but a byword for a range of ideas and processes of 'feeling about', 'feeling for', or 'feeling into' artwork and others and subsequent pro-social action. Milk's own Ted Talk fails to define the word, and presents a number of different configurations of the relationship between VR and Empathy which rely on varying definitions of the phenomena.

Despite the vagueness of what the claim that 'VR is an Empathy Machine' actually means, the phrase pervades the VR documentary landscape almost *ad nauseam* (Robertson, 2017). Most prominently, claims of 'empathy' are cited as evidence that VR documentary and by extension, VR itself, is a tool 'for good' (*VR for Good: Virtual Reality Storytelling Focused on Social Impact*, n.d.). The dominance of the 'Empathy Machine' conception of VR, and its value as a witnessing medium, has perhaps hampered exploration and discussion of other documentary genres and audience experiences that VR might offer (Rose, 2018b).

Focus of Inquiry: Gaps for Practice Based Research

The proposed task of this PhD studentship was to ‘explore the empathy machine’ through practice. Certainly there are multiple avenues for practice based exploration proffered in the above brief summary of discourse. As an artist and producer however, I was particularly interested in the frequent and uncritical repetition within discourse of ‘empathy’, not only as a claimed de-facto product of VR as a documentary medium, but also as the unquestionable goal of all documentary production, and not a concept subject to ethical critique itself (Bloom, 2016). More specifically, I was interested in the ethics of the relations between audiences and contributors implied by ‘a machine’ through which “we become more empathetic..more connected and ultimately we become more human” (Milk, 2015) and within works being produced and exhibited with reference to ‘empathy’ at that time. My research proposal quickly narrowed to explore the ethical implications of representing documentary contributors within a medium which ‘feels’ so ‘unmediated’ (Lombard & Ditton, 1997; Bolter & Grusin, 2000) that it might be better understood “*not as a media experience but as an actual experience*” (Bailenson, 2018 p. 46, italics in original). This inquiry can be further divided into the ethical implications for contributors and for audiences that must both be contended with as a maker.

Ethical Representation of VR Documentary Contributors

The promotion of VR documentary as a tool of media witnessing has resulted in what might be understood as an ‘empathy machine’ genre of VR documentary, with tropes for representing contributors as recipients of empathy. This results in a preoccupation with documenting contributors’ suffering, and/or their resilience in the face of suffering, in order to engender empathy and compassion from a presumed more privileged audience.

‘The Empathy Machine’ conception of VR further promotes that VR’s ability to produce presence and the illusion of direct experience can grant audiences a perspective on documentary content *akin to the subjective experience of documentary contributors*, either by ‘being there’ ‘with’ them or being there ‘as’ them (Nash, 2020 p. 107).

There are examples of VR documentary that, while permitting audiences ‘direct experience’ of ‘what it’s like’ to be another, focus’ less suffering in favour of ‘sharing’ or ‘swapping’ experience - such as Marshmallow Laser Feast’s *In The Eyes of the Animal* (2015), or the live body swap

experiments of the *BeAnotherLab* (*BeAnotherLab*, n.d.). Conversely, there are works of VR documentary that address suffering without appealing to an interpersonal definition of 'empathy' as literally occupying the position or perspective of another, and that further avoid proffering individual victims to represent systemic or institutionalised violence, such as Eli Aslami's *Death Tolls Experience* (2015) (see also Lannin, 2017). However, the majority of academic and industry discourse, as well as cultural hype, around the potential of VR documentary is its ability to bring audiences into closer alignment with the specific 'point of view' of another. As such when documenting global injustice or humanitarian issues, there has been a prevalence of representing and further 'making experienceable' specific and individual instances of suffering for audiences in service to empathetic understanding (Gregory, 2016).

Much headset industry led discourse on VR documentary uncritically promotes the inherent moral goodness of virtual reality technology based on this 'empathetic' potential (Yang, 2017). This is in line with wider VR industry narratives around the technology itself "as an agent of human advancement, human betterment and life enhancement" (Rose, 2018b). Milk's (2015) talk infers it is through the technological competence of the VR 'machine' that empathy is generated. However, the texts that outline media witnessing do not conclude the form or associated technology unequivocally or unproblematically possesses inherent moral value (Frosh & Pinchevski, 2009, p. 12). Many of the fundamental texts on the moral implications of creating and consuming images of distant suffering highlight the inherent 'fragility' of the moral responsibility engendered through media witnessing (Nash, 2018, p. 122). Does viewing images of suffering *always* inspire a sense of audience responsibility? A sense that something 'must be done'? Or are there alternate impulses behind their creation; as tools of historicization, propaganda, or simply is there some kind of pleasure in viewing or struggling to look at such images ("there is the satisfaction of being able to look at the image without flinching. There is the pleasure of flinching" - Sontag, 2003, p. 37)? Is there a difference between feelings of sympathy or commiseration for the misfortune of others and a sense of outrage at that suffering which sparks direct action and protest (Sontag, pp .36 -38)? Does the proliferation of images of suffering lead to forms of apathy - "confirm that this is the sort of thing that happens in that place" and the ubiquity of images of *some* bodies suffering, say, migrating bodies in the global south "cannot help but nourish the belief in the inevitability of tragedy in the benighted or backward - that is, poor - parts of the world" (Sontag, p. 64)? Does the proliferation of such

images, suffused within a culture of 'spectacle' in which we are simultaneously bombarded with all other manner of images lead to a deficit of attention and motivation for change ("the implication is no: it cannot be stopped - and the mingling with attentive and inattentive onlookers underscores this" (Sontag, p. 38)?

Certainly some have argued that VR documentary uniquely commands audiences attention in the saturated landscape of the contemporary 'attention economy', but have divided on whether this is due to "restitut[ion of] the audience's emotional involvement in current events" (de la Peña et al, 2010) or simply because the VR headset itself blocks users ability to view any other content simultaneously, an increasingly a more rarified form of media consumption (Uricchio 2016). Beyond this, advocates for VR documentary as an empathy generating media have for the most part neglected to address wider ethical questions around witnessing media in favour of more simplistic formulations - "empathy is good, and VR facilitates empathy, so therefore VR is good - - no questions please" (Yang, 2017). Empathy serves as an "all-encompassing (but misleading) rejoinder to any criticisms of voyeurism or exploitation" (Uricchio et al 2016 p. 18). Depictions of contributors in VR documentaries within the 'empathy machine' genre can easily be compared to the 'poor, suffering' victims of the Griersonian documentary tradition, a practice that has long been problematised in wider documentary discourse (Winston, 1998).

Ethical Relations between Audiences and Content

There are further ethical questions that emerge when VR is uncritically adopted as a tool for media witnessing, as the experiential and embodied nature of VR significantly changes the *quality* of this witnessing. Arguments for the moral affordance of media witnessing are based on mediums which permits audiences access to 'something of the event' (Ellis, 2011, p. 128) mediated, for the most part, by the 'window' of the screen. As Milk puts it, VR places audiences "through the window..on the other side, in the world, inhabiting the world" (Milk, 2015) and 'living' the story (Google News Lab, 2017) and as such profoundly obfuscates or 'disappears' the experience of 'mediation' (Riva, 1999 p. 91).

Academic research has shown users engage with virtual environments as they would if 'really' present - or 'respond-as-if-real' (Slater et al, 2009). Unlike screen based media's 'presence-at-a-distance', the presence engendered by VR is experienced as "truly 'natural',

'immediate', 'direct' and 'real'". VR is a "mediated experience that seems very much like it's not mediated" (Lombard and Ditton, 1997, p. 1). As such VR goes beyond communicating 'something of the event' to *simulating* that event, and any documentary contributors within. Although this can be brought into dialogue with audiences' relation to more traditional witnessing texts (See Nash, 2018, expanding on Frosh, 2011's 'imaginative world building') it poses profound ethical questions about both audience experience and contributor representation. Interactive documentary scholar Kate Nash (2018) suggests that the simulative quality of VR documentary, particularly work within the broad 'empathy machine' genre, prioritises the user's own experience of transportation and exploration of 'what it's like' within the documentation of contributor's environment and/or experience, at the expense of attention to contributor's own testimony:

There is an inherent tension between attention to the other and the experience of transportation. The effect is to encourage a profound turning away from the speaking subject (Nash, 2018, p. 128)

This transportation is not only spatial, but emotional. Advocates for VR as an empathy machine like Milk and de la Peña take as evidence audiences emotional responses inside their work - "they were affected" (Milk, 2015), "I started seeing these really intense, authentic reactions from people that really blew my mind" (de la Peña, 2015a). An audience member crying when exiting a headset is an image often conjured by those promoting VR documentary as a tool of empathy (see also de la Peña, 2015a). Nash asserts that just as the draw to visual exploration in VR documentaries encourages a physical turning away from a speaking subject, literally and conceptually, attempts to heighten audience emotion act much the same way (Nash, 2018). Audiences are encouraged to focus more on how it *feels to them*, rather than listening to how it feels for the other. Sam Gregory uses the term 'self expressive witnessing' to discuss the relation between 'Empathy Machine' VR documentary content and some forms of contemporary humanitarianism which proffer "the emotionality of the donor, rather than the vulnerability of the distant other, as a key motivation for solidarity" (Chouliaraki cited in Gregory, 2016, see also Chouliaraki, 2011 and Ahmed, 2004 pp. 20-41). More scathingly, this is described by Lisa Nakamura as providing VR documentary audiences opportunities for "feeling good about feeling bad" (Nakamura, 2020).

Milk's definition of a "machine..through which we become more empathetic" could also be read as presenting the *development* of empathy as an *end in itself*. This is echoed in discussion about the increased use of the term Empathy in political discourse of the early 2010's, exemplified by Obama's public speaking and writing. In these texts, Empathy is presented as a skill, or a form of personal development, rather than as precursor to further other-oriented action (see Pedwell, 2012).

Digital artist Robert Yang has described the preoccupation with empathy within VR documentary discourse and media as 'appropriative', and "fundamentally about mining the experiences of suffering people to enrich the self-image of VR users..or, even worse... to enrich the cultural appeal of VR brands". He questions "Do you really need to wear a VR headset in order to empathize with someone? Can't you just fucking listen to them and believe them? You need to be entertained as well? Are you sure this isn't about you?" and concludes "if you won't believe someone's pain unless they wrap an expensive 360 video around you, then perhaps you don't actually care about their pain" (Yang, 2017). In his scathing review, Yang raises important questions that VR makers engaging in representation of contributors and their experiences must contend with¹¹. Not only that audiences may be engaging with simulative content based on contributors' real lives in a self oriented or self expressive manner, but a further question around the ethics of simulating someone's suffering in order to verify it. He further suggests a relationship between this and appropriation; defined as "the act of taking something that belongs to someone else, especially without permission" (Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, n.d. -b) and originates etymologically from *ad-proprius* 'to make one's own' (Online Etymology Dictionary, n.d. -b). He further questions if experiencing a simulation of suffering could ever lead to *appropriate* (and non-appropriative) other-oriented action? If indeed that is the goal of this form of content, which Yang himself is evidently sceptical of.

These provocations propose an investigation into what (if any) audience subject positions might utilise VR's simulative potential and yet resist audiences self-oriented engagement with content.

¹¹ Yang himself makes interactive simulation games in which audiences engage in forms of enactment of queer and gay culture such as cottaging, spanking or aftercare which have been (mis) described as 'gay simulators' or simulation games for "straight people to understand what being gay is like" (Yang, 2017; 2015) and therefore also engages with these questions as a maker.

In other words, how might VR's affordances of presence, agency and embodiment facilitate listening and attendance to the subjective and distinct experience of a represented contributor, rather than encouraging audiences appropriate that experience by 'making it their own'.

Ethical Relations between Audiences and Contributors: The Risk of Improper Distance
 Questions about the appropriate relations between contributors and their virtual representation, audiences and virtual content, and ultimately, audience and contributors are encompassed within Kate Nash's (2018) articulation of 'The Risk of Improper Distance' posed by VR documentary. She suggests that VR's "ability to foster a moral response to distant others is neither impossible nor guaranteed, rather that it depends on the way that VR experiences are designed" (Nash, 2018, p. 120) and that therefore VR makers must not merely assume the moral affordance of VR as 'witnessing' media, but consider it "comes with an inherent moral risk: the risk of 'improper distance'" (Nash, 2018, p. 120).

Media theorist Roger Silverstone (2007) outlines proximity and distance as moral categories of representation. A moral response to media, for Silverstone, relies on one feeling close enough to a represented other to feel a sense of moral obligation or responsibility toward them, yet permits enough distance to appreciate the limits of representation and our ability to share in, understand or 'know' the full experience of others. 'Proper' (or in other words 'ethical') 'distance' is the balance of the two, "in which the relationship between proximity and distance is mediated by an effective measure of understanding, care and responsibility" (Silverstone, 2007 p. 117).

VR, particularly the empathy machine genre that relies on replicating in some way the contributors 'point of view', poses particular 'risks' of improper distance because of its 'illusion of non mediation' (Lombard & Ditton, 1997). In works in which the subjective experience of the represented contributor is proposed to be simulated for the audience, that contributor is at risk of becoming 'indistinguishable from ourselves' (Nash, 2018, p.120; Silverstone, 2007 p. 172). VR content can feel so 'real', "like truth.. like life", (Milk, 2015), that audiences can feel *too close* to the subject and the contributor, over-identifying with them and their experience in ways that are potentially objectifying and appropriative. In work that permits an embodiment-as-contributor, or as-if-contributor, audiences are encouraged to identify with the

contributor so profoundly that the experience they focus on becomes 'their own', thus the media risks erasing the alterity of the contributor completely.

In content in which audiences 'meet' or are 'with' a contributor, the illusion of non mediation prohibits a critical apprehension of the constructed nature of their representation. Within the history of documentary, particularly from makers informed by feminist and de-colonial theory, 'reflexive' practices are utilised to dispel any ambitions of capturing 'true' likeness of contributors, in both a material and political sense (Nichols, 1991 pp. 56 - 68). In a material sense, reflexive practices draw attention to both the material process of filmmaking, and the wider construction of meaning through the formal apparatus of the documentary, thus bringing into question the indexicality of image to reality. In a political sense, bringing awareness to the construction of meaning within the documentary form can be extrapolated to the socio-political sphere. Reflexive filmmaking aims to bring audience awareness to how dominant ideologies are embedded within and perpetuated by media narratives (Nichols, 1991, pp. 63-68). Alternatively, in simply producing representations of contributors that refuse to conform to 'iconographic norms' for depicting, for example, women, documentaries can achieve politically reflexive aims by undermining, laying bare or 'making strange' patriarchal ideology and challenging audiences "assumptions about life" (Elizabeth Anne Kaplan quoted in Nichols, 1991, p. 68).

VR documentaries could potentially be reflexive in both a material and political sense. VR fundamentally destabilises traditional 'windowed' documentary methods of constructing meaning, as audiences within virtual environments or 360 videos are presented an image within which "the possibility of any masterful gaze feels somewhat undone" (Frilot & King, 2017). This opens potential for VR to produce more 'activated' viewing subjects, in line with other 'immersive' mediums such as Installation art.

The need to move around and through in order to experience [the artwork] *activates* the viewer, in contrast to art that simply requires optical contemplation (which is considered to be passive and detached). This activation is, moreover, regarded as emancipatory, since it is analogous to the viewer's engagement in the world. A transitive relationship therefore comes to be implied between 'activated spectatorship' and active engagement in the social-political arena. (Bishop, 2005 p. 11)

In making artwork that has no fixed viewing perspective, the artist might imply that there is no one 'right' way, 'privileged position' or 'central point' with which to look and make judgements about the world or artwork. Art historian and critic Claire Bishop (2005) suggests this reading of immersive installations "has had particular influence on the writing of art critics sympathetic to feminist and postcolonial theory, who argue fantasies of 'centering' perpetuated by dominant ideology are masculinist, racist and conservative" (Bishop, p. 13). The 'decentering' of the viewer, and dominant ideology, as achieved within the immersive installation space could certainly be possible in interactive VR environment which permits audiences six degrees of movement freedom (6DoF)¹².

Furthermore, VR's potential to "engage embodied knowledge" and as a "technology of corporeality" (Rose, 2018a) propose it as a medium through which to explore and expand existing 'embodied' and 'haptic' reflexive strategies. Feminist, decolonial and 'intercultural' filmmaking has drawn on the 'proprioceptive', 'embodied' and 'haptic' potential of 2D media to "raise ontological questions about the truth of photographic representations" (Marks, 2000, p. 172) and undermine the 'totalizing quest for meaning' of the western filmmaking endeavour (Trihn, 1990). However, as Mandy Rose (2018a) notes, contemporary cinematic VR, particularly work relying on the moral affordance of witnessing, attempts to "foster an impression of documentary material as unmediated reality", to "offer the participant a sense of unmediated access to locations and social worlds" of documentary contributors (Rose, 2018a p.112) thus operates on "the pretence of totality, in which the image can fully recreate another's experience" (Bollmer, 2017 p. 69). Ultimately this "illusionistic agenda" of the 'empathy machine' genre impedes more "critical response[s] from the viewer" (Rose, 2018a, p. 112).

Summary of Research

VR is a rapidly developing platform for documentary making which requires urgent interdisciplinary research, particularly from practitioners (Rose, 2018a). This PhD is formulated from the outset as 'Practice Based', where "not only is practice embedded in the research process but questions arise from the process of practice" and "the making process itself leads

¹² It is perhaps less conceptually viable in 360 video, compromised by the technology as recording 360 degrees *from a central point*.

to a transformation in the ideas - which in turn leads to new works” (Candy & Edmonds, 2018, p. 64; see also Candy, 2006). Within this method of enquiry, the creation of artwork is “the centre of the [research] project, at the heart of its method, and as its primary manifestation” (Price, 2021). VR and interactive documentary ethics are an expansive area of research, within which this research project sits. More specifically, this research aims to articulate and develop strategies to uphold ‘proper’ or ‘ethical’ distance[s] within production of VR documentaries, as demonstrated through practice.

Research Questions

Practice based research has been described by professor Tara Brabazon (2020) as “throwing a rock in a pond”, the creation of the practice based artefact presenting as a conceptual “leap” beyond articulated theory. “The goal of the exegesis is to connect the shoreline – the limitations of knowledge - with the object thrown in advance of knowledge” the artefact (Brabazon et al, 2022, p. 52). Practitioner researcher Susan Kozel suggests that practice based inquiry can be guided by a sense or feeling that a research question is present and explorable within material, if not yet fully articulated in words, or what she describes as the ‘trace of a question’. She further suggests “the affective state that drives us to research can be euphoria, desire, repulsion, outrage or a sort of discomfort similar to an itch”, “akin to the creepy compulsion to turn over a rock” (Kozel, 2010 pp. 209-210). This thesis is guided by my own uneasiness at the model of audience - contributor relations presented by ‘a machine that makes us more empathetic’ (Milk, 2015) and associated works in the Empathy Machine genre. The ‘shoreline’ of this research is Nash’s articulation of ‘The Risk of Improper Distance’, but tracing the ‘trajectory’ of my practice required engaging with a supporting methodology that might allow me to identify ‘proper distances’ as they emerged in my making and to further allow descriptive language to further articulate the early ‘traces’ of research questions. My first question might be more concretely defined as:

Q.1 How might I recognise, describe and evaluate ‘proper’ or ‘improper’ distances as they emerge within my own and others VR documentary practice?

Through parallel activities of making and reading I became particularly interested in critical phenomenology and particularly ‘Queer Phenomenology’ as a descriptive methodological

experiment presented by Sara Ahmed. Queer Phenomenology as a methodology not only as illustrated in her 2006 book of the same name, but building on her prior publications *Strange Encounters: Embodied Others in Post-Coloniality* (2000), *The Cultural Politics of Emotion* (2004) and other essays.

Phenomenology is broadly a methodology of description, attendant to embodied experience. Queer Phenomenology is the “queering” of the phenomenological method and the moving of queer, feminist and decolonial theory “toward phenomenology” (Ahmed, 2006, p. 5). Queer Phenomenology, in articulating how bodies ‘orient’ and ‘extend’ into space, and accounting for the political implication of this movement, provides invaluable descriptive language with which to articulate ‘proper distance’ within practice. Ahmed’s Queer Phenomenology, with its inclusion of feminist, decolonial and queer ‘perspectives’, is particularly suited to articulate the power relations of the proximities, distances and ‘profound turning away[s]’ of the empathy machine conception of VR. The introduction of Queer Phenomenology to ‘the risk of improper distance’ expands the concept of ‘distance’ from the 2 dimensional axis; of being too close or too far (literally and conceptually) to the documentary subject. It suggests further questions of proper *orientation*; *towards* what is the audience oriented and conversely *from* what position are audiences centred around, and proper *extension*; what is the VR user permitted *to do* in space and what are the political and ethical ramifications of this. Additionally, Ahmed uses queered ‘perspectives’¹³ to challenge prior phenomenological methods that pretend to an a-historical and a-political ‘view from nowhere’. Similarly, Queer Phenomenology can be used to interrogate the constructed VR ‘first person’ view, and the political and ethical implications of its pretence of ‘unauthored’ ‘unmediated’ reality.

Queer Phenomenology was employed early in the research process as an answer to this first more descriptive question.

Working out from gaps in existing research that a practice based enquiry might respond to, my second and third research questions can be articulated as:

Q.2 What methods of VR design can support ‘proper distance’ between audience and

¹³ A phenomenological ‘perspective’ does not just relate to the visual, but to an embodied experience. These embodied ‘perspectives’ then inform political lenses; feminist, queer, indigenous etc.

content?

And

Q.3 What methods of production design can support 'proper distance' between a contributor and their VR representation?

The first question responds to Kate Nash's proposition that proper distance(s) is a matter of VR design (Nash, 2018 p. 21). The second appreciates that this design not only includes the technological elements of VR experience, but also how the documentary is produced, including the relations between maker, contributors and creative assets.

'Sticking' with Empathy

'The Empathy Machine' is presented in this research as a genre of VR documentary, but certainly not the *only* genre, nor is empathy the only lens through which to consider VR. Other research has suggested new terms or aspirations for VR documentary such as 'radical compassion' (Bollmer, 2017) 'shimmer' & 'encounter' (Scott-Stevenson, 2020 & 2019) and that the "dominance of the empathy claim" has perhaps become a "distraction, if not a barrier to development" of the medium (Rose, 2018b, p. 142). Never the less I follow Nash (2020) in suggesting discourses on empathy are 'helpful' to practice in that they "highlight[s] important questions about the ways in which proximity and distance in this relationship [between audience and contributor] are managed and the implications of this for engaging ethical debate" (Nash, 2020 p. 113)

Across this thesis I make use of the term 'sticky', borrowed from Sara Ahmed. Ahmed uses this word to describe the ways in which things, feelings, concepts or objects can become stuck together. This is not due to some objective reality of connection, but a "history of contact". The repeated positioning of two objects or ideas as related, leaves "impressions", and they become stuck to one another. We can consider VR as "a sticky object; what it picks up on the surface "shows" where it has travelled and what it has come into contact with" (Ahmed, 2006 p. 40). As previously suggested, there is no one concrete definition of empathy against which VR documentary or VR in general can be objectively measured (Fisher, 2017; Sánchez-Laws,

2020). In press and industry discussion of VR, empathy has often taken on “a superficial and blurry meaning” (Sora-Domenjó, 2022, p. 3). When critics, advocates or academics define empathy for the purposes of measuring it against VR, either to support or dispel the comparison, they necessarily end up working at cross purposes to other authors who have chosen another of the myriad of definitions. Comprehensive surveys, like Sora-Domenjó’s (2022), must group research based on the varying conception of empathy at play - as perspective taking, as imitation, as helping behaviour etc - and ultimately concludes “there is little empirical evidence of a correlation between VR exposure and an increase in empathy that motivates pro-social behaviour, and a lack of research covering VR films exposure eliciting empathy” (Sora-Domenjó, 2022, p. 1). Similarly there has been a lack of substantial evidence that the more ‘immersive’ documentary content is, the more profound its positive social effects (Farmer, 2019).

Responding to this literature, I deemed it unconstructive to task this research with exploring whether VR *does* or *is* or *promotes* empathy. Empathy as a concept however, has proved a lucrative metaphor for exploring the risk(s) of improper distance. Empathy literature is replete with the language of proximity and distance, of relations between self and other, with sameness and difference, merger and strangeness, that also define any articulation of ‘proper distance’. In response to this, running throughout this research is a 4th question:

Q.4 What conception of Empathy (if any) is useful in assessing proper distance in VR documentary?

The Shape of This Research

This PhD research is presented in two parts: this written exegesis and the practice based artefact *With These Hands*. This exegesis contains images of the practice based experiments and varying visual materials produced across production. *With These Hands* is an interactive VR documentary and attendant installation that has been presented alongside this exegesis to form my practice based inquiry.

This written exegesis details my journey to that artefact, through interweaving theory and description of practice. The writing forms 5 chapters, of which the first is this introduction. The

second is an engagement with the history of the medium of this practice based research, Virtual Reality, interwoven with reflection on where its methodology - practice - and attending descriptive method - queer or critical phenomenology - can be drawn out or drawn on. Particularly I look at prominent critiques of the empathy machine genre of VR documentary, and how these relate to the history of phenomenological inquiry into Empathy and Alterity. From this material, I suggest some boundaries for practice.

In chapter three I describe some 360 filming from early in my research, through which I establish my 'subject' as gender; its expression, performance and phenomenology. In reflecting on practice, my own and others, I find that the work that seems most successful in upholding 'proper' or ethical distance between audiences and contributors, does so through embodied interaction. This interaction presents opportunities for symbolic 'reciprocal' relations between audiences and contributors. This prompts me to reorient my practice toward the more embodied and interactive medium of games engine produced VR, and my attention towards reciprocity as a potential method for producing 'proper distance'.

Chapter four is dedicated to the description of the production of *With These Hands*. *With These Hands* was produced in collaboration with SLEEC (Survivors Leading Essential Education and Change), a grassroots organisation, hardship fund, online community and submission based blog made by and for survivors and victims of sexual violence. It is through my collaboration with SLEEC and their wider community, that the design for an embodied VR work was put in service to sharing challenging, complex and under discussed narratives of sexual assault and recovery, and representing both survivors and 'perpetrators'¹⁴ of sexual harm. The production of *With These Hands* presented a rich opportunity to consider reciprocity, alterity and consent, not only within its material and exhibition output, but within the production process. This chapter is split into three chronological movements; Pre-Production, Production and Exhibition.

In chapter five, I reflect on my practice in reference to my research questions. Attending to reciprocity as a theme emerging in practice, and building from this, engages with reciprocity in wider ethical discourses of empathy and the 'face-to-face' encounter. Through practice based engagement with conceptions of sexual consent and an ethics of reciprocity, a description of

¹⁴ This thesis will later elaborate on this problematic terminology.

embodied interaction as 'feeling-with' the Other is presented, as an expression and method of 'proper distance'.

Contribution to Knowledge

There are many examples of critical VR documentaries that successfully manifest 'proper distance' by imaginatively engaging VR affordances. However, there is a paucity of formal academic research which outlines methods, techniques or approaches to doing so, particularly from a maker's perspective. This exegesis and artefact thesis addresses this research gap.

This research also begins to bring existing critical, decolonial and feminist cultural theory, documentary theory and art practice research to bear on VR documentary practice. It draws connection between the particular affordances and materials of VR making and this established critical lineage. Although examples of feminist practice based research in VR exist (Davis, 2004), there is a lack of academic accounts of practice based research following in this lineage, accounting for contemporary developments in technology and discourse. This is a further achievement of this research.

Additionally, this exegesis and artefact thesis pushes back (or perhaps forward) on the wholesale adoption of Levinasian ethics of representation in VR documentary, as proposed within the current conception of 'The Risk of Improper Distance'. Building on works of critical phenomenology relating to sexual ethics, I propose a reconsideration of the Levinasian ethic and its insistence on the 'infinite alterity' of the contributor. I suggest that the mediums affordances of embodiment and interactivity permit a more reciprocal - albeit 'asymmetrical' - encounter with the documentary contributor. This asymmetrical reciprocity', that can be drawn out of the work of Simone de Beauvoir (1997), accounts for a 'sociopolitical alterity', or contingent and surmountable forms of otherness resulting from oppression in the ethical encounter - but without reliance on reducing the documentary contributor to 'essential otherness' (Anderson, 2019). Although articulated here through theory, this proposal was equally attended to and drawn out from practice, particularly as a product of my collaboration with SLEEC, their wider community, and their own attendance to ethical representation.

The RL of this VR research

This PhD was completed across 5 years between 2018-2024. It was therefore greatly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic measures between March 2020 - April 2022¹⁵. It was also deeply influenced by the ensuing public political debate and unrest in the UK and across the world.

The pandemic was an extraordinary circumstance in which to try and produce work and conduct research - isolated from peers, workspaces and operating almost entirely online for 2 years. Pandemic restrictions had a profound impact on my ability to make work and access resources, lockdown restrictions prematurely ending production on some works in progress. Beyond the practical however, the pandemic also greatly influenced the content of the work, and my critical questions were sharpened by expanded public discourse. The greatest impact of note was that through an interest in pandemic activist action, I became acquainted with SLEEC and their work.

Ironically for research attempting to negotiate an ethical 'distance' in practice, the pandemic was typified by a constant vigilance of the physical distances between bodies, and a perpetual re-navigation of varying 'safe', 'sanctioned' and 'ethical' proximities to others. The ethical proximity of a 'social distance' for example, was *socially moderated and regulated personal obligation* - "if your friends ask you to meet, you must say 'no'" (Johnson, 2020). This ultimately serving to absolve the government of responsibility when covid cases inevitably rose. Similarly, instances of food shortages and overwhelmed and overworked healthcare workers were deemed the result of the public's lack of self control, for which we "should all be ashamed" (Slawson & Bachelor, 2020) rather than the result of mixed messaging from the government, and *its* failure to appropriately fund and 'protect' the NHS (UK Parliament, 2022).

The extreme societal changes required to lessen the spread of covid had huge cultural impact in the UK. Things once deemed impossible suddenly became possible; the mass housing of the homeless; the provision of a type of Universal Basic Income provided on application, and

¹⁵ National lockdowns were enforced between March - June, and October - December 2020 and Glasgow and other areas of the UK experienced additional 'local' lockdowns. Forms of covid regulation, including a vaccine programme, mandatory mask wearing in public and various restrictions on household mixing remain in place until March 2022 (Institute for the Government, 2022; "What are the latest rules for face coverings and masks?", 2022).

many public institutions, art galleries and museums pivoted to provide online activity - actions that many homelessness and disability activists had been calling for for years previous with little movement. The invasion of Ukraine by Russia in February 2022 resulted in governmental moves in the UK and Europe to provide the safe transport of Ukrainian refugees by providing free rail tickets (Stone, 2022). Similarly, advertising which encouraged the public to assess if they had spare bedrooms to offer to these incoming refugees (International Organization for Migration United Kingdom, 2022) illustrated not only that it is a political choice to allow others to drown in the international waters of Europe, but that the empathy for certain refugees 'like us' can be manufactured and dissipated by the government and press (Bayoumi, 2022). Queer phenomenology has proved a lucrative critical lens through which to examine pandemic politics, with its attention to bodies, proximities, and free movement in space. It also proved a critical tool for examining the phenomenological effects of the pandemic on various bodies, including threats to bodily freedom, both real and imagined, from Black Lives Matter to 'anti-vax/anti-mask' protests, and the expansion of UK anti-protest law - described by Amnesty international as "deeply authoritarian" and it's passing into law in 2022 a "dark day for civil liberties" (Amnesty International UK, 2022).

In the UK, raised awareness of racially motivated police crimes in the US and UK led to global protest and unprecedented shifts in public opinion. This, in combination with the murder of Sarah Everard in 2021 by a serving police officer Wayne Couzens, and public critique of police responses to protests and vigils in both instances (Burnett, 2022; Maheshwari-Aplin, 2021), raised previously fringe calls for police defunding and alternatives to policing to the cultural fore¹⁶.

Questions raised by SLEEC's work and activism in the wake of the murder of Sarah Everard and resulting cultural debates became the origin point of the content *With These Hands*, the technical underpinnings of which had been in-development since earlier in the PhD process. These include complex questions about victimhood (who gets to be a victim, and who does not), policing (who is served by the police, and who is not) and alternatives to policing and incarceration.

¹⁶ See Duverney's (2020) Vanity Fair interview with prison abolitionist Angela Davis as an example of the mainstreaming of this discourse.

2 QUEER PHENOMENOLOGY AND THE EMPATHY MACHINE

Image 2. - A contributor turns away from the 360 camera, October 2019

“A profound turning away”

A specific memory comes to mind when thinking about the VR user's ability to ‘turn away’.

I was a host for VR exhibitions and film festivals between 2016-2018. At that time, the most powerful and accessible headsets were tethered, meaning the experience runs on a high powered PC or laptop, connected via cables to a headset and external sensor system. A consequence of this is that monitors connected to the PC show a video feed of the user's view inside the headset, allowing a host to watch the experience ‘through their eyes’. This helps the host to identify issues with headset tracking, and perhaps to intervene if an audience appears stuck. Most helpfully, it allows a host to assess when an experience is coming to an end. A side effect of this setup is a form of voyeurism. The VR host witnesses what feels like private and intimate interaction between the user and the content. The narrow field of view of the screen reveals the focus of the user's attention. I know this effect from attempting to screen record my own work in-headset. I believe myself to be recording a neutral, static view, but when re-watched, subtle tilts of the head, the motion of breathing and other reactions unnoticed in the recording reveal my attention and involuntary responses to specific scenes and assets. In comparison to the cinema or theatre, a VR experience feels to the user rather private. In VR, I feel alone, in a media experience layed out just for me. Viewers on the outside can't see what I see, and that's part of what makes being observed in a headset feel so awkward. Although these monitors are not obscured from the audience when they enter the venue, the screen only shows the in-headset view while in use. Therefore users are not made consciously aware before entering VR that hosts are able to monitor their experience, and this perhaps adds to the voyeurism of the footage. This is where the user looks when they believe no one is looking.

This particular VR experience was room scale, meaning users are required to walk around a designated area in order to have a more embodied experience within the VR content. They choose not just where to look and which way to turn, but where to go in space, including closer or farther from objects or characters. The venue host is tasked with both fitting the headset and watching over the user during their experience, protecting them from bumping into objects, other visitors, tripping over or getting tangled in wires.

The piece was 'The Last Goodbye' (2017) created by Gabo Arora and Ari Palitz in collaboration with Chris Milk co-founded production company Here be Dragons and the USC Shoah Foundation. In 'The Last Goodbye' Holocaust survivor Pinchas Gutter recounts his memories of Nazi concentration camp Majdanek, in Poland, including his final moments with his sister, who did not survive. The story is told through Gutter's first hand testimony, and captured in a mix of 360 and 2 dimensional video inside and around the camp. In the 360 video portions, Gutter is filmed walking the perimeter of the buildings. In other scenes, interior spaces of the camp are captured with photogrammetry, producing highly detailed 3 dimensional life size models of the environment, its colours and textures, as a photographic snapshot. The 2D video capture of Gutter is then CG'd into this digital replica environment. The narrative result of these combined technologies is that we, the audience, are taken on a tour of the camp, with Gutter as narrator and guide.

The project's press materials stress the 'realness' of the experience. They highlight the accuracy of the photogrammetry technology, and promote the fact that Gutter, although CGI'd into some of the scenes, was really there at Majdanek to record his testimony (USC Shoah Foundation, n.d.). The sensory experience of the 3D scenes however, reads very differently.

The overall sensation for me in the work was of uncanniness. Gutter does not feel like another body present in the rooms with me. While I feel co-present with Gutter in 360 video portions, which also feel 'live' or 'real', there is a stillness to the scanned environments which feels deeply artificial, almost like a game, and Gutter in his 2 dimensionality reads as a hologram. The almost-but-not-quite fidelity of Gutter and the room works against my sense of it as 'real', and I feel, in fact, further, not closer, from the 'reality' of Majdanek. Nevertheless the experience is, as one might imagine, very emotional, with Gutter himself at points breaking down in tears when recalling a song from his childhood.

In my time hosting this piece, many users left the headset crying. In fact, it's a common concern of VR hosts to clean and maintain clarity in the headset lenses as users' hot tears create condensation within the sealed eye mask. Being a VR host often requires removing headsets from crying audience members, and holding space for those who need to take a few moments before revealing their faces to what is often a line of expectant others waiting their

turn. The longer one hosts for a particular experience, the more accustomed one becomes with the emotional beats of the piece. These are viewed on the screen many times, as the majority of audiences are compelled toward, in this instance, to the most emotional parts Gutter's address, when he sings a song to his sister through a breaking voice. This also leads one conversely to notice when this is not the case.

I recall one audience member in particular who was very excited to experience the work. Some users are physically chaste in their interaction with VR environments, holding their hands tight to their bodies or folded in front of them, only lightly shifting in place or gingerly turning around. Other users are more physically empowered, exploring the rooms to the maximum of their abilities, attempting to test the boundaries of the experience literally and figuratively. This particular user explored the space with relish, crouching down on the floor and exploring all the plains of movement possible. As the piece reached its emotional crescendo, I could see glimpses of Gutter's soundless singing in the distant peripherals of this user's headset view. As Gutter sings to his lost sister, this user was rotating his head forward backward, and then around and through a tap and sink captured in exquisite detail in the corner of this gas chamber.

Phenomenology and VR Research

Academics interested in VR documentary's relationship to the wider documentary field, including its ethics, have called for "more agile critical frameworks for the analysis and critique of these technologically mediated encounters" as the "forms of experiential engagement involved in VR challenge analytic tools of visual culture". They further call for "a next generation of research", that might draw on phenomenology, which might prove "more relevan[t] than textual analysis to address these forms where storytelling gives way to what some are calling storyliving" (Rose, 2018a).

Phenomenology is broadly a "manner or style of thinking" and a methodology for describing and reflecting on direct experience, which takes the world as always 'already there', before reflection begins. It offers "an account of space, time and the world as we 'live' them" and "tries to give a direct description of our experience as it is" (Merleau-Ponty, 2002 pg vii-x). As such it is suited to both description, and further reflection on forms of 'storyliving'.

Originating as a way of doing philosophy in the writings of Edmund Husserl, phenomenology emerges as a critique of the sciences and other philosophies which rely on overview theories (or what Husserl calls 'presuppositions') which assume a perspective 'over' the world and outside of direct experience. As such, these sciences pretend to possess 'a view from nowhere'; a disembodied perspective not accessible to direct experience. For Husserl, direct experience and the 'intentional act' of perception is the only 'absolute given' available to the philosopher with which to make truth claims (Moran, 2000, pp. 9-11). The history of phenomenology has, however, been described as "the story of the deviations from Husserl" and his highly specified and greatly criticised method of phenomenological 'bracketing' (Moran, p. 3). This method proposes the practitioner to be sensually and philosophically examining only the *bracketed* object or scene, dispossessing the scene and the philosopher himself from any "presuppositions", including the context of their meeting, and any and all external influence or bias. This method has been widely critiqued, from outside of and within phenomenology discourse, as a practical impossibility and a masculinist 'fantasy' (Ahmed, 2006 p. 33-34).

The main body of phenomenology then, is a series of more delicate approaches to a way of doing philosophy that concerns itself with the sensory experience of the world, attempting to attend most closely to this sensuousness as a source of knowledge, whilst not claiming that all other influence of culture and understanding can be merely bracketed away. Phenomenology is not one comprehensive method, but a series of different authors' approaches. Key texts on technology (Heidegger; 1962, 1977), empathy (Levinas; 1969, 1987; Stein, 1989) have been referenced in key texts of 'VR' and 'The Empathy Machine' discourse (Coyne, 1994; Perry Barlow, 1990; Bollmer, 2017; Bollmer & Guinness, 2020; Murray & Sixsmith, 1999). However it is Merleau-Ponty's phenomenological methods that appear most frequently (Davis, 2004; Popat, 2016, 2017; Kozel et al, 2018) and which feature most heavily in Sara Ahmed's *Queer Phenomenology*.

A valid critique of Phenomenology, especially of Husserl but also of following authors, is its perception as de-politicised. Philosopher and social theorist Theodor Adorno criticised (Husserl's) phenomenology for its lack of attention to history, labour or power relations, deeming that phenomenology cannot politically or socially 'emancipate' nor 'better the

conditions of life' (Procyshyn, 2020). Critiques from more contemporary feminist or decolonial lenses have focused on traditional phenomenology's tendency to present the embodied experience of the researcher rather uncritically as a neutral tool of perception. As such, 'traditional' phenomenology creates its own 'view from nowhere', the view from 'anybody' or 'everybody', a 'neutral', 'natural' and 'unsituated' body, "a pipe dream of pretended neutrality" (Studlar, 1990) which "confirm[s] the fantasy of a subject who is transcendent" and disregarding the effects of gender, class, able-bodiedness on both perception and the time and space afforded to philosophise about it (Ahmed, 2006 pp. 27-34) .

Later works of phenomenological description, however, successfully use the methodology of phenomenology to describe the experience of the *specific* body. Describing how power (over, or lack there-of) is felt and experienced in the marginalised body. Phenomenological meditations on gender for example, in Simone De Beauvoir's *The Second Sex* (1997) proving a foundational text for feminist thought and Frantz Fanon's (1986) *Black Skin White Masks* similarly for anti-racist and decolonial critique. Contemporary phenomenology, influenced by these experiments, is now well within a 'critical turn', within which Sara Ahmed and Queer Phenomenology sit. This turn redirects or reorients phenomenological description of lived experience towards political and social justice ends; 'interrogating the concrete conditions, institutions and assumptions that structure lived experience' (Puncta, n.d.). Critical phenomenology is commonly defined as 'an approach to phenomenology which deals with not just the experience of reality itself but the social, political and cultural milieu in which these experiences occur' (Weeks, 2022). In its critical form, phenomenology can illuminate the 'invisible' structures of whiteness, heterosexual imperatives and ableist assumptions of an encountered constructions; be these buildings, institutions, in media or indeed in virtual environments. This illumination occurs primarily through the descriptions of how those structures are felt by bodies of 'difference'. Rather than a focus on the 'I touch the world' of traditional phenomenology, the focus is on 'the world touches me' - the pressures felt by the non-normate body, as it rubs against a construct's confines.

VR's Technological and Conceptual Development

Many authors have mapped the history of Virtual Reality technology, integrating the development of the hardware, software and conceptualisation of Virtual Reality within a history

of immersive and illusionary art practices, including the history of the panorama, rotunda and the stereoscope (Grau, 2003; Urrichio, 2016; Lister et al, 2003; Bolter & Grusin, 2000). Some have taken wider steps through a history of virtuality, tracing oral story traditions, theatre, the printing press, photography and film to the telephone (Blascovich & Bailenson, 2011). Many take prehistoric cave painting practices to suggest immersion in media is a fundamental human desire (Blascovich & Bailenson 2011; Uricchio, 2018; Allen, 2021, Lee, 2004; Biocca, 1997; Biocca and Levy, 1995).

It is, however, broadly accepted that the history of contemporary VR media and technology, particularly the Head Mounted Display (HMD) can be divided into three waves (Rose, 2018b). The first in the 1950's and 60's resulted in the conceptual and technological development of the HMD's and stereoscopic 'immersive' video, in the work of Ivan Sutherland (1965, 1968) and Morton Heilig (1956) respectively (Grau, 2003; see also Heilig, 1992). The second wave in the 80's and 90's, in which the term 'Virtual Reality' was coined (Lanier, 2017), develops alongside the burgeoning internet, and discourse on cyberspace and VR technology are profoundly enmeshed (Hayles, 1999; Perry Barlow, 1990; Coyne, 1994; Stone, 1998 , Bolter & Grusin, 2000). Contemporary VR technology is now in its third wave. This wave was arguably ushered in by the purchase of 21 year old Palmer Luckey's VR gaming startup Oculus by social media tech giant Meta (then Facebook) for 2 billion USD in 2014 (Golding, 2019; Harley, 2020). This event was the catalyst for many major tech companies to invest in some form of virtual, augmented or mixed reality headsets (including Google, Samsung, HTC, Sony, Microsoft and others).

The wave analogy indicates the ebb of development that occurs between bursts of activity, due to decline in public interest, demand and funding (Rose, 2018b). However artistic, academic and military experiments with VR, as well as it's developing use within industry, does continue intra-wave (Kreuger, 1993; Basu, 2019; Grau, 2004 pp. 169-177). Much technological groundwork in VR was built and funded through corporate and military investment, however the pronounced increase of artistic interest in VR and interactive technologies in the early 90's proved to be equally as influential on the shaping and framing of VR in the current public consciousness. This work was born out of investment in virtual and telecommunications

technologies by leading artistic research labs such as Banff Centre of the Arts in Canada¹⁷ as well as others. Increased artistic engagement with Virtual Reality technology considerably influenced not only conceptions about what VR would be *used for* in the future, but also broke considerable conceptual ground. In particular, influential theorists (and practitioners) Brenda Laurel and later Janet H Murray (*Computers as Theatre* (1991) and *Hamlet on the Holodeck* (1997) respectively) stressed that virtual online venues were soon to become sites of live, narrative and interactive play and thus can and should be read as theatre. More conceptually however, Brenda Laurel in particular stressed that theatre thinking and metaphors are more expansive frameworks through which to consider the future of human computer interaction, particularly with Virtual and Simulative technologies, as summarised in her influential maxim “think of the computer, not as a tool, but as a medium” (Laurel, 1993 p. 151). Other influential artistic VR work of this period is that of Char Davis, which is detailed at length later in this chapter.

Further work of note in the lead up to VR’s third wave, the emergence of VR as a documentary medium, Chris Milk’s Ted Talk and related discourse of ‘The Empathy Machine’, is the creative research of Nonny de la Peña. Her research into journalistic applications for VR technologies resulted in her highly influential early VR documentary *Hunger in Los Angeles* (2012), which premiered at Sundance. Although de la Peña does not use the word ‘empathy’ in her academic writing at that time (Sánchez-Laws, 2020), it is very quickly attributed to her work¹⁸ and is something she does later lay claim to (Bye, 2016). There is also a considerable body of research into VR as a tool of ‘empathy enhancement’ emerging from Jeremy Bailenson’s Virtual Human Interaction Lab founded in 2003, and in particular his ‘empathy at scale’ research project (Bailenson, 2018). It is notable that in this more recent history of VR, there is a much closer connection between content and technological innovation (Rose, 2018b). Palmer Luckey was a journalism student and intern of de la Peña, designing the headset for the 2012

¹⁷ The Banff Centre’s 2 year virtual programme spawned many influential proto-VR installations such as *The Placeholder* by Brenda Laurel and Rachel Strickland and *Inherent Rights* by Paul Yuxweluptun. Both these works spoke to Native Canadian mythology and experience, and as such, although described as artworks at the time, would comfortably be adopted within contemporary documentary VR discourse.

¹⁸ Bryan Bishop’s (2013) article on *Hunger in Los Angeles* is titled ‘Digital empathy: how ‘Hunger in Los Angeles’ broke my heart in a virtual world’. In it Bishop describes exploring the piece “peering into the faces” of the “crude” computer generated figures who act out the audio verite recording of a line outside a food bank in LA. When one of the figures collapses, experiencing a diabetic attack, Bishop’s “heart rate picked up, and I impulsively wanted to do *something*” despite not having any body with which to aid the man in the simulation. Reflecting on the piece Bishop says “I was surprised how much I cared”.

Sundance showcase. A visit to Bailenson's lab by Meta CEO Mark Zuckerberg, in which Bailenson related to him the "many ways the unique power of VR can be applied to make us better people, more empathetic, more aware..and more productive at work", may well have influenced Zuckerberg's investment in Oculus just "a few weeks after" (Bailenson, 2018, p. 5).

Phenomenology and VR Description

'Embodiment' appears frequently in both VR and Phenomenological discourse. Maurice Merleau-Ponty is perhaps the phenomenologist who places most emphasis on 'embodiment' in his writings, suggesting the "body is the vehicle of being in the world" (Merleau-Ponty, 2002 p. 82) and thus the experience of being-in-the-world is 'embodied'. The mind and its thinking of the world cannot be separated from a body which experiences the world, and as such Merleau-Ponty's phenomenology presents itself in opposition to Cartesian dualism.

'Embodiment' takes on a specific meaning in some VR research, in what is sometimes also referred to as 'the illusion of body ownership' (Slater et al 2008; Slater, 2009) or 'Body Swap Illusion' (Petkova & Ehrsson, 2008). In this 'illusion', one can experience that either a virtual or virtual body part are one's own or part of one's own body (a VR expansion of 'The Rubber Hand Illusion' (Petkova & Ehrsson, p. 2). This experience can even be induced between two live people - using headsets and head mounted cameras - resulting in participants experiencing a 'swapping' of bodies (Petkova & Ehrsson, p. 4; see also *BeAnotherLab*, n.d.). VR users can in this sense 'embody' others or experience 'embodiment-as-other'¹⁹.

Despite a general understanding of the potential for VR embodiment, and frequent references to phenomenological texts in writing around VR's second wave, the dominant discourse of VR in this era (referred to interchangeably as 'Cyberspace') frequently characterised VR as producing a kind of 'disembodiment' (Murray & Sixsmith, 1999; Hayles, 1996). VR is described as a "form of out-of-the-body experience" (Rheingold, 1991 p. 256) in which one is "reduced to a point of view.. everything amputated" (Perry Barlow, 1990). Contemporaneous feminist accounts of the era describe this as VR's 'view from nowhere' problem. As feminist technology

¹⁹ It's now very common to be provided a virtual body or avatar in commercial VR experiences and well understood that users experience these as part of or an extension of their own body. The unfortunate evidence for this is the regular occurrence of particularly female users being sexually assaulted in multi user VR space, and their experience of this as profoundly disturbing, violating and 'real' (Basu, 2021).

theorist Anne Balsamo puts it “in efforts to colonise the electronic frontier..the material body is repressed and divorced from the locus of knowledge..the body as a sense apparatus is nothing more than excess baggage for the cyberspace traveller” (Balsamo, 1996) and VR artist Char Davis (2004) describes:

Virtual reality - as conventionally constructed - is the epitome of Cartesian desire, in that it enables the construction of artificial world where there is the illusion of total control, where ageing mortal flesh is absent..such a desire to escape the confines of the body and the physical world is symptomatic of an almost pathological denial of our embodied embeddedness in the living world (Char Davis, 2004).

Roxanne Allucquere (Sandy) Stone, digital communication theorist and pioneer of transgender studies, offers a starker warning:

The discourse of visionary virtual world builders is rife with images of imaginary bodies, freed from the constraints that flesh imposes. Cyberspace developers foresee a time when they will be able to forget about the body...No refigured virtual body, no matter how beautiful, will slow the death of a cyberpunk with AIDS. Even in the age of the technosocial subject, life is lived through bodies. Forgetting about the body is an old Cartesian trick, one that has unpleasant consequences for those bodies whose speech is silenced by the act of our forgetting; that is to say, those upon whose labour the act of forgetting the body is founded - usually women and minorities. (2000, p. 525)

These critiques acknowledge that white western male bodies are the bodies upon and around which the technological apparatus and narratives of virtual reality and its effects are developed. A VR based on a feminist or other understanding of the body and embodiment might well operate very differently (see Murray & Sixsmith, 1999). Particularly Stone’s critique echoes that of ‘traditional’ phenomenology from ‘critical’ phenomenology. Whilst acknowledging the body’s sensory capacity to construct a ‘reality’, if this construction and contemplation is not considered in relation to the ‘social, political and cultural milieu’ of that body, that is, that bodies ‘situatedness’ (Haraway, 1988) it risks re-subscription to the pitfalls of a ‘view from no-body’ or a fantasy ‘every-body’.

Phenomenological VR Practice

In contemporary VR research, there have been extended works of descriptive phenomenology of VR experience, articulating both VR's creative and ethical implications (Popat, 2016, 2017; Bender and Broderick, 202; Murray, 1999). However, there is a paucity of more critical applications of this methodology to explore ethical questions of representation, particularly from practitioners and within creative, narrative VR practice.

However, within second wave discourse there is a key example of extended application of phenomenological methodology in practice by artist Char Davis around her VR artworks *Osmose* 1995 & *Ephémère* 1998. Davis' investigations with VR could further be described as critical or feminist phenomenology, and her resulting practice approached VR as a reflexive medium. Although Davis does not categorise her work as documentary - rather - as art and a form of painting (Davis, 2005), through a contemporary lens it could easily be read as such²⁰. It can therefore be considered an early example of reflexive VR documentary practice.

Davis acknowledged the potential of VR to bring "heightened awareness of [the] body as a site of consciousness and the sensation of consciousness occupying space" but was also acutely aware that the origins of the technology "lie deep within the military and western-scientific-industrial-patriarchal complex" and as such tend to recreate a "collective unconscious of Western culture" (Davis, 2004) "ripe with subconscious perceptions and prejudices" (Ziauddin Sardar cited in Davis, 2004). Inspired by Merleau-Ponty and his extended descriptions of 'disorientation' as a philosophical tool, Davis developed 'an embodying user-interface' which sought to facilitate "perceptual ambiguity which might serve to dismantle Western 'mis-perception' of the world" (Davis, 2004).

At this time in its conceptual development, VR is thought of more as a navigable space construction, than a narrative form. In *Osmose*, alongside a number of other techniques of 'perceptual ambiguity', Davis turns her attention to 'dismantling' western and masculinist

²⁰ VR's contemporary framing as a documentary medium comes in part from the rhetoric around empathy and understanding surrounding the work of influential VR makers such as Chris Milk and Nonny de la Peña. Additionally, in recent history, the organisations funding, exhibiting and championing XR and immersive works have been documentary festivals, including IDFA and Sheffield Doc Fest. These festivals have historically taken an incredibly broad definition of documentary in calls for work. IDFA, for example, only requires that applying projects that use new media and emerging technology "reflect on reality" (IDFA, n.d.).

approaches to traversing virtual space. Davis is opposed to joystick based 'walking' interactions which "reinforce an instrumental, dominating stance towards the world" (Davis, 2004), or other approaches such as the almost comical heroic masculine idealism of the pointing-to-fly locomotion employed in contemporaneous experiments emerging from VR startup VPL (as described by Perry Barlow, 1990²¹). In their place Davis uses participants' own breathing as a navigational input, measured by motion sensors on a audiences 'vest'. The effect, as described by Davis, is reminiscent of the way divers use breath to control body buoyancy underwater, and "facilitates a convincing sensation of 'floating'" (Davis, 2004). Breath for Davis, quoting Drew Leder's *The Absent Body* (1990), "is a potent tool of overcoming dualism", breath transgresses the imaginary safe boundary of outside/inside and points to our fundamental 'interconnectedness' to the outside world - "In following breath, one begins to embody this truth" (Drew Leder, 1990 cited in Davis, 2004). In her conclusion, Davis suggests that the 'transformative' potential of VR is its ability to jolt us away from 'habitual perceptions and culturally biased assumptions' and can be used to 'convey alternative sensibilities and worldviews', 'perceiving freshly' (Davis, 2004).

The work of Char Davis presents as a jumping off point for my own practice based inquiry, and models how critical feminist and postcolonial phenomenology can guide and lend critical language to practice. However, I have found the most rich phenomenological unpickings of themes of the 'the empathy machine' vision of VR documentary; calls to emotion, 'orientation' towards 'orientalist' depictions of 'others', and the risk(s) of distances between some bodies to others is the writing of Sara Ahmed, and her project 'Queer Phenomenology' (Ahmed, 2006).

²¹ The Superman/Übermensch implications here are almost too expansive to footnote.

Queer Phenomenology: Extension and Orientation

Sara Ahmed is often cited in critique of Empathy Machine discourse (Bollmer, 2017; Pozo, 2018; Raz, 2020) due to her assessment of the political implications of calls to emotions like Empathy in *The Cultural Politics of Emotion* (2004) and *The Contingency of Pain* (2002). She suggests that when we are called to experience the suffering of others 'as are own' and empathise with others without a recognition of the political history of that pain (particularly in the relationship between white settler and indigenous testimonies), this is tantamount to 'violent' 'appropriation'. In *Strange Encounters: Embodied Others in Post-Coloniality* (2000), Ahmed presents a critical understanding of the purpose of 'The Stranger' in cultural conceptions like 'neighbourhoods', 'nations' etc. She considers how one is 'recognised' as 'a stranger', as one who is 'out of place'. She also considers the 'encounter' between 'the one who is strange' and those who are not, and how even extending 'warm feelings' toward or even drawing closer this 'stranger' only seek to affirm the normative (see also 'eating' the 'stranger' in hooks, 2014). Although Ahmed's work has always been broadly phenomenological in its attention to the affective, or 'felt on the body' qualities of these discussions, it is in *Queer Phenomenology: Objects, Orientations, Others* (2006) that she most explicitly brings the ideas of the previous texts into direct conversation with the history of Phenomenology.

In *Queer Phenomenology* she articulates further her previous accounts of the directional or 'orientational' quality that calls to emotion take *toward* Others. She also presents a phenomenological methodology of Otherness or 'Queer Phenomenology' as a form of 'disorientation'. This is not a phenomenological *account* of being Othered, which according to Ahmed, has been more successfully achieved by other writers such as Frantz Fanon, Simone de Beauvoir, Iris Marion Young & Audre Lord for example (Ahmed, 2006, p. 4). Rather, Ahmed presents a way of using the personal phenomenology that arises from being 'strange', out of place or 'disoriented' as a critical tool. She builds on Merleau-Ponty's account of disorientations as moments of revelation in phenomenology, where, Merleau-Ponty suggests, things can be seen 'slant-wise' or 'queer', or outside of presumed 'natural order'. She describes the lived experience of being non-white and queer as being a 'slant -wise' view of the world, a view from a disoriented position, or a position off centre or 'out-of-line' with cultural expectations (Ahmed, 2006 pp.12 - 20).

Orientation

Orientation is much elaborated on in Sara Ahmed's *Queer Phenomenology*, not only its 'queer' uses, as in 'sexual orientation', but also its etymology. Orientation speaks to having a direction, a 'point of view', or rather, the point *toward* which one orients from a fixed central position. It also, necessarily, refers to 'The Orient'. 'Orient' etymologically emerges from *oriri*, "to rise", and relates to the sun as rising in the East. This 'East' however, has historically been affixed to a geographical location - 'east-of' ancient Europe, where the word, and this specific geographical mapping of the world, originates. The opposite or opposing position of 'Orient' is 'Occident', meaning "setting", which is a 'West' that relates to an 'East', but has through geopolitical moves become 'The West': Western Europe and North America. The occident is also the point *from* which one views, or 'here' rather than 'over there'. By attending to the spatial quality of these words Ahmed unpacks 'orientation', and uses it to discuss the power relations of 'towardness', 'facing' or indeed, the ability to 'turn away', by being cast in a central position (Ahmed, 2006, pp. 113 - 116).

Extension

In Ahmed's writing, to be able to turn away, or toward, to face 'an Other' also serves as a *forms of extension*. An illustration of what the body can do, its freedom in space (Ahmed, p. 115)

According to Merleau-Ponty, bodies that are 'oriented' can more easily or effectively 'extend' into space. A body which is dis-oriented fails to extend properly, and is limited in its successful movement. If one becomes disoriented, for example, one might struggle to successfully reach out and grasp an object. Ahmed draws upon Merleau-Ponty's work on disorientation and extension to discuss race, gender, sex and sexuality as orienting devices. Sexual orientations which 'deviate' from the direction of the heterosexual ideal, for example, are felt by the body of the Queer person as the pressure of not being 'in line'. To move in the direction of queer desire is to be met with socio-cultural and systemic forms of resistance, which restricts the body in its freedom to perform movements. These might be movement toward certain life goals of marriage or children; unequal access to healthcare or legal protection, or exposure to even more fundamental obstruction or violence as the queer body moves through physical space. She describes the sensation of conflict in the urge to hold hands with a same sex partner, for example, in a certain area, because of an understanding that this could potentially interrupt

their journey, making it less safe or less easy. Conversely, bodies which orient in the 'right way', toward the 'right' desire, experience an extension and expansion of their bodies movements in space. This extension or lack of resistance, in reaching out to hold a partner's hand for example, might feel so 'natural' it could go unnoticed or unseen, to the extent it might become incomprehensible that such a restriction could exist for another body (Ahmed, p.101). Ahmed suggests that, like a repetitive strain injury, these expansions and restrictions shape the bodies they act upon, empowering some and disempowering others.

I have found the concepts of orientation and extension can be used to further elaborate on what feels uncomfortable when VR is used or described as an 'empathy machine'. Ahmed's thinking can further critique this concept, as well as suggest an alternative, more reflexive potential of VR documentary - as a tool of 'disorientation'.

Critique of 'The Empathy Machine'

The suggestion that VR is 'an empathy machine' is potentially so pervasive because its claim is so vague and the true meaning of its sentiment so elusive. The claim is most famously attributed to Chris Milk²², but reference to empathy are repeated in media discussing VR documentary long before this moment - in Bryan Bishop's recounting of his experience with the 'first' (de la Peña, 2015) VR documentary *Hunger in LA*, for example (Bishop, 2013). Even in its second wave iteration, before it was described as a documentary medium, it was claimed that VR *enacts* "new kinds of empathy". By permitting a literal occupation of another being or objects 'point of view', we can come to know "“what it's like” to be a gorilla, dinosaur or Molecule" (Bolter and Grusin, 2000, p. 246). However, praise for VR as a documentary medium is frequently accompanied with reference to crying and the emotional responses of audiences, which further proposes empathy as an *outcome* or *what follows* the VR viewing experience (see de la Peña, 2015a). The emotional experience of being faced with the 'realities' and emotions of the suffering distant others who are met within the artwork has been described as 'empathy', without the VR work necessarily permitting access to a specific 'point of view' - "this type of

²² The phrase 'empathy machine' was in fact coined by cinema critic Roger, who claims that *fiction cinema* is "like a machine that generates empathy. If it's a great movie, it lets you understand a little bit more about what it's like to be a different gender, a different race, a different age, a different economic class, a different nationality, a different profession, different hopes, aspirations, dreams and fears" (RogerEbert.com, 2018)

transporting emotional power could be a massive tool for generating empathy...I kept thinking of the kids” (Stein, 2015)

These two broad ‘empathetic paradigms’ at play within the empathy machine genre of VR documentary have been acknowledged within critique. However, as previously mentioned, VR documentaries may employ or intermingle both, as audience subject position changes within works. These two paradigms are defined by Raz (2022) as ‘enhanced intimacy’ which would include VR works which generate face-to-face encounters with contributors and their testimony, and ‘sensory motor simulations’. In ‘sensory motor simulations’ audiences are encouraged to have a more sensory engagement with the environment of a contributor, such as witness a recreation of their testimony or experience (such as the hallucinations in 6X9) or work that induces embodiment-as-contributor. As Raz (2020) notes however, these two broad forms do not aim at different kinds of empathy; one social and one merely somatic (in relation to the much hyped literature of ‘mirror neurons’²³). Both aim to connect the user to the documentary contributor in a social sense, and therefore are suggested to engage or enhance social forms of empathy.

For the purposes of proposing a broad subject and form for my own documentary work, it is worth briefly recounting the critique of these sub-genres and their distinct appeals to ‘empathy’. Both these forms are subject to critique for their potential to encourage ‘improper distance’ between audiences and contributors, but in subtly different ways. Interestingly, both of the leading critiques of these disparate empathetic paradigms urge makers consider ‘proper distance’ as illustrated within Levinasian ethics²⁴.

²³ A concept so heavily discussed and referenced since its emergence in the 1990's that it was described as “the most hyped concept in neuroscience” (Jarrett, 2012).

²⁴ Very broadly speaking, there could also be described a third seam of critique for the empathy machine genre that rather than focusing on how empathy is claimed to be produced within the media, and the improper distances inherent to the form, look further at how claims to empathy are promoted by tech companies. These critics suggest that promoting the social good of VR is aimed at “reset[ing] the narrative. At a moment when Silicon Valley sorely needs good press... that Silicon Valley is an essentially humanitarian enterprise” (Tarnoff, 2017; see also Nakamura, 2020; Sutherland, 2017; and Yang, 2017) and further engages with a contemporary current social ‘obsession’ with empathy, particularly in transnational politics. These tech company and governmental ‘calls to empathy’ have drawn criticism for the ways empathy is framed within neoliberal politics as a form of self development and citizenship, rather than a precursor to social justice action or activism (Pedwell, 2016). Although I take these critiques as valid, as they are less related to the form of VR as a creative medium, they are less helpful in proposing a site for practice.

Sensorimotor Simulations and Grant Bollmer's 'Feeling-into'

There are critiques of VR's ability to perform as an 'empathy machine' based not on a critique of VR's 'pretence to totality', or the ethics of claiming totality, but in VR's failing to enact the totality it claims. Prominent empathy critic Paul Bloom suggests that "it's ridiculous to use virtual reality to empathise with refugees" because it only visually represents a contributor's point of view, and cannot simulate sensations of fatigue, hunger, mental distress or physical and mental illness - "the awfulness of the refugee experience isn't about the sights and sounds of the refugee camp" (Bloom, 2017). Bloom suggests, in another example, that a simulation of more subtle forms of sexual and racial discrimination, might feel bearable in the short timeframe of the VR experience. It is only in the experience of a lifetime of repetition of these microaggressions that their impact on one's embodiment and body comportment can be felt and understood (as Ahmed's (2006) repetitive strain injury). Bloom also references what has been played out in some academic investigations into simulation as an 'empathy tool'. In proposing the user's experience as like-for-like the referenced experience of a contributor, the result is a "distorted simulation of what it would be *like for him/her* - and not for the other person" (Raz, 2020, p. 1460). For example, short term simulations of disabilities such as blindness result in users overestimating blind peoples confusion, frustration and suffering (Bloom, 2017; Ramierez, 2017; Bailenson, 2018)²⁵. Bloom's critique, however, rests more on VR's failure to *accurately* simulate, than the *ethical problem* of simulating. This is made apparent in Bloom's reference to the controversial text *Black Like Me* (1961), in which white author John Howard Griffin lived disguised as a Black man, which Bloom (2024) deems as "a serious attempt to appreciate what it's like to be another person" rather than highly suspect documentation of cultural appropriation leading to 'false consciousness' (Gaines 2017; see also Nakamura, 2020).

Grant Bollmer is the academic who has most rigorously taken against the sensorimotor simulation vision of the empathy machine from an ethical perspective, drawing on it's connections to a definition of empathy as emerging from 19th century German aesthetic theory '*Einführung*' (Bollmer, 2017; 2020; Bollmer and Guinness, 2020). Bollmer suggests that VR documentaries which permit a literal or more conceptual 'inhabiting' of a contributor's body,

²⁵ This 'problem' of simulating blindness has been deemed by many to be very successfully negotiated in the interactive VR artwork *Notes on Blindness: Into Darkness*, which takes a synaesthetic approach to representing the experience of a blind person's 'hearing world' with visuals (Nash, 2020)

represent a ‘cannibalistic’ (Bollmer, 2020) relationship between the audience and the contributor. In these experiences, the “annihilation of the Other” occurs as the audience ‘absorbs’ all of the Other that can be made experienceable into themselves (Bollmer, 2017 p. 72). As precursor to this, Bollmer looks to the history of the word ‘empathy’ and focuses on the moment *Einführung*, as a term denoting the sensory and emotional experience of “feeling into” an artwork, is used to describe social phenomena. Psychologist Theodor Lipps expands the meaning of *Einführung* to describe the moment of “project[ing] myself into the body of another” in order to grasp what they feel²⁶ (Bollmer, 2017 p. 73). Bollmer’s critique is lodged at VR experiences that presents contributors as objects that audiences can ‘feel into’, citing the ethical ramifications of this.

Firstly, he points to the ‘annihilation’ of difference between audience and contributor. By ‘feeling into’ a contributor and coming to know how *she feels* through the experience of how *I feel*, I have obliterated the conception that she has her own distinct feelings to mine. Furthermore, this version of empathy requires that the suffering of the others be ‘made experienceable’ on a sensory level - “what I cannot personally experience cannot serve as the grounds upon which I acknowledge your existence” (Bollmer, p. 64). The repetitive strain injury of systemic, institutionalised and socially maintained injustice and prejudice is harder to communicate via this method and therefore remains broadly unacknowledged. Bollmer (with Guinness, 2020) critiques the ‘orthopaedic’ logic of the empathy machine rhetoric that presents the bodies and experience of contributors as ‘Corpus nullius’ (Guinness, 2020) to be occupied or absorbed in order to ‘educate’ or flex one’s empathetic capacities (Bollmer & Guinness, 2020). Bollmer (2017) brings this into dialogue with the Levinasian phenomenological ethics. Levinas posits that the I of subjectivity can include ‘objects’ that can be taken into body, like food, or a tool that I can absorb into my body schema to expand or *extend* myself²⁷. However, The Other, as recognised as a conscious person “is that which cannot be absorbed” (Bollmer, 2017 p. 70). Thus the presentation of the body, experience and suffering of contributors to be ‘felt into’, to be sensually absorbed by the audience, with which they can find extensions through pedagogic empathy development for Bollmer, is what makes the Empathy Machine rhetoric ethically

²⁶ It is possible that the translation of *Einführung* to the English ‘empathy’ by psychologist Edward Titchener in fact generates a distinction between ‘empathy’ and related word ‘sympathy’ that it is possible Lipps himself did not intend (Jahoda, 2005)

²⁷ See also Merleau-Ponty’s discussion of the blind man’s stick as ‘extension’ (2002, p. 176); see also Ahmed (2006, pp. 46 - 49) on Heidegger’s hammer “extend[ing] of bodily capacities to perform action”.

untenable. These Other's of The Empathy Machine are not recognised as persons but are 'objectified' or 'Othered'. The relationship between othering and objectification is described by Ahmed as directly relating to extension;

The Otherness of things is what allows me to do things "with' them..Rather than othering being simply a form of negotiation, it can be described *as a form of extension. The body extends its reach by taking in that which it is "not" where the "not" involves the acquisition of new capacities...*The "not me" is incorporated into the body, extending its reach (Ahmed, 2006, p. 115)

Enhanced Intimacy and Kate Nash on the United Nations VR project

Kate Nash's conception of Improper Distance is notably applicable to both paradigms at play within Empathy Machine VR (Raz, 2020). However, her attention to the early VR documentary output of the United Nations, which includes *Clouds Over Sidra*, serves as a particular dissection of the improper distance of 'enhanced intimacy'. As she explains "the works do not simulate the others' experience or aim to put the user in their shoes directly. Rather they simulate an encounter, or meeting with the Other" (Nash, 2018, p. 126).

Following Chouliaraki (2011), Nash suggests that simulative and transportational qualities of VR can present potential for improper distance as it works to obscure (geographical and conceptual) distance, as users are transported to the site of suffering. However, the work does not provide audiences sufficient resources to judge the predicament of the other, nor their own relation to the 'map' of this suffering. Moreover "VR further tends toward improper distance where it presents distance spaces and others in aesthetic mode, inviting a contemplation of these as a tableau vivant or spectacle rather than painful reality" (Nash, p?). VR's ability to permit a sense of 'unmediated' access to the sights and sounds and emotions of suffering comes at the expense of an 'analytic dimension' required of media witnessing (Nash, 2018, p 125). The UN VR programme in particular follows trends in humanitarian communication in which distant 'deserving' others are "constructed as intimates that the Western spectator is encouraged to think about as 'friends'" (Nash, 2018. p. 126). This is exemplified for Nash in the scene in *The Ground Beneath Her*, when contributor, Sabita, looks to camera and offers the

viewer a flower, whilst in the voice over describing her hopes for the future. Thus the work implicitly addresses the viewer as Sabita's benefactor.

Nash suggests that the call to intimate co-presence with the minoritised other, and attend to her testimony, could be seen as carrying the moral potential of the face-to-face encounter of Levinasian ethics. However, the transportative and explorational potential of the VR experience, which is capitalised on within these productions, presents to the user as a tension of attention. Users are simultaneously asked to listen and share space with the contributor, but are also hailed to *turn away* from the speaking subject through the medium's design to explore the 360 or 6DoF environment.

All the UN works, and many other works in this genre, disproportionately feature global majority women and children in private spaces such as camp tents, slums and bedrooms "taking advantage of the impossibility of public space for displaced and disenfranchised people" (Nakamura, 2020, p 57). As Lisa Nakamura notes "VR's navigational interface requires the user to constantly pivot in a circle to find the person who is speaking or the point of view described in the audio narration, peeking and snooping within spaces where their physical bodies might not have been welcome" (Nakamura, p. 57). In this description can be further teased out perhaps the Occidental nature of the user in VR, more literally in 360 video content, but also perhaps appreciable in my account of 6DoF audience spatial investigation in *The Last Goodbye*. It is the *audience and their experience*, not the contributor and their testimony, that are the 'central point' around which the experience is formed. The contributor and their environment is what is oriented toward or away from, and also as the 'oriental', the 'over there', as opposed to 'here'.

Reflecting on the emotionality of audiences, Nash suggests that the risk(s) of improper distance presented by the medium require that audiences' emotional responses and reactions to content should be contextualised within social and political discourse. If the audience's own emotional response becomes the main focus of their attention, the work is further exhibiting improper distance. The discourse on VR that presents it as an 'empathy machine' runs the risk of promoting projects that focus on a maximisation of emotional response, and as such

“epitomises this narrow and ultimately troubling vision of moral responsiveness” as merely a call to emotion (Nash, 2018 p. 129).

Returning to Phenomenology: Empathy, Alterity and Ethical Representation of the Other

Phenomenologists such as Edith Stein were critical of Lipp’s conception of empathy for its pretence to a direct experience ‘within’ the experience of another (Bollmer, 2017). Stein’s (1989) definition of phenomenological “empathy” is the direct perception of an Other as more than just another object, but ‘an object-that-is-subject’, an object that has its own consciousness and *might* perceive ‘me’ back (Anderson, 2022 p.12). Both Edith Stein and Edmund Husserl suggest empathy is merely recognising another person as a body-consciousness. “Crucially, it does not require feeling another’s feeling as one’s own, or even having a strong sense of the contents of the other’s feelings; empathy is simply the feeling of foreign consciousness” and “the sense of being copresent with a foreign embodied consciousness.” (Anderson, 2022 summarising Stein, 1989 p. 12).

One of the many rifts or partitions in phenomenological discourse is around the ethical implication of this ‘empathy’ and how the Other with subjecthood is conceived. Within these discourses emerges the concepts of ‘reversibility’, ‘reciprocity’ and the opposing concept ‘alterity’. To very broadly summarise; is my ethical responsibility to not harm the Other based on my perception or conception of him as ‘like me’, ‘my equal’ and thus we are *reversible*, and *reciprocally* responsible to one another? Alternatively, is any attempt to ‘conceptualise’ the Other through this ‘reversibility’, using myself as a proxy of the Other and vice versa, attempting a ‘totalising’ view of the Other I cannot possess through direct experience? By this logic, my responsibility to the Other cannot rely on her ‘graspability’ to me, or her formation as ‘like me’, and she must possess complete existential alterity, an ‘infinity’ of Otherness (Anderson, 2019). This debate has been drawn on in the fields of anthropology, but also crucially documentary ethics, and the question of *representing* the Other. Is the ethical imperative of the Other based on an ability to perceive (or represent) the Other as ‘like-me/us’ or to perceive (or represent) their complete unknowability, difference, and alterity, thus acknowledging their freedom or independence from ‘me’ or ‘us’.

Emmanuel Levinas is the leading phenomenological voice on 'Existential Alterity' as described within his conception of the 'face-to-face'. As Bollmer (2017) suggests, Levinasian ethics insist we must approach the Other 'as a face', not an instrumental thing to be assimilated within me. Any attempt to project oneself inside the other, to imagine myself in her position or how she feels, to attempt to 'grasp' her, is tantamount to violence. I must instead acknowledge her 'infinite' difference or alterity (Levinas 1990, p. 90). Crucially this relationship is non-reciprocal - it cannot be based on assuming she might or could do the same for me. For Levinas this is an unethical insistence on 'reversibility'. The idea that the other can act reciprocally to me is based on an illusionary symmetrical 'sameness' of perspective and is thus unethical. Ahmed defines Levinas' position as 'protecting the Otherness of the Other' (Ahmed, 2000, p. 140)

Levinas himself is suspicious that any 'mediated' encounter with the other, though documentary for example, is only an illusion of a real encounter (Renov, 2004, p. 157). Authors such as Judith Butler (2004) have argued however, that Levinas' ethics can still be used as a provocation about ethical representation. For Butler, representations of Others must 'protect otherness' by "show[ing] their failure" to capture the other (Butler, 2004 p. 144). Bollmer suggests that the ethical imperative of Levinas enforces that an ethical VR documentary would not allow an audience "any attempt to experience, or even completely understand, the experience of another". He suggests that the fundamental aim of empathy (by Lipps definition) is unethical as it "requires a shattering of the surface that is the face" and encourages "getting under the skin to 'understand' someone else" (Bollmer, 2017, p. 71).

Proper Distance, as articulated by Silverstone (2003) and Choularaki (2011; with Ograd 2011), and adopted by Nash, is a form of media intervention, or mediation, between audience and documentary subject based in the moral philosophy of Emmanuel Levinas and the face-to-face. Proper Distance is the negotiation of Levinasian 'proximity' in the 'mediated spaces' of new technology (Silverstone, 2003 p. 6). As Silverstone describes it, "Levinas's notion of proximity preserves the separation of myself and the other, a separation which ensures the possibilities of both respect and responsibility for the other" (Silverstone, p. 8). But further adds that, in media making "we have to determine - perhaps case by case - what that proper distance is or might be when confronted with both familiar and novel appearances or representations of the other" (Silverstone, p. 9). Choularaki and Ograd (2011) further articulate this task as "representing

unfamiliar others as others with humanity” and that “proper distance invites the impossible question: can we image the other in her or his own terms?” (Chouliaraki and Ograd, 2011, p 341). Stereotypical media representations of Others that define *improper* distance are when media makers either appeal to two distinct discourses. The first - ‘common humanity’ - are depictions of others that bring the other into self-sameness. Alternatively - discourses of ‘strangeness’ - which, while acknowledging “irreparable distance between self and other”, often remove the political from this configuration in order to present media technologies as ‘acts of connectivity’ that cultivate our “phatic’ familiarity with the other’ (Frosh, 2011). Furthermore this reliance on strangeness is what leads to “a narcissistic engagement with ‘our’ own pleasures and desires in the face of disconcerting difference” (Chouliaraki and Ograd, 2011).

At first, from a critical phenomenology and critical documentary perspective Levinas’ account of the face-to-face feels progressive and liberatory, as it acknowledges power-over relations.

If one could possess, grasp, and know the other, it would not be Other. Possessing, knowing, and grasping are all synonyms of power (Levinas 1990, p. 90).

It rejects a presumption to ‘know’ the Other, in favour of a never-quite-knowing attention to her without her assimilation or ingestion²⁸. Furthermore Levinas’ ethics has been read as a project of not just talking *about* the other, but attempting to ‘give the other a voice’ and as seeking to empower disenfranchised groups (Davis, 1996, p. 144). As Ahmed notes, Levinas is read as ‘on the side’ of the minoritised Other, who appears in Levinas’ texts in a variety of guises; the widow, the poor and the orphan (Ahmed, 2000, pp. 141-142).

However, Levinas’ face-to-face and his version of existential alterity are not without criticism, most famously in a short footnote in Simone Beauvoire’s *The Second Sex*. In her brief but oft referenced feminist critique of Levinas, she problematizes his uncritical overlaying of the masculine and feminine in his conception of ‘Same’ and ‘Other’ which positions women and the feminine as the perfect examples of ‘infinite alterity’. As such Levinas presents ‘the relation between masculine ‘Same’ and feminine ‘Other’ to be *exemplary* of ethical relations’ (Anderson, 2019, p. 3). Most cuttingly de Beauvoir questions:

²⁸ In Levinas this is represented as ‘needing’ vs ‘desiring’, where desire, in comparison to need, is met with no satisfaction or ‘satiety’ (Ahmed, 2000, p. 139)

I suppose that Levinas does not forget that woman, too, is aware of her own consciousness and ego. It is striking that he deliberately adopts a man's point of view...When he writes that woman is mystery, he implies that she is mystery for man—so much that his description, which claims to be objective, is in fact an affirmation of masculine privilege (de Beauvoir, 1997, p. 16).

Levinasians protection of otherness, and in particular his use of women as unknowable 'face', has been read elsewhere 'effacement'. "Without the possibility of individual self - expression, the Other is denuded of its speaking. Denuded of her accents, cries [and] lamentations, the Other is, precisely in her concrete difference, that is in her embodied specificity, effaced" (Cynthia Willett quoted in Ahmed, 2000, p. 144).

Boundaries for Practice

Kate Nash's expansion on Silverstone's and Chouliaraki's *Improper Distance* is still a solvent description of the 'risks' the Empathy Machine genre presents to 'representing unfamiliar others as others with humanity' and the task of 'imagining the other on his or her own terms'. However the critiques of Levinasian ethic's lead me to be suspicious to take up his calls 'infinity of Otherness' (Anderson, 2020) within practice. Despite my hesitance to fully adopt a Levinasian ethic, there are some boundaries for ethical practice that emerge from this history.

The most prominent example of 'distances' that occur in 'The Empathy Machine' genre are geographical. Kate Nash (2018, 2022) is particularly critical of the recreated tourist gaze, and the tendency to represent 'distant' 'deserving' Others. Although one can, of course, be 'distanced' from suffering on one's doorstep, a very early decision in the practice was to not make work about a subject geographically far away, nor anything that resembled charity media, particularly about global majority people or refugees.

A more nuanced conception of the idea of distance however, would be an attempt to make a piece of work about something that audiences were not distant from *conceptually*. To make work around a topic that inherently *everyone* already has prior experience of, but that there might be some kind of 'emancipatory' potential to explore through VR documentary. As a

genderqueer or gender non conforming person myself, 'gender' became the most obvious first avenue to explore. In line with critique around the over-representation of minority gender, global majority people in 'empathy machine' VR, particularly women and children, I also decided to particularly seek out male contributors and also perhaps wider contexts or subjects that exhibit a certain western, patriarchal and heterosexual conception of 'masculinity' as the topic which the audience might 'orient toward' rather than "around" (Nakamura, 2020).

Further, prompted by existing critique, I wanted to avoid sensationalism. This is both sensationalism in Bollmer's sense, taking as ethically suspect an aim to recreate the sensory experience of a contributor, or permit the sensory exploration of the contributor's restaged testimony. I also aimed to avoid sensationalism in the sense that Nash describes, that in promoting VR as 'an empathy machine' one implies its most appropriate use is to maximise audience's emotional response to content. In this sense I wanted to seek an engagement with the topic of gender which didn't rely on generating emotional reactions for audiences, nor attempt to represent 'what it's like' for the contributor. The engagement with the contributor would, rather, encourage more political reflection from audiences. In the case of gender, this would be perhaps a reflection on gender itself as social construction.

These 'traces' (Kozel, 2010) of boundaries for practice are what I brought forward into my early experimental making.

3 EXPERIMENTS WITH QUEER PHENOMENOLOGY

Image 3. - 180 image of a rock face, August 2019

The Climb

I am setting up a VR game for a user testing session. The game is called 'The Climb'. Inside the game I look down and where I feel my hands holding controllers, I see only another pair of hands, free of controllers and cut off at the wrist. They are far larger than my real ones, and much stronger looking. I would say they were 'man hands'. I am setting up a lot of projects for the user testing session so I don't have long to explore the game, just to test that it works. The game allows me to choose from a range of climbing locations and scenarios. The aim of the game is to climb the rock face in front of me with my 'hands' by reaching and 'holding' onto its surface, using the trigger buttons of the controllers. I quickly skip through the instructions so that I can test the game play.

The game's aesthetic is very realistic, and exemplifies the promise of VR. In front of me is a red sandstone rockface, I can hear wind and birds in the distance, if I look down I see clouds and miles of rockface stretching below me. I have been magically transported to a place I will never get to be in real life, halfway up a mountain after hours of climbing. I can experience the thrill and beauty of this position without any of the risk. In fact, a part of the thrill is itself the feeling of risk without actually being at risk. The only risk in this climb is the risk of feeling a bit stupid, as I simultaneously perceive two realities on top of one another - one, as near death on a cliffside, the other knowing I am in a corner of an open office and that at any moment someone might see me 'climbing' (waving the controllers in the air). This, as well as my general lack of interest in climbing, leads me to gingerly reach up for my first hold. As if understanding my hesitation, the game makes up for it. It translates the half raise of my arm into a full body swing of this hand I control. My real body doesn't move through space like this at all, but this body makes up for my lack; it moves faster, reaches further, and is unburdened by the weight of my corporeal flesh. I move up the rock face at a pace completely unattainable to my real body. With each hold, the sensation in my 'real' hand of pulling the trigger with my index fingers, becomes transformed. I begin to feel like I am 'holding', rather than 'triggering', what I am seeing is affecting how my hand is feeling. I feel as if I am not performing a clicking motion, but a grabbing motion, my hands mimicking the shape of the climbers.

Gradually, the hands in front of me get more 'tired'. They indicate this with a 'power bar' like meter that is attached to 'our' wrist. As this fatigue worsens, 'our' breathing, the breathing that

the game is playing into my headphones, that I understand as 'his' but also 'mine', gets more agitated. A symbol starts flashing around my hands that suggests I need to 'chalk up'. I realise that I skipped through the instructions too fast at the beginning, and I don't know how to chalk up. The hands start to become red and sweaty and sore looking. 'He' starts sounding as if 'we' are in pain the more we climb. 'He' starts to moan in pain. I feel panicked that I am causing him pain and that our hands might just give way and we will fall to our death. Eventually, we just can't hold on anymore and we fall, but the game goes into slow motion and fades to grey, so this isn't as bad as I imagined.

*I take off the headset, and check to see no one was watching. Despite the amazingly detailed visual and sonic world of *The Climb*, the real world appears now so much more lush with possibility and vivacity in comparison, even though this is an office, and that was an exotic clifftop. The real world feels almost more real than before. I recover from this sensation and continue to set up for the user testing session. This involves going back to my laptop to send some emails. I start to type and as I do I become aware of my hands on the keyboard. Just as I felt 'inside' 'his hands' in the game, I now feel 'inside' my own. I suddenly feel my typing just as I felt the 'grabbing' of the rock, as my eyes confirm the sensation of the keys under my fingers, but the power of this sensation is magnified. Just as I heard his breath inside my head, I begin to hear my own and just as I felt responsible for his body I now feel responsible for my own. I become aware of myself inside this body, controlling it, moving it. I sense how this body moves, not like the climbers, more stilted, restricted. I feel the touch of the world pressing up against my fingers through the keyboard. This sensation is so profound I am almost moved to tears.*

I remember this feeling so strongly that I can tap into it now as I type these words. I felt amazed that for all the VR documentaries I had experienced, about so many topics, none had felt as affecting as this sensation. This experience did not claim to tell me about someone else' story, but by being placed in someone else' body, I felt something I never had before about my own.

Queer Phenomenology in Early Practice

In my early practice I was interested to see what would happen if I was to orient toward the invisible, the tendency toward the normative, without explicit reference to any 'Othered' experience or person. Could an attention to gender in this way destabilise the concept of

'normative' or 'natural' gender performance, as Davis (2004) suggests 'perceiving freshly'. To speak of or to the project of gender and sexuality equality without the need to appeal to a 'distanced' 'suffering' of an 'Other'?

There are many existing VR works that explore queer lives and gender, including many 'body swap' experiences. Most famous perhaps is the *Machine to Be Another*, a semi-performance piece in which a pair of people "of two different genders" either don a VR headset or head mounted camera and disrobe, mirroring each others movement as they do so and gradually undress (BeAnotherLab, n.d.). The result is a sensory blurring of one's own and the other's body. This performative piece has been enacted with many different actors, beyond a 'gender swap' concept to discuss race and other measures of difference. In a queer reading however, one might consider if the body swap experience reifies gender as attached to the sexed body, rather than disarticulating it from biological fact. Despite the sensitive language now present on BeAnotherLab's webpage around gender, the prevalence in the media material of gender swaps between legibly male and female participants, and the culmination of the experience being undressing, implies an understanding of 'difference' being biological sex differences.

VR however as a media, but also as a conception of cyberspace, has long been touted with the potential to expand and destabilise the relationship between gender and biological sex (Turkle, 1997). Famously the Wachowski sisters, the transgender siblings and writer/directors of *The Matrix* which might be *the* defining pop culture referent for VR, have described the movie as in part a metaphor about the 'real' and the 'discursive' world and a 'trans metaphor' ("The Matrix is a 'trans metaphor'"2020).

There are a number of works of 'empathy machine' VR which expressly focus on minoritised gender and sexuality, particularly series' on LGBTQ lives such as *Queer Skins* (2020) and *Authentically Us* (2019). These pieces follow forms present in much empathy machine content, and respectively focus either on recreating for the audience 'scenes from a life' of a gay man who died of AIDS related illness, such as the moment of diagnosis (*Queer Skins*) or allow us to 'meet' and 'step into the lives' of queer and transgender people, by experiencing co-presence with them in some space relevant to their particular story, like their home or work environment (*Authentically Us*). Press materials of the works explicitly describe 'empathy building' as a result

of experiencing the 'intimate interior worlds' or 'stepping into the lives' (Fovrth Studios, 2018; Queerskins VR, n.d.). The 'distance' of these works is that assumed between the experience of the user (as straight or cis-gender), and that of the documentary contributors' experience of gender or sexuality. More clearly we might suggest that what is oriented *toward* in these works is queer sexuality and trans expressions of gender as difference. The work is oriented *from* a position of heteropatriarchy and in doing so conforms to that heteropatriarchy as invisible standard or origin point to which the distance or difference of queer lives can be measured. However urgent the task of representing and acknowledging queer lives as valuable and vulnerable, this distancing is not necessary to discuss sexuality, gender or trans expressions of gender and could be read as ultimately unhelpful within the a queer project of gender and sexuality equality. Other works of XR, such as Rob Eagle's *Through The Wardrobe*, have more successfully explored gender and gender expression (particularly through dress) *as a universal experience*, which is rendered invisible for some (cis-presenting people) and hypervisible for others (gender non-conforming or genderqueer people). The mixed reality headset presentation of the work in combination with 'real world' installation, in which audiences listen to stories of genderqueer people, whilst being encouraged to interact with or wear physical and digital items of their clothing, further engages with these ideas of the visible and invisible in a playful way.

In *Queer Phenomenology* (2006), Sara Ahmed engages with Merleau-Ponty's numerous descriptions of 'disorientation' as a phenomenological method and effect in which objects "slip away" from grasp and understanding and become thus "queer". She also thinks about spaces, just like objects, as extending bodies. Spaces are shaped by what tends to happen there, just as bodies are shaped by what they tend to do. Spaces are shaped by certain bodies, and by virtue of being designed around that bodies movement, it designates other bodies that do not 'belong' to the space, that would find it harder to use²⁹. Thus some bodies tend to exist in certain spaces, shaping them, so that to be in them feels natural, as its *tendency* is embraced by the shape of the space (Ahmed, 2006, p. 51).

VR is in some ways a tool of disorientation, or rather, it reveals the fragility of orientation, exploded by even the slightest misalignment of movement and image. The history of VR in some ways is a history of striving to overcome this nauseating effect. Literal disorientation in VR

²⁹ Very broadly this description can be evidenced by the socio-material construction of disability (see Hamraie, 2017)

has sometimes been used to creative, if not particularly critical effect, such as Jordan Wolfson's *Real Violence* (2017). In this piece, audiences 'witness' a graphic yet strangely unemotional beating on a New York street, which may or may not be a hate crime (lightly implied by the use of a Hebrew song in soundtrack). The user watches on whilst their view of the event 'rolls' across the user's field of vision. The work is a combination of 360 video and VFX and the effect for the viewer is like being in a stationary roll cage placed directly in front of the beating. The piece was so nausea-inducing that exhibitions of the work installed safety rails so that stationary standing viewers didn't topple over in disorientation. This famously ambiguous artwork does not, certainly, aspire to any kind of emancipatory revelation (apart from as a vague critic of 'The Empathy Machine' conception itself perhaps) and the experience is somewhat sadistic in its intention to induce strong physical discomfort in audiences (Bollmer and Guinness, 2020). Certainly this work, when I experienced it, generated a most intense desire to turn away. One is almost completely consumed by your own feelings, both disturbed at the imagery and nauseous from the rolling. Ultimately I felt forced to shut the event out by closing my eyes.

My approach to disorientation in VR aims to be much less literal. As Wolfson's work shows, to be physically disorientated is such a powerful sensation that one cannot help but have a completely self oriented sensory experience, which as Nash suggests is exemplary of improper distance. What could be disoriented from (as in 'queered') could be more the physical response to space, or the feeling of 'tendency' toward a space, or conversely the experience of being 'out of place', rather than a physical disorientation in space itself.

The physical response to space in VR is well documented, with examples of VR in which users walk a virtual 'plank' or high wire, with heart rate racing and occasionally screaming, despite the 'knowledge' that their body was only inches from firm ground (Popat, 2016; Bolter and Grusin 2000, p. 164 - 165). What happens if we *turn toward* that physical response to space as a means to explore *it* as a documentary subject? This decision to at first work with space, orientation and gender performance was also informed by the technology available to me at this time, which was initially only 360 cameras. 360 cameras are most highly adept at rendering space, and generating 'presence', but are more complicated technologies to explore embodiment and agency³⁰.

³⁰ Embodiment and Interactivity are obviously not impossible to achieve through 360 video, and have been attempted to varying levels of success. 360 embodiment requires head mounted cameras on dummy's or actor's

The work I made across this time became explorations of this concept, but never became prototypes or publicly exhibited work. I will provide a brief account of each work using their working titles.

heads to give the impression of embodiment. Interactive 360 video requires running 360 video capture through games engine software e.g unity.

Passing WIP

Image 4. - Still from 'Passing' WIP, November 2018

Experiment 1 'Passing'

Early in my PhD I was living very close to Ibrox football stadium. Match days had to be marked on the calendar as the entire local area would be taken over by fans moving toward or away from the grounds. These migrations flooded the area with bodies, making it difficult to navigate streets and footpaths, particularly against the flow of this human traffic. These groups felt on approach not like individuals, but a unit, in their directionality and speed of motion, but also in their shared dress (football colours) and attitude, energy or group feeling; particularly after matches, depending on the result.

At this time I had a shaved head and so was experiencing a certain kind of freedom in my gender presentation. Depending on how I dressed and moved my body it was possible for me to 'pass', in passing at least, as male. This would mean that faced with moving through a crowd I could choose not only where to move but how to move, how to present physically - as male or female - in order to receive the least friction in my passage. This physical presentation might best be described as a kind of stiffening or softening depending on my chosen approach, neither feeling more 'natural' for my body to perform. This decision was made, it seemed to me, purely on an assessment of what might cause the least friction or interruption to my movement.

This physical reaction to the 'face' of the Other (in this case a kind of collective Other) felt like a fertile material to explore in practice, as well as related ideas about space and bodies in public (the street) and within architecture (the football stadium). As an early test, I wanted to try and record in 360 a recreation of being situated within this crowd in the hope that the viewer's physical response (perhaps the stiffening or softening I felt) might be 'turned toward'. I was interested in drawing attention to this physical reaction as a response to a virtual experience, in other words, drawing attention to audiences perhaps gendered 'response-as-if-real', as a technique of 'disorienting' audiences from this as 'natural', allowing them to 'perceiving freshly' this experience. In doing so the work might permit audiences a 'critical distance' from gender performance enough to discuss 'passing' or 'performing' as something experienced by both cis and trans gendered people, and further illustrate gender as not a biological fact but an embodied experience.

Practice activity on this project consisted of two sessions of 360 camera test shots around and inside the football stadium, attempting to see if it would be possible to generate a sufficient feeling of presence and co-presence within these moments of group movement to engender this sensation. In these test shots, the camera was placed at around 'eye level', in aid of facilitating presence. Without at that time a stable enough tripod, this required me to stand beside or hold the camera myself. As well as the outside and inside of the stadium, I also shot outside busy pubs in the area associated with the resident football team (Rangers) fans post match. Very early on it became evident that the camera itself was interfering with the capture, as it drew more attention (to myself and it) than I would have alone. 360 cameras are relatively unusual looking, attracting more curiosity than perhaps a traditional camera might. However I do also believe that the use of any camera may have drawn a similar response for reasons I will later outline.

The most interesting moment I capture in these early tests is an interaction between myself and a bar bouncer. For me personally, this shot is particularly interesting to reflect upon as it's possible to see the moment, from the 'outside' perspective of the camera, of my own physical 'softening'. In the shot I am stationary outside a busy bar. This individual walks up to the camera holding a silver tray, attempting to hold it 'over' or 'in front' of the camera to stop it filming or to stop it filming his and others faces, indicating that he does not want to be filmed and also that he does not understand this camera is filming in all directions. He asks me what I am filming, but as he does he hesitates and acts slightly surprised. This is a response I, at that time in my life, often experienced, and read as someone being confused by my gender, or as the moment in which they realise I am not a cis-male as they may have presumed. In this moment in the video recording, which is slightly tense, I visibly soften my face and attitude, presenting not only as friendly, but also quite feminine. I reply "I am trying to capture the post-match atmosphere" and giggle - tension dissipates and he laughs and repeats "oh, post match atmosphere" and walks away.

At the conclusion of these experiments, and on reflection with my supervisory team, the 360 capture, while still very interesting in terms of gender, is not 'doing' what I wanted it to. The ability to capture the crowd presents problems in terms of both ethical approval and due to the influence of the camera on crowd behaviour. Moreover, my aims for the footage presented an

ethical question of 'using' the contributors as essentially atmospheric objects. Rather than capturing individuals, I sense my trying to 'use' the capture of the crowd to summon up a feeling of gender performance in the viewer, which I might then endeavour to turn their attention to. There was something uncomfortable for me in this 'use' of the crowd as objects, rather than subjects and individuals, as well as this 'use' being of service to a completely introspective and solipsistic experience of the audience. This felt like an example of an 'improper' distance, and is one reason why this particular line of practice was not explored further.

I was attempting to use the Rangers stadium and fans to capture essentially 'group behaviour' of a certain 'masculine' flavour, which I experienced personally. However, there are broader cultural implications that quickly emerged within or overlaid upon the footage. There is a 'hooligan' characterisation of football fans, that this footage seemed to reference, which carries additional preconceptions around race and class. In Glasgow in particular, histories of sectarianism in football, and with this team in particular, were also unavoidable undercurrents to the images. This team, and the associated pubs, have historically been linked with hate crimes and sectarianism (Morrison, 2024) that not only influences the experience of the footage, but also how these crowds might respond to being filmed, which they might associate with policing, surveillance or negative press scrutiny. I believe this is palpable in the actions of the bouncer. Finally, the national lockdown made more filming impossible, as crowd events were suspended, and added a further conceptual layer onto crowd footage. During the period of social distancing and for some time after, the most palpable response to crowd footage was one of discomfort and fear around the possibility of covid transmission (Heathcote & Kiefer, 2020). For all these reasons, *Passing* was not explored as a piece beyond these test shots.

 The OH Expedition WIP

Image 5. - Still from 'The OH Expedition' WIP, October 2019

Experiment 2 - The OH Expedition

In the first year of my PhD I am struggling to find subjects for my documentary practice. I don't know many people and I am beginning to feel like I don't really understand much about the culture around me, academically or more broadly, as an English person in Scotland. I am feeling quite lost.

On Instagram I see a post from an old hometown acquaintance, Tom, who is moving to the Outer Hebrides to attempt to live for a year in a tent, whilst walking, writing, and raising money for Alzheimers UK. This mission is a response to his fathers history as an 'exhibition leader', taking English inner city school kids to the Outer Hebrides in the 60's and 70's, as well as his fathers recent Alzheimers diagnosis. Tom names this proposed activity (and associated Instagram account) 'The OH Expedition'.

There seemed to me something mis-timed about his decision to pursue something so dangerous and isolating, precisely at the moment of his fathers diagnosis. Tom was the only son of three still living at home, and without his own family or work commitments. His leaving left his mother to become the full-time, sole caregiver for his father. Tom's actions felt, from my outside perspective, as those of someone who also felt a little lost, and I reached out to him.

Although Tom was documenting his own journey through a combination of journaling, map making and social media posts, he agreed to me visiting him, as well as to some recorded telephone and in person conversations and some 360 filming at points in his journey. At the time I am not sure whether this project quite fits into my research, or what the intended outcome will be.

Over the next 8 months, Tom and I stay in frequent contact and I visit him on the Hebrides 3 times. Across the course of this, Tom's attitude and outlook changes drastically. In the spring of his arrival, Tom is exuberant with enthusiasm about the rich possibilities of his 'quest', as he plans to literally and figuratively 'forge his own path' through the island, creating alternative walking routes to those in his many books and maps, including those taken by his father. My last visit is in a wet, cold and isolating autumn, and Tom is semi-squatting an empty cottage and questioning his choice to leave his family, and his ambitions to 'know' the islands, what that

had meant to him and what it means now in the face of his fathers steep mental deterioration. Tom ends up leaving the islands just before winter. The first cases of Covid-19 emerge in the UK that January and Tom spends the lockdown living at home, helping care for his father in the last 9 months of his life.

My early conversations with Tom engage with many of the themes I am interested in exploring. There is the undertone of a certain kind of 'masculinist' project of an 'expedition' in which the 'wilderness' becomes something to be navigated, mapped and 'known'. This is also interesting when considered against the historically 'feminised' caregiving responsibility Tom might be otherwise engaged with back home, the inherently 'unknowable' quality of palliative care, as well as the potential threat of the demasculinization of the head of the household 'losing' his memories and knowledge. These tensions are all themes Tom brings up himself in our recorded conversations.

In test shots, presence in the spaces of the Hebrides Tom frequents; the interior of his tent, the various hostels he visits and landscapes he traverses are all well captured by the 360 camera. What is less well captured is the act of *moving through* the landscape. Tom and I both muse about the represented stillness of the 360 capture versus his more dynamic experience of walking and we consider alternative ways this might be captured³¹. Similarly, what is captured in the audio is mine and Tom's conversation, and his thoughts as prompted by my questions. What is not captured is the huge periods of silence and ineffable direct experience that Tom is predominantly engaged in. A final dissonance in the experience of filming is that Tom spends the majority of his time alone, which my presence interrupts. Filming in 360, especially in a landscape as treeless and bare as the Hebrides presents the problem of my presence within the 360 field of vision of the camera. In order for me to shoot Tom so he 'appears' as he ostensibly 'is' - alone - I have to go to great lengths to hide, which means laying down in ditches and silently huddling outside the tent in the rain. The artifice of these actions feels quite in opposition to the authenticity of Tom's action and intention.

Ultimately, although this project 'looks towards' the 'close to home' - masculinist and western fantasies of the wilderness, aloneness, the expedition, map making and so on, that point is

³¹ 360 video when used to shoot motion, especially when not 'steadied', is liable to cause motion sickness and nausea.

made by replicating the form of 'empathy machine' content that Nash critiques. It attempts to recreate in some way for the audience Tom's experience. Although the feminist leaning of our conversations does bring attention to political dimensions of Tom's activity, it also encourages a turning away from Tom by making him an 'object' of discussion. The work in some ways questions Tom's motives, even if this occurs through his own voice over and reflection, enacting an Othering of Tom, making *him* strange, as well as perhaps the wider constructions of gender at play in his actions.

Although this project is valuable to me personally, and has become an ongoing collaboration between Tom and I to be completed at a later date, it very quickly appeared incongruous with the aims of this thesis to explore a form of VR design that enforces or enacts 'proper distance' beyond traditional empathy machine formats. In facilitating a 'looking at' Tom, even from a broadly feminist or critical perspective, the work in its design does not engage the audience in any reflexive capacity as to their own experience of gender or their act of looking. For these reasons The OH Expedition is not expanded beyond test shots and recorded conversations.

Queer Phenomenology in Existing Practice

In reflecting on my early practice, I felt I was struggling with an 'orientation around' personal, internal reflections on gender, whilst 'orienting toward' contributors as objects that might facilitate this introspection. This felt at odds with 'proper distance' as previously outlined.

At this point in practice I wanted to 'turn back' to my time as VR curators and host, to reflect on two works of VR documentary that stood out on a conceptual level. I felt these works upheld proper distance in the turnings, orientations and extensions facilitated by their interactive mechanisms. As Nash (2018) has suggested, many VR documentary works, in their focus on emotional response and visual exploration, promote a 'profound turning away'. By contrast, these works encourage a turning toward or, indeed, an interactive engagement with the contributors of the work which is neither objectifying or othering, nor relies on users emotional intimacy with contributors, nor present contributors lives as 'experienceable'. It is through reflection on these works that I come to re-evaluate the term 'reciprocity' or 'the reciprocal' within VR documentary. This term describes the interaction possible in these works and subsequently leads me to reconsider both the VR platform for my practice (moving toward

embodiment and interactivity), but also to question the appropriateness of the Levinasian ethics when evaluating 'proper' distance in interactive media.

Orientation in Zohar Kfir's 'Testimony' (2017)

Testimony is both a VR documentary and expanded web based archive of first person accounts of people who have experienced sexual assault. I first experienced *Testimony* in 2017. The *Testimony* site is no longer live, so the following description is based on my memory of the work and screen recordings available online.

I am in a black endless space, with light particles and smoke effects that float in the air, giving this space a sense of depth. There is a sombre ambience to the space created by this and the soundtrack which is unobtrusive. The effect is reminiscent of celestial space, but also perhaps a mental space, and also digital space. I feel in a sense that I am 'in' a website landing 'page' or in a cinematic rendering of 'inside the mind'. I do not have a body in this space, and this space is not one that affords a body; there are no walls, floor or anything else that would imply a body.

In front of and all around me appear a series of circular 'windows'; flat black and white video clips of different people, shot as 'talking heads'; in front of darkened backgrounds, facing the camera directly. There are multiple videos of each person, and each person's videos are connected by a white line, like an abstracted vine, on which the video 'windows' hang like fruit. These vines criss-cross around me. There is no 'starting' point from which to begin the experience, but each vine lightly suggests an order of viewing for that contributor. As I look more directly at one of the figures in her video window, a light animation of the vine seems to 'bring' the window towards me, like a flat plane of glass. Once the plane of the video is at an appropriate 'watching' distance, it unpauses and the figure starts speaking to the camera. As she speaks, the dark space of the interface behind her lightly animates in a way that gestures towards the story - abstracted visual effects of a flashing police siren, for example, but so subtly I hardly notice. After a while, I look away from the video, and the video plane recedes and joins the others on the vine.

Zohar Kfir's work continues to stand out to me as an unusual VR documentary, working much more in the lineage of websites or webdocs, than an embodied VR documentary, or anything

that might be described as 'storyliving'. What is immediately obvious is that there is *no attempt* to generate a feeling of co-presence with any of the interviewees. We are clearly not in a shared space. They are clearly a flat video, and I am also not really embodied in a 'place' in any architectural sense. Although there is light animation that accompanies each video, it does not facilitate me to feel present within the contributors story. The contributors stories themselves are quite long, and discuss the wider context of a sexual assault experience beyond the event itself, including telling friends and family, reporting to the police and in some cases going through legal proceedings. There's a range of people; of different ages, races, genders and sexualities, and of stories. The contributors' testimonies are all different, some more emotional, some more conversational. The project clearly aims beyond just a collection of descriptions of rape experiences, toward an archiving of testimonies that, taken as a whole, are critical of a culture that does not listen to survivors. These various not-listenings are represented in the stories by failures; of police, the law or legal system to prosecute perpetrators, failure of loved ones to believe survivors, and in the case of the male contributor, perhaps a cultural failure to acknowledge that men also experience sexual assault.

In its design, it doesn't appear that *Testimony* utilises many, if any, of the affordances which are claimed to make VR an appropriate medium for documentary, particularly in 'Empathy Machine' conception. I do not feel presence at the site of contributors suffering - there is no vivification of these stories as 'truth' or 'reality' to me. I do not feel present *with* these contributors more than I would in a flat documentary or website. I don't 'meet' them, they don't make eye contact or respond to me. The agency or interaction I have in the experience is, in fact, very limited. I can choose in which order to engage with the stories, and crucially I can choose to listen to a story or not. There is a received logic that might beg the question - if the project isn't utilising presence, co-presence, embodiment or more engaging kinds of agency and interaction - *why would you make this project in VR?* And yet this project for me in large part *only* works in VR *because* of VR's embodied interface and the way the project engages with the concept of 'turning' and 'orientation'.

The project clearly does not aim to generate a traditional conception of embodiment - I have no body, and the space construct is not one that implies a body. However the project is navigated through a form of *embodied interaction*. I do not engage with this content by clicking or

searching, nor sitting back and observing, as a webdoc or traditional linear documentary might invoke. The interaction *is a turning toward* the speaker. The documentary *itself* is receptive to my turning to a contributor video, and responds by bringing that content *toward me*. The video does not just start, or enlarge, the video physically *comes to meet me*. In this sense the documentary engages me in a spatial relation to its content. If my attention wanders, or if, for whatever reason I feel I cannot listen to the story presented, in my act of *turning away*, the figure and their story *move away from me*. Even though it's clear that the testimonies are not live, but pre-recorded, and there is no simulation aimed at disguising this fact - I am, non the less, having a live, *and reciprocal* relationship with them. In this embodied sense, the documentary speaks to the reciprocal impetus of listening - if I am not listening, these figures won't speak, and if I can't listen, these figures won't force me to.

The experience of *Testimony* and its construction as a work of VR documentary is one completely at odds or in opposition to the 'Empathy Machine' template, and the 'turning away' as described by Nash in key 'Empathy Machine' works³². *Testimony*, as well as being a sensitive and culturally critical documentary about sexual assault, also represents to me one of the most cogent examples of 'proper distance' in action.

Extension in Anagram's '*Make Noise*' (2018)

Anagram are one of the most established immersive documentary makers currently working in the UK, and their practice spans VR, AR, audio walks and installations. *Make Noise* is a 2018 BBC commissioned VR project about global women's rights and more specifically the activism of British suffragettes. The piece utilises animation, audio archive and audio responsive interaction. In my work as a curator and host of VR exhibitions I have shared *Make Noise* with hundreds of audience members, and I have programmed it in multiple VR exhibitions and festivals. From a VR curator's perspective, *Make Noise* is an impactful yet enjoyable and playful piece of work, particularly to show in a VR cinema or group audience setting. From a critical maker's perspective I find *Make Noise* to be an effective navigation of the risk of improper distance, in particular improper distance in the form of *extension* facilitated by interaction.

³² Nash does herself discuss *Testimony* as illustrative of 'proper distance' (Nash, 2020 pp. 118-119).

To begin Make Noise I have to press and hold the 'trigger' of the small controller that operates the Oculus Go headset I am wearing. After I do this, and enter into the piece, I won't have to touch it again because, as the introduction explains, "here your voice has power" (Abdalla, 2018)

As the abstract visual 'world' of Make Noise is revealed to me, a voice over tells me that "here" my voice can "make change". To illustrate this, floating spiky balls expand and contract in response as I speak aloud as instructed. In a series of stylized and colourful landscapes, I hear the authentically crackly audio archive of women describing their feelings - "the women was wakening up! [sic]", and actions - "I used to smash the windows of the home office as regularly as I could, and I was very good at smashing, because I could smash on the run". These are the voices of elderly suffragettes reflecting on the movement. The striking range of accents in the voices indicates the inter-class union of their fight to be legally recognised as "proper persons[sic]". At different points in the work I am encouraged to "use my voice" to do things like 'smash', 'push' or 'blow away' representational objects of oppression; clothes pegs, hammers, irons and handcuffs. I have to do this by shouting out words of protest like 'rights!' and 'fight!', or calling out the names of women who inspire me. In the final scene I am called to "build a monument with [my] voice". The more sustained a note I hold, the quicker the pieces of rubble before me congregate to form statues of significant women. This experience is all supported by a thumping and percussive soundtrack that allows me to fall into a kind of rhythm when shouting, and provides a musical key and backing track for when I sing my final monument building notes.

The experience of speaking aloud inside the headset, especially in the presence of others, is exceedingly awkward and embarrassing. There is a sense of being seen and heard, when you cannot see or hear the other, which makes you feel vulnerable and exposed. There is a shame associated with breaking the social contract, and responding to voices that aren't 'really there' or others can't hear. This is a palpable sense of misalignment between me 'in here' and the 'real' world outside. This feeling can also be experienced when one has to 'do' something inside the headset, like walking or reaching and grabbing. Most headset experiences allow audiences to perform a wide range of motion and activity in-headset with relatively little bodily effort perceptible from the outside, requiring a physical motion more akin to the relaxed

operation of a TV controller. The experience of using voice to interact with the content is one of exposure. I can perceive my voice as an extension of my body, spilling out of this headset and into the real world venue I am in, beyond even the people or person with me in this room, out toward maybe even other people in the building.

The world of Make Noise is fun enough however, for me to push through this embarrassment. The interaction is responsive in a way that encourages me to 'push' my voice further. Each time my voice falters or is not quite loud enough, the work will show me - a clothes peg I am trying to 'blow away' might wobble but not quite fall. This sense of a goal causes me to draw more air into my diaphragm and push my voice out louder in order to 'hit' the obstacle with appropriate force. In the final statue building scene, if my voice 'runs out', the pieces of the statue start to fall apart and all the construction I have achieved comes undone. For my final notes I have to completely fill my belly with air in order to sing the note long enough to 'complete' the statue and the result is that I am almost shouting along with the music.

Showing this work to group audiences involves at first a lot of giggling. Some audience members are embarrassed to speak first, while others try to test what might happen if they don't speak at all. As the work progresses however, audiences become more confident, both in understanding what is required by the headset, and emboldened by the sound of other voices around them. By the time they approach the scene in which they call the names of women who inspire them, many audiences laugh aloud, as they begin to call each other's name, or the names of mutual friends and family or public figures. This sense of togetherness in the piece builds until the final scene where, in an act which is quite moving to witness from the outside, the group start to 'sing' their monument building notes in harmony with one another.

As a host, one particular sharing of the work stands out to me. In this sharing, most of the group behaved as normal, but one audience member remained silent throughout the entire work. When he came out of the headset I asked him what had happened, if the piece had worked as normal or if something had gone wrong? He replied to me that although he had not worked on Make Noise, he was a technologist in the BBC's R&D department, working on VR and other new media. He said, rather proudly, that actually you don't "have to" make noise. That you can, in fact, just blow on the microphone which is embedded in the bottom of the

headset, and this will 'trick' the interaction. I was amazed in this moment, not only that one might be such a buzzkill as to refuse to take part in ostensibly light hearted group noise making, but more seriously, that someone could listen to the voices of the women inside the experience and decide to try and trick the system. I was shocked that whilst hearing women describing these amazing acts of bravery and discomfort, of 'stepping out of line' in an era of extreme regulation of womens bodies, actions and movements; smashing home office windows, chaining themselves to buildings, risking social exclusion, imprisonment and death for women's rights, that anyone, let alone a man, might actively try and avoid the admittedly socially uncomfortable act of noise making in the headset.

This user allowed me to articulate what I had previously only physically sensed in the interaction of the work. Although, evidently, not foolproof, I understood that not only was the experience of noise making in the work a symbolic act of solidarity with these women, and contemporary women's rights activists globally, but also a means of ethical relation with the work.

In order to listen to and see this work, I had to give of myself (my voice) and make myself in some way vulnerable, as these women had done. This reciprocal relationship exemplifies the proper distance of this work. In this piece, the act of interaction is not framed as an exploration of these women's lives and experience, which permits a consumption of their experience to extend what my body 'can do'. But rather my extending out (sending my voice out, but also being 'out of line' with social convention) is reframed as reciprocal action. Moreover, this action has 'real world' consequences - I might be heard by others and therefore in some way exposed or made vulnerable. This vulnerability is not equal to the sacrifices of the Suffragettes, and is certainly not a re-enactment of their action, nevertheless there is a relational quality to my giving and receiving of voice in the piece. This ethical contract in the work was made all the more palpable to me in the actions of the audience member who undercut it.

Turning Toward Embodiment: Early Technical Proposal for *With These Hands*

At this point in my research the most interesting examples of work that seem to address proper distance do so *through their embodied interaction*. In my own experiments in practice using 360 video, I had not been able to avoid pitfalls of improper distance such as a tendency toward

'Othering', and 'using' the represented documentary contributors as *objects* with which to explore the wider documentary subject of gender performance. Moreover the reflexivity of the works had relied on voice over instructing audiences to 'turn toward' their own embodied experiences and reflect on them. Footage of contributors became mere backdrop to this. In particular, this resulted in forms of improper distance as outlined by Chouliaraki's 'ironic' mode "that reduces the world-beyond-us to our own 'truths' about ourselves" (Chouliaraki, 2011, p. 373).

Through recalling my experience in *The Climb*, and by experiencing another piece of work *She's Already Gone* (2019), I start to sketch a proposal for an *embodied* piece of work, that might also facilitate reciprocal, embodied interaction. Particularly I was interested in exploring embodiment as a tool of phenomenological disorientation, or rather, reorientation, in which contributor and audience might be found to be in more equitable relation to one another. Where audience and contributor might be found to be in 'alignment' through a shared embodiment, so that they might *orient together* toward an object or subject such as gender presentation. However it was eminently imperative that contributors and their bodies not be presented as 'corpus nullis', as empty of biography, but simultaneously their biography must not be alluded to be communicated through embodiment 'under their skin'. I was also interested in the experience of 'sharing skin' as bringing phenomenological attention to skin as the imagined boundary between Self and the Other.

In *She's Already Gone*, artist and painter Yu Hong had 'painted' aspects of the virtual world in her natural medium of oil paints. Collaborating VR company Khora then used these paintings to texture the objects of the virtual world. I could see how this world was constructed, the artist paintings were like skins, which were then wrapped around the bare extremities of the 3D models. This gave me the initial technical idea for a project which evolved into *With These Hands*.

Rather than recording likenesses of contributors, the skin of their hands could be photogrammetrically scanned, and this scan could be used to re-skin or texture 3D models of hands, which could be used as the means to interact in the work, much like *The Climb*. Rather than 'meeting' a likeness or representation of the contributor, or being placed in *the position* of

a contributor 'in their shoes', the audience interacts with the work *using* the hands of the contributor or 'with' them. This concept felt to me quite different to any other embodied VR pieces I have previously experienced and technically, not something I had seen before. All avatars I had seen previously were CGI, more or less realistic, that stood in for 'real' contributors. I had also seen characters that are 'met' in VR, constructed through 3D capture, but I had personally never seen a project that embodied users in 3D captured material.

On first consideration, it would seem apparent that any VR documentary in the 'in-the-body' genre poses an exceptional risk of improper distance and is perhaps incompatible with a critical Queer understanding of embodiment. Not only do in-the-body-of works actively encourage a merging of audience and contributor, and present as replicating "what it feels like" for the contributor, but they also imply the *difference or knowledge* to which the audience gains newfound insight *is in* the body. The body *is* the object of difference, rather than any socio-political construct which is projected onto that body. However, I began to consider what the effect would be if audiences were embodied *in the hands and skin* of a contributor, rather than being *in their shoes* or *in their mind* or *in their body*. An experience *in the hands* or *in their skin* does not make such knowledge claims about the body represented. In one sense it merges, as it merges sensory experience of the user - touch - with the 'skin' of the contributors. However, in another way it distances; not only the user from the contributor, but also disorients one slightly from the usual perception of touch and particularly self-touch, inflecting it with phenomenological attention.

I was particularly inspired by these passages from Merleau-Ponty's *The Phenomenology of Perception* (2022):

If my left hand is touching my right hand, and if I wish to suddenly apprehend with my right hand the work of my left hand as it touches, this reflection of the body upon itself always miscarries at the last moment: the moment I feel my left hand with my right hand, I correspondingly cease touching my right hand with my left hand

(Merleau-Ponty, p. 105)

When I press my two hands together, it is not a question of two sensations that I could feel together, as when we perceive two objects juxtaposed, but rather of an ambiguous organisation where the two hands can alternate between the functions of 'touching'

and 'touched.'....The body catches itself from the outside in the process of exercising a knowledge function; it attempts to touch itself touching, it begins 'a sort of reflection,'
(Mearleu-Ponty, p. 106)

This concept for digital embodiment presents the opportunity for the representation of the 'other' to in some sense, 'touch' audiences back. This represented a key shift in thinking for me; bringing audiences attention to the sensation of touch might present opportunities for them to 'reflect' on 'improper distance' inside this, and potentially other VR work.

This new conception for a work brought new challenges; I didn't have an idea of what the work would be about specifically, or who my contributors would be. I didn't know exactly how the textures would be made, nor any specific ideas about which headset would be best to design for. At that time, hand tracking without the use of controllers would require additional hardware to be incorporated, such as an external sensor. I also understood that I would need to seek the assistance of a VR production studio or unity developer, and therefore required additional funding. This moment also coincided with the advent of the pandemic in March 2020.

In August 2020 I did some basic research and development (R&D) on this project, at that time untitled, with a Glasgow based VR company. At that time it was unclear when headset sharing (which would be required in exhibition if this project were to be designed for VR) would be deemed safe and additionally not *feel* unsafe or disgusting³³. Hence we explored a version of the experience which combined hand tracking with overhead (or rather over-hand) projection. This work was carried out under that company's NDA, and is therefore not shareable within this research.

In September 2020 Oculus released the Quest 2 headset (Meta, 2020), which substantially improved on previous all-in-one VR headset models - providing 6DoF experiences without external sensors and a computer, and including controllerless VR interaction via hand tracking. Between late 2020 and late 2021, I worked on securing funding to research and develop this project as a Quest 2 experience, whilst also seeking an appropriate collaborating production company, and documentary subject for the work.

³³ Like crowds, the touching of objects and especially sharing of objects that touch the face, felt to me at least, more disgusting during the high pandemic.

4 PRODUCTION OF WITH THESE HANDS

With These Hands - Practice Based Arefact

Image 6. - Photogrammetry of Moss Asset for 'With These Hands', October 2022

Speaking, Listening and Turning Away

In March 2020 the whole of the UK, and much of the world, goes into lockdown. As a result, I, and most people I know are using our phones more than ever before. To connect with loved ones, to read the news, as entertainment, as a semi-mindless stress relieving activity. My phone and computer become my window onto the world. In May, news of George Floyd's murder breaks, and the virtual window of my phone, usually open on the image and video sharing platform Instagram, is awash with videos of this awful event.

Then, it becomes awash with criticism of those sharing of the videos.

Then it explodes with the images of Black Lives Matter protests all over the world, accompanied by waves of posts about how to take 'action'. These include infographics, lists, hyperlinks, books, films and donation pages. There are how-to's; how to write to your parents, how to write to your local politician, or how to make posters and banners to hang out your real window. Happily we share and re-share, tweet and re-tweet this information. It feels like the 'right' thing to do in a confusing time, where there are real questions about how best to conduct a civil rights movement during quarantine. Change, however, seems possible. A concept that gets shared within these infographics is that we might be able to move beyond our current harmful policing system if we can challenge our perception of crime, and our predilection to punishment.

Sharing and re-sharing online takes on a new cultural significance. Quotes like Audre Lorde's 'Your Silence Will Not Protect You' and the phrase 'Silence = Violence' (a take on the AIDS activism slogan, Silence = Death) are repurposed in shareable graphics and hashtags. The sharing of posts themselves becomes the opposition to 'silence', becomes a 'speaking' in solidarity. Some friends message other friends to suggest they aren't posting 'enough'. There is a sense of one's social media being watched, and an unpleasant urge to repost information, not to share it with an imagined new audience, but as evidence to a surveilling audience.

By June, lockdown is still happening but in different forms; local lockdowns, home isolations and quarantines. Posts are still being shared, but different kinds of 'speaking's and 'silence's are imagined in them. One such post is black text on a white background that reads:

*"If I am friends with your abuser
DM me
and that will change
I see you. I hear you. Your story matters*

The "DM me" meaning 'direct message', is in a bolder, purple font. Perhaps it's been edited or overlaid onto an original post that used different terminology. Perhaps it once read "tell me" or "talk to me". Perhaps it's just a different colour for emphasis.

The image gets shared by people I follow, some local, some across the world. It goes 'viral' and I see it posted many times a day. Along with this post, other posts start being shared. These other posts and reposts name different people from different communities across the world as 'abusers'. These are followed by posts from people who know the 'abusers', coming forward to publicly disassociate from them. This then happens to someone I know tangentially. This person loses many of their close friends very publicly, gets asked to leave his flat and loses his job within a few days. Male friends of mine tell me they are scared to bump into him, as they don't even want to look at him.

I find this post and moment very troubling. It makes palpable the limits of solidarity by this virtual definition. The "If I am friends" post seems exemplary of the ways online 'solidarity' corresponds with an attitude of disengagement from more complex relating. A 'turning away', exemplified in the way my friend feels he can not bear to even look directly at this person. In this post the use of 'DM me' turns the word 'friends' into a virtual, and therefore expendable connection. A result of social media's repurposing of social language is that one can 'friend' and 'unfriend' someone at a click of a button.

The sentiment behind this post is no doubt to believe and act in solidarity with survivors of sexual violence, which is admirable and necessary in lieu of other forms of justice and safeguarding³⁴. However, the post turns the 'action' of that solidarity into a click of a button and the sharing of a post. It doesn't give any further advice or instruction about how else to support

³⁴ This thesis does not suggest that a criminal conviction necessarily represents victim justice. Nevertheless it is a fact that less than 2% of all rapes reported between 2021-2022 were later prosecuted (Parker, 2023).

this survivor, who is also required by the post to outline their abuse in a 'DM' (no easy task or small ask). It also doesn't suggest any further obligations of me the reader to my 'friend' the abuser, in fact, quite the opposite. Although this post purports to be about listening to survivors - "I hear you" - it doesn't foreground the listening act at all, nor what comes after. Instead it advocates for a turning immediately from an account of harm (another turning away) to 'unfriending', and ceasing all contact with the named abuser.

This post seems unaligned with the current cultural moment, in which we are collectively becoming more aware of the harms of policing and prisons, and attitudes to crime and criminals which dehumanises them, sometimes to the point of lethal force. This post completely bypasses any constructive approach, or opposition to this carceral logic³⁵. By carceral logic, when someone harms another, society is made safe when we lock them up, separating them off, so the law-abiding public doesn't have to engage or even look at them. To support survivors beyond a carceral logic would not be a social shunning of a perpetrator of harm, but would involve imagining ways to bring that person into community, into a restorative dialogue or action. This would require a far more attentive listening to both survivors, perpetrators, and also ourselves, as we assess our abilities and limits to do so.

Conceptual Origins of *With These Hands*

I had previously met SLEEC through interviewing them for a VR project I made separate to my PhD research. However, I started attending their workshops after the aforementioned moment in my personal life during lockdown and encouraged the men around me to do the same. SLEEC in their work actively approach the problem that if we culturally want to move away from policing and carceral logic, men must learn to speak with other men about violence against women³⁶. Further, we must, as a society, find new ways to engage with 'perpetrators' of gender based and sexual violence.

³⁵ Carceral logic is a worldview which underpins both the US and UK policing and justice system, in which retribution, control and violence are seen as central components to ensuring public safety (Lopez, 2022).

³⁶ A project which later became even more pressing over the timeline of this project, in the wake of the March 2021 murder of Sarah Everard by serving police officer Wayne Couzens, the failures of the UK police force in regard to that case (Dodd, 2024) and further emerging data on violence against women committed by police officers in service (Hall, 2023).

Through working with SLEEC in my professional and personal life, I built a rapport with Meggan and Bryony, the survivors who run the organisation. I also began to see profound overlap between the problem of perpetrator and survivor representation in existing media and the ‘improper distances’ of empathy machine VR content.

With These Hands is the result bringing the proposal for a VR mechanic - the ‘wearing’ of the photogrammetrically produced ‘hands’ to interact with real and virtual objects - into dialogue with organisational aims of SLEEC. SLEEC work to platform original content from survivors which push back on what they see as dehumanising and othering portrayals of survivors and victims in mainstream media. In particular their Disobedient Survivor Blog presents ‘unheard’ narratives of sexual assault and recovery, written by those with lived experience of sexual and gender based violence. They also organise survivor lead workshops and drop in spaces for men to discuss male violence, rape culture, masculinity and patriarchy. As SLEEC describe on their website;

Whilst it’s essential that survivors direct this work, responsibility has to shift onto men. We need new ways for men to be actively involved in dismantling the roots of male violence. Collective organising is a necessity. We build spaces through education, conversation and research that prioritise men’s relationship to patriarchy and rape culture. (SLEEC, n.d.)

SLEEC and I’s shared ambition was to use VR as a platform to share ‘unheard’ narratives of SA and survivorship, which aim beyond simplistic stereotypes of victims and ‘perpetrators’³⁷, to more accurately represent the “complex and messy” (SLEEC, n.d.) aftermath of sexual assault. In this now more developed conception of my project, titled *With These Hands*, pre-existing writing from survivors and victims of rape and sexual assault, and further original writing from a male or ‘perpetrator’ perspectives, would form the content and subject of the VR documentary. Access to these stories and their authors would be facilitated by SLEEC, including those who had submitted their writing to the ‘Disobedient Survivors Blog’, and attendees to their workshops for men.

³⁷ The complexities of the word ‘perpetrator’ and the specific content of this work will be discussed later in this chapter.

My practice based research aim was to explore the potential of this VR mechanic to support those ambitions, aiming through the narratives and the works interaction design to encourage 'proper distance' between authors, their experiences and audiences. The project and its aims sat comfortably within my broad subject of phenomenological experience of gender and gender performance. Of all my practice experiments, it was this project that was pursued to prototype, as it provided the richest site to expand my practice based research.

Dominant public discourse of 'survivors', 'victims' and 'perpetrators' of sexual harm are rife with 'improper' distances and a large portion of SLEEC's work is dedicated to unpacking how these contribute to the minoritisation and tokenisation of survivor voices, and ultimately perpetuate gender based violence. Exploring literature around the topic of sexual assault and sexual consent provided a wealth of additional phenomenological research on alterity, reciprocity and consent, which is brought to bear in this chapter on both the notion of proper distance, and 'empathy'. Reflective of the interplay between theory and practice, the following chapter interweaves passages of thick description, and accounts and images of practice, with supplementary theory relating to discourse on sexual consent, rape and survivors in media it's, including the experience-led knowledge of SLEEC themselves³⁸. My work on this project and with SLEEC is broadly separable into 3 sub-chapters; Pre-Production, Production and Exhibition.

³⁸ In the following sections I quote SLEEC and other collaborators on this project and these accounts are derived from my memory and notes. These sections have been shared with my collaborators for edit or comment before inclusion in this final document.

4.1 Pre- Production

In my research up to this point, ‘proper distance’ had been largely conceived as the appropriate relationship between an audience, a documentary contributor and the documentary material. However, across pre-production with SLEEC, the term also proved useful in thinking through the relationship between a documentary maker and a documentary contributor. This expansion of my research is perhaps seeded by Chouliaraki and Ograd’s (2011) proposition that “proper distance invites the impossible question: can we imagine the other in her or his own terms?” (Chouliaraki and Ograd’s, 2011 p. 341). This pre-production process began with a process of listening to what those ‘terms’ might be.

SLEEC and I’s work on *With These Hands* began in late 2021, when I approached them to co-apply for development funding to explore the ethics of making media with and for survivors³⁹. The funding would support a series of workshops; one knowledge sharing session between SLEEC and I, and two further co-run workshops with their wider ‘Consult Survivors Community’, and prior attendees from their survivor-led courses for men, respectively. The remaining production funds could be split between us to support research and development of two separate creative outcomes; a VR documentary for me, and a podcast interview series for them. Through these workshops, SLEEC could also assess if they would want to continue working on *With These Hands* as consultants, if the project were to receive further production funding.

Both SLEEC, their wider cohort, and I, understood that they would be feeding into a pre-existing creative project, which was already in-part technically developed. In this sense the project was not ‘co-creation’, or collaboratively designed. However, it felt important for the ethical ambitions of the project that any funding for *WTH*, including this early development funding, also financially support SLEECs independent work. I do therefore describe our work together as ‘collaborative’, and to SLEEC as my collaborators and consultants, whilst acknowledging the limits to this terminology and SLEECs ability to creatively influence a project already in development.

³⁹ Please see the funding timeline in Appendix I.

In our first workshop, in which I shared with SLEEC the technical proposal for *WTH*, SLEEC laid out to me some creative boundaries for the project moving forward. Firstly, I would, where possible, use the original writing of the survivors and provide them opportunities to edit, voice and be scanned for the project themselves, if this was their choice. If not, the authors should be given final choice on any casting decisions and considerable influence over virtual environment design for their scene. Survivors who gave their original writing and likeness to the project should be paid for their creative work, and paid a non exclusive licence fee for their writing, in line with SLEEC's own publishing agreement. It was also important to SLEEC that the project contained at least one male perspective story, as one of the most pervasive issues SLEEC approach in their work is the perception of gender based violence as a 'women's issue', despite most violence against women being perpetrated by men. This too was something I wanted to include, based on my own personal experience.

The aim of the second and third workshop was to present the concept for the VR to the two groups SLEEC would collate from their network in order to gather feedback. Specifically we would be asking the groups how they felt these stories should be told, how the authors should be framed and represented, and what the benefit and also what might be the potential harms of sharing stories from both survivors and perpetrators perspectives in a single creative piece of work.

SLEEC had already done considerable work in considering what a contract might look like between a publisher and an author, which they currently used for their blog and in their other work. SLEEC and I decided that the second workshop would be with a group of minority gender sexual assault survivors - SLEEC's 'Consult Survivors Community'. Along with creative feedback, we would seek feedback from this group on what kind of materials; contracts, consent forms, licensing agreements or other forms of agreement would support more ethical relations between a documentary maker and a contributor. During this workshop we would present for discussion a series of example documents; from SLEEC's own contract, to more traditional media and university consent and release forms and practices. A practical outcome of this workshop would be a reimagining of the documentary consent process, which could then be presented to the university ethics board and used in production.

The third workshop would be with prior attendees of SLEEC's 'Dismantling Male Violence and Rape Culture' survivor-led workshops. Bryony and Meggan inform me that the men who attend their workshops have often been in a similar position to the one I described to them, where someone in their social circle has been publicly or privately accused of sexual harm. The SLEEC workshops act as a valuable venue in which the men can speak with other men about issues of misogyny and rape culture, whilst supported by survivors with direct experience. This project's workshop would ask these prior attendees what kinds of stories it might be useful to represent, if men in their position were the imagined audience, and what narratives would they find helpful or affirming to hear. Ultimately in this workshop we would also assess if any of these attendees might be interested in sharing their personal experience within the project. SLEEC's blog does not share writing beyond those with direct experience of sexual violence, so for the male perspective narrative/s, we would be unable to work with existing content.

The framing of the 'male narrative' within this text, and *WTH*, as one relating to a 'perpetrator' or male sexual violence is not to suggest that men are the *only* perpetrators of sexual violence⁴⁰, nor that men are never victims of sexual violence. However, SLEEC's organisational mission, and subsequently an ambition of *WTH*, is that men are encouraged to take up male sexual violence against minority gendered people as a 'men's issue', and something to be addressed within their friendships and social circles. In my own experience, it was the male friends of the named male 'abuser' that were the most inclined to 'turn away' from their responsibilities to that friend and the situation. SLEEC in their work have identified this as a common experience, and as the result of the feminisation of the labour of supporting assault survivors, holding perpetrators to account and publicly critiquing rape culture. It therefore felt important that *WTH* provide a narrative from a male perspective on male violence against women and minority genders.

The workshops were not only hosted by myself and SLEEC, and we were joined by relevant co-hosts. These included VR documentary maker Jane Gauntlett and sex worker and activist Black Venus for the SA survivor group, and activist, academic and social psychologist Lewis Wedlock for the men's group. SLEEC and I decided not to record these workshops, because in SLEEC's experience it limits what people are comfortable to share, and can stifle the

⁴⁰ Although this thesis is critical of the policing and justice system, it is pertinent to acknowledge that male perpetrators are an overwhelming majority of sexual assault convictions, at 97% in 2022 (Rape Crisis UK, 2025).

conversation. Instead, I proposed an interactive document containing prompt questions and example material that attendees could edit and comment on. In practice however, the most fruitful and compelling moments in the workshop was the live discussion, which has no formal documentation save my own notation.

In the following accounts of these workshops I bring my memories of these workshops, my notation and the written contributions from attendees together with relevant academic literature. In doing so, I trace the impact of these three workshops on the experience design of *With These Hands*, the contributor call outs and the version of a consent agreement that was eventually used in production.

Workshop 1: Between Eyerolls, Empathy & Hands

Despite travelling all the way down from Glasgow to Bristol to meet with SLEEC in person and share some VR work with them, I am now holed up in an airbnb with Covid, and we are meeting once again on zoom. Bryony and Meggan join me from the sofa in Meg's house.

I hit the 'share screen' button, and they see that I have prepared a multi page presentation about the ethics of Virtual Reality documentary and my concept for a VR project. They look at each other and shuffle in their seats awkwardly. They say they haven't prepared a presentation, as they were just expecting a more casual chat. I say that's ok and for want of any alternative, commence on a 20 minute monologue. Luckily, Meg and Bryony are generous listeners, and I am able to introduce them to the concept of 'the empathy machine', the ethical issues of representation and the classic 'empathisable' documentary subject: a 'good' 'suffering' 'victim'. They then tell me about the origins of SLEEC.

They had both quit their jobs and volunteer positions in sexual assault and sex worker support services. They fundamentally objected to the moralistic and paternalistic position those services took toward their users, and were becoming disillusioned by the limitations of charities' to make palpable change in service users' lives or on a wider political scale. They were also both at that time experiencing what they describe as a 'breakdown', and decided to do that together on a beach in Mexico. There, they experimented with taking pictures; in bikinis, eating cake on the beach, napping in bed and buying themselves bouquets of flowers, exploring how to produce

an image of a 'survivor' or 'victim' in 'breakdown' that they felt they themselves could relate to. For them, it doesn't look like the images on the front of charity support pamphlets: black and white images of anonymous women with their face in their hands. For them it looks like people resting, treating themselves, being angry, looking sexy or stupid, half naked on a beach. These aesthetic experiments became the origins of SLEEC; a bright and joyful social media account and website, dedicated to supporting survivors of sexual violence in various ways including; a mutual aid fund, talks, workshops and a community blog which shares challenging and unheard stories written by survivors. When Meg and Bryony speak in workshops or to the press, they use the moniker 'the disobedient survivors'.

We move on to discuss my concept for 'With These Hands'. I share a storyboard in order to explain the experience and user journey.

There is an awkward silence. Meg and Bryony are looking at each other, once again shuffling in their seats.

"What is it?" I say, I can sense that something I have said has touched a nerve.

"We kind of" says Bryony, laughing awkwardly "we kind of hate hands".

"Yeah we're just so sick of hands, they are everywhere in survivor pamphlets and stuff, like covering faces or holding coffee cups" says Meg, rolling her eyes "we actually have an instagram post where we wrote about how much we hate it".

"It's the anonymity," explains Bryony, "being forced to be anonymous. We don't want to be made anonymous and we don't assume other survivors want to be anonymous either.

Sometimes I have wanted to publish writing using my own name and picture and I've been told by the publisher I can't"

At first I am surprised. Although the hand focused design of the project was about a certain kind of embodiment, and attempting to move beyond a simulated 'face-to-face' encounter, it had also crossed my mind that it also permitted the anonymity of the contributors. I, just like Bryony was suggesting, had not considered that a contributor might not want to be anonymous.

At the same time I am excited that SLEEC aren't afraid to tell me that they hate my idea. I am also excited because, even though our ideas of how it might be achieved are different, we are both interested in representing the survivors as whole, complex individuals and not just generic, sympathetic characters, represented by generic, anonymous hands.

I explain that the hands I want to make, unlike those in the SA support pamphlets, will be highly detailed scans of the contributors hands and when the audience 'wear' them, every scar, wrinkle and fingerprint will be visible. I want the hands to feel like an intimate portrait, and far from generic or anonymous. "That's amazing though" I finish "that you wrote about that. Maybe in the piece, we can actually use that bit of writing?"

In my first workshop with SLEEC it becomes clear that the problem of representation pervades their work as well. SLEEC's use of the 'the disobedient survivors' moniker is a clear challenge to a certain conception of what a sexual assault survivor is, or how they are expected to behave in order to be believed, deemed worthy of care, support or respect. In short, *empathisable*. It exposes the expectation of 'obedience' to a behavioural script, in which, for example, that person would want to be anonymous, feel ashamed about their experience and perhaps, not eat cake on the beach in a bikini. Behind SLEEC's tongue-in-cheek images is a desire to redefine a 'survivor' in a way that holds complexity, and their moniker is a self aware reference to the challenges that language poses to that.

The use of the word survivor, even, SLEEC explain to me, is contentious. Proposed at first to overcome associations with the term 'victim': a person who has a crime 'done to' or 'perpetrated upon' them. 'Survivor' is felt to imbue the person described with more agency, moving away from the event of crime etymologically. The Latin of survive being 'super' ("over") 'vivere' ("to live") (Online Etymology Dictionary, n.d. -e), shifting emphasis to one's ability to "out live" or "live beyond" an assault. In other words, a recovery of life or selfhood after the implied depersonalising experience of a rape or other sexual assault. This term however is not unproblematic. For example, a person who has experienced a rape or sexual assault might well feel that they *have indeed* been a victim of a crime perpetrated upon them, and that the word 'victim' better acknowledges their lack of complicity in the event, which it may feel important to recognise. Furthermore, the term survivor still defines the person described as permanently

marked by violence, even while it acknowledges their continued existence afterward. The term 'survivor' is also associated with words like 'strength', 'bravery' 'overcoming' 'recovery' which imply an upward and forward trajectory which does not always align with the non-linear experience of 'living beyond', including 'break down', 'regress' and 'flash-backs' which are natural parts of not only being a 'survivor' but also a human being.

Beyond 'victims' and 'survivors' is the even more limited available language to describe 'perpetrators' who 'commit' rape, sexual assault, sexual misconduct, sexual harm or gender based violence. The 'perpetrator' figure has no space for complexity, already defined by legal terms denoting guilt, intent, criminality and immanent punishment. In SLEEC's abolitionist perspective, the prison industrial complex is so mired with racist, classist and ableist constructs that it cannot be reformed to a more equitable system, nor perform a role in a more socially holistic approach. As such, the language of that system cannot be repurposed beyond its original use, nor broadened to hold complexity. It has been expressly designed to define, separate and subjugate 'criminals' as a separate category of human being which are less-than. On the other end of the spectrum, 'those who harm' feels so vague as to become almost moot. "We are all, obviously, capable of harm" Meg says, and while it's important to acknowledge that fact, there are different degrees of harm, of which some are easier to countenance than others, and some are easier to be held accountable for than others.

Part of the impetus behind the course SLEEC run for men is the urgent need to unpack the figure of 'the perpetrator'. Many of the men in attendance find it hard to know how to address accusations of sexual harm made against their friends because they simply cannot marry their experience of their friend as a whole human being with this narrow image of 'a perpetrator'. The result is a bind in which either the person *is* a friend, and therefore *not* a perpetrator, or *is* a perpetrator and is therefore *not* and perhaps *never was* a friend. Similarly, people accused of sexual harm or violence are greatly disincentivised from acknowledging culpability because the language and image of a perpetrator does not suggest 'living beyond' this definition.

Embedded in the carceral language of perpetrator is the demarcation of the less-than-human. As such it is understandable that one accused might do everything in their power to refute being labelled as such, rather than acknowledge harm caused, or engage in any reparative or restorative action.

SLEEC have written on these thoughts often, including in a call out for a 'disobedient survivor' photoshoot, in which they summarise the problems of representation;

Survivors are depicted as one-dimensional, often shown as weak, broken and dehumanised. Usually, we are reduced to faceless figures, silhouettes, shadows or body parts.

This causes deep problems in how others (and ourselves) view this part of our identity. Not being represented as human, as normal people with a range of emotions creates a huge separation and detachment to us. We are an outsider, we are othered. We [are] reduced to our experience, our trauma.

This is not helpful to our recovery or our perception of trauma or the impacts of violence and abuse. People are not only uncomfortable with survivors/victims looking and presenting as powerful, capable, multifaceted individuals but it leads to us not being believed or validated if we do not fit these stereotypes. Within the charity sector we need to be seen as incapable and vulnerable so that we can be 'rescued'. People want to save, so we need to look like we need 'saving'.

This type of imagery exists because we live in a society where people need to 'deserve' support and help. We have created a set of conditions that determine what deservability[sic] looks like; innocent weak female victims and violent bad male perpetrators. (SLEEC, 2024)

It is apparent that SLEEC have their own conception of an 'improper distance' between the image of a survivor and what it actually is and looks like to have experience of sexual violence, and how this manifests in interactions with support services. There are also obvious issues of distancing in the insistence on representing 'bad male perpetrators'. We agree that undermining these limited characterisations of the authors and contributors within *WTH* should be a priority of not only the writing, but of the VR design, and wider installation itself.

At the conclusion of our workshop SLEEC agree to consult on the production of *With These Hands*, and act within a fixed capacity to connect me with potential contributors as chosen from submissions to the disobedient survivors blog.

Workshop 2: "We HATE Consent Forms"

Later in the conversation Bryony asks "why can't the people in the documentary show their faces as well? I really think it's important for people to show their faces if they want to".

I explain my feelings about representing a 'face-to-face' interaction in VR. "I met Sidra" (referring to the Chris Milk talk which I have shared with them earlier in the meeting) "Or I feel like I met her, but she didn't meet me. She doesn't benefit from any of the feelings I had toward her. They don't go anywhere, those feelings, they just hang around inside of me".

I also talk about the conversations I have had with Jane Gauntlett, and her documentary about her own epilepsy, in which the audience 'meet' her at the end. "People come up to her crying" I say "people she has never met come up to her as if they know her, and sometimes they might tell her something really intense or personal, about their own experience of epilepsy or someone they know. And while it's amazing to connect with your audience, people feel like she has shared something intimate with them, but in actual fact that was pre-recorded, and in real life she might have never chosen to do that with this person. I don't think that in VR, showing a face works the same way as it might in another medium"

Meggan and Bryony nod back to me. "That happens to us sometimes. When people hear what we do they sometimes just immediately disclose something that's happened to them or someone they know, and we aren't always ready for, or in the space to hear that"

The conversation continues and I talk SLEEC through documentary and university ethics processes. We discuss 'consent' and 'release' forms, and how I would have to pre-produce these for the ethics committee for review before approval.

"We HATE consent forms" says Bryony "it's such a stupid idea - that I could consent to something that's going to be written or made in the future and I don't even know what it's like

yet! How can I consent to that? And how can the consent be something that I just give away once at the beginning and then it's gone and I can't take it back? We hate the whole idea of consent forms. Can we just not have them?"

Defining Consent

In recent decades, consent has been at the fore of discourse on both sexual and documentary ethics and “consent is taken to have the unique ability to transform otherwise impermissible acts into permissible ones” (Anderson, 2020 p. 1). In their definition of sexual ethics, consent distinguishes, or rather transforms sexual violation and rape into sex. In the case of documentary ethics, contributor consent permits the documentation of events, and signifies the contributors ‘release’ of their image, words and ‘story’. Consent in this context protects the maker's right to reproduce these towards his own ends as he sees fit, often ‘in perpetuity’, regardless of the impact on or wishes of the original consenting party. In both conceptions, consent is something that is given in response to a request, and two parties are conceived; one who requests, and one who can either permit or refuse this request. An ethics that requires one either ‘give’ or ‘attain’ consent before action is suggested to protect the more vulnerable party from abuse. Feminist critique has illuminated however that, in practice, consent can just as easily be utilised by a more powerful party to refute an accusation of abuse. If consent - by some definition - was obtained, then the accusation of abuse cannot be sustained (Alcoff, 2018).

Issues of sexual consent are a key area of expertise and interest of SLEEC and the wider Consult Survivor group. Beyond this however, SLEEC themselves and many of the Consult Survivors group are also writers and activists, and have interacted with journalists and media before. As such there was extensive knowledge, experience and critique of traditional conceptions of media consent agreements in SLEECs existing work and featured on the Disobedient Survivor blog. Considering that *WTH* as an artwork, and the work surrounding its creation would be forming a large part of a PhD research project, and would therefore be subject to an ethical review, I deemed Bryony's request to abandon the consent form altogether beyond the limits of this project. However, early on in the planning of our funded activity, SLEEC and I proposed to bring the Consult Survivors group's expertise to bear on the

creation and conception of the documents which would be reviewed by the ethics approval board, and form the *WTH* production's answer to the 'consent form'.

The main aim of the second pre-production workshop was to facilitate a discussion on how media makers can engage more *consensually* with contributors or collaborators to share their stories, as well as a discussion of what specific challenges VR as a medium, and similarly, working within an institution like a university, poses to that ambition.

The rest of this segment will take excerpts of notes taken live during that workshop by myself and others attendees within an interactive document made for that purpose. I also include screenshots of the document itself where appropriate. Prior to this I will here briefly summarise the feminist critiques of definitions of sexual consent as these inform and interplay with the critical ideas raised.

Consent as speaking

Rape is an 'essentially contested category' and as Joanna Bourke (2007) illustrates in her text 'RAPE: A history from 1860 to the present', one defined within specific historical, political, economic or cultural contexts. Even within the narrow context of say, contemporary British law, rape is not a concretely defined event (Bourke, 2007 p. 9). It is sometimes defined by an accompanying act of violence or physical force, and sometimes the act itself, however enacted, *is* the violence (Brownmiller, 1975). Sometimes it's defined *by* a vaginal penetration by a penis (Greer, 2018) and/or the emission of semen, yet at other times other orifices and objects "have been included in the corporeal mapping of rape" (Bourke, 2007 p. 9). Sometimes, the accompaniment of "non-penetrative assaults" with "high levels of degradation and trauma" bring that assault into the same punishable level as Rape (Udal, 2003). It is a matter of debate if all non-consensual sex is Rape (Greer, 2018). Furthermore, sometimes the refusal to heed or acknowledge a "no" is the grounds for deeming a sex act non-consensual, and sometimes it is the failure to acquire a verbal "yes". More complex still are the instances in which a body's action are thought to read, rightly or wrongly, as communicating a "no" or "yes" beyond the verbal (Angel, 2022 p. 14, Anderson, 2020).

Despite the complexity of defining Rape, the ameliorative power of 'affirmative and enthusiastic consent' has been championed by universities', op ed's and books aimed at parents and young adults and integrated into law (Anderson, 2020), and pop culture, along with related maxims: "no means no!" (Angel, 2022 p. 19). However feminist critique suggests that consent as it is commonly discussed is insufficient to deal with wider patriarchal social scripts that destabilise a yes means yes, no means no definition of sexual consent as a speech act (Angel, 2022).

Within a patriarchal society, it has been argued, consent is socially coerced, even in some instances so as to avoid rape (Cahill, 2001). Or in other words, one might say yes when one means or feels no. Conversely, within these cultures, for women to desire different kinds of sex with different people can carry social stigma. To even develop awareness of such desires has historically been socially discouraged. In other words, one might feel yes, and say no (Schulman, 2016, p. 49). Furthermore, there are instances in which a body is so culturally sexualised that it can, legally if not ethically, justify the assumption of a yes, beyond even a verbal no. This is evidenced in the way the clothing and underwear of rape victims is brought into court cases to attest to the defendants confusion around whether a sex act was consensual, and the legal difficulty in assessing rape in the context of sex work and dating apps (Angel, pp. 11 -13 & p. 30). The disproportionate conviction rates for assaults on White women as opposed to Black women can be read as both a bias against Black women in the legal system, and that Black women's racialisation incorporates a hypersexualised component that is taken to muddy the waters of consent. In other words, some no's mean more than others and "if no is meaningless how can yes be meaningful?" (Angel, 2022, p. 14). Consent is also, in cultural practice if not in theory, gendered and heterosexualised, as something women give or withhold, and men ask for or receive. This lays the burden of deciding the limits of sexual contact to be predetermined by women on the commencement of sexual contact or even beforehand. Secondly, it prescribes men as always wanting sex, an ominous pre-cursor to the idea that rape is the natural and inescapable result of men not able to attain 'enough' sex through consensual means (hooks, 2004, p. 81 - 82).

The #metoo movement began with community activist Tarana Burke in 2006 (Brittain, 2024), but rose to prominence during the public reckoning of Hollywood producer Harvey Weinstein in

2017. This movement and its focus on 'speaking up' is emblematic of a contemporary moment that valorises women's self knowledge and speech as a feminist duty that protects against rape. In this moment, which author Katherine Angel (2022) dubs 'consent culture', consent is charged with the ability to transform all the ills of sex; from rape all the way to bad and unenjoyable sex⁴¹. This version of consent demands the unequivocal and informed speech from women engaging in sex to 'speak up', not only about sexual misconduct and harassment, but also to 'know what you want and to ask for it'. The necessary fall out from this is that a woman who does not know what she wants, or does not say from the outset, makes herself vulnerable to the inevitable consequences. Angel makes the connection between 'consent culture' and Rosalind Gill and Shani Ograd's 'Confidence Culture' (2017), a liberal view that presents women as free autonomous individuals, and transforms structural inequalities that women face in society and in the workforce into personal failings of assertiveness, self belief and self love. Sara Ahmed describes the oppressive phenomenological experience of this double bind, in which women are called to 'speak up', as if the constraint on speech was only an internal experience, and not culturally cultivated external pressure, with the implication that women and girls are "their own obstacles, in the way of themselves" (Ahmed, 2016).

This liberal definition of consent as a speech act also further suggests consent as a contract between independent free agents (Anderson, 2020). The ample criticism of this contractual conception of consent has at times been accompanied by the presentation of alternatives. These include to conceptually reframe consent by suggesting new dialogic metaphors of generosity or gift giving (Diprose, 2002) or to deposition consent as the only and ultimate norm guiding sexual ethics by incorporating it into other practices or acknowledging different 'degrees' of consent (Alcoff, 2018; Kukla, 2021) or completely abandoning consent (Fischel, 2019; Ichikawa, 2020).

Although these existing debates were not expressly referenced in the workshop with the consult survivors group, much of this workshop understandably focused on the language of 'contracts' and 'consent'. The group raised challenges to the language of documentary and

⁴¹ It is of note that there is ongoing debates on the boundaries of bad sex, non-consensual sex and rape. Some argue the boundaries between these might in fact be arbitrary (see Cowling 1998) and if rape is non-consensual sex, it's possible there is more rape than sex occurring in most heterosexual marriages (Greer, 2018). Conversely, others argue that the collapsing of bad sex, non-consensual sex and rape is an epistemic injustice to rape victims (Brison, 2022)

university consent documents, by referencing the ways these were at odds with a more nuanced conception of sexual consent as an agreement.

Consent as an agreement

The workshop with the consult survivor group was 2 hours, on an evening in April 2022. My overriding memory was that the time went so fast, and the conversation was so rich that I was struggling to speak and make notes at the same time.

I had made a document in Gdrive that acted as the shared backdrop to the conversation, but was also editable. Attendees who could make 'suggestions' and 'add comments' which would show within the text respectively as edit's or as a linked comment to the right of the main document (see Image 7). The document itself featured a series of prompts which were posed by SLEEC.

It quickly became apparent during the workshop that attendees were much more interested in speaking than in editing the document. The participants could, however, see me taking notes in the document during the session. Despite not functioning as expected in the workshop itself, the functionality of a shared document which records multiple authors' edits, did eventually become integral to the 'consent document' outcomes. Despite the document used in this workshop not reflecting a plurality of *direct* voices as intended, it does still record the multiple perspectives which informed both the production and content of *With These Hands*.

The first set of prompts put to the group was: "What feelings and thoughts come to mind when you think of consent forms and contracts?", "What negative connotations and words do you have?", "What positive connotations and words do you have?".

Image 7. - Workshop Responses, April 2022

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Giving up power

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

What do I gain from this?

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Negative: They are often quite inaccessible. It is often difficult to change them - it might also take a long time.
Positive: There are ways in which we might be able to change this - to make them more accessible.

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Negative: A plot
Positive: A plan

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Plans are dynamic, and can be interacted with in the future

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Loosing privacy

 Sex and Rage
Apr 13, 2022

a contract should be powerful, never violent

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

One person gives consent, and one person takes it.

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Negatives: Disempowering. What if I change my mind?
What is the intent?

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Inflexible
What if it doesnt feel right anymore?

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

A formal acknowledgement of a power exchange

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

The beginning of a conversation

 [Redacted]
Apr 13, 2022

Negative - Intimidating and long/inaccessible language
- Usually only offered in English/translations are left up to the person signing

 [Redacted]
Apr 13, 2022

Positive - Good to look back to for info
- Informative/clarifies what you're getting into
- Tells you more about who you're working with / opportunity to spot red flags

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Support post review

 [Redacted]
Apr 13, 2022

- Being able to choose if you include your face/name/bio
- Being informed about the organisation and other work they have created to see how your story may be presented/formatted

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Showing the end project before sharing it.
Telling you when it will be shared

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

'Trust'

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

The trust to be part of this process

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Shift ideas about power - it's not always a negative.
What is going to be done with this power?

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

A violent contract is different from a powerful contract

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Someone gains something, do you loose something?

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Positive: Lifting the burdon of sharing.
'Grateful to be taken out of my hands'

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Communication, credit, compassion

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

Someone Put labour into this, someone cares about this.

 Tessa Ratuszynska
Apr 13, 2022

A period of time to alter things

The first responses recorded are negative; consent forms and contracts can be inaccessible in their presentation and formal language; they represent one party gaining something - the contributor's consent, and imply the other party loses something - the right to privacy, their autonomy, their right to change their mind.

However, there were also positives proposed about the traditional consent form format. The necessity of signing a document provides a formal moment to have a conversation about shared goals for a project and final outcomes, and can essentially act as a 'conversation starter'. The presentation of a well thought out consent form can demonstrate the "labour" and "care" a maker has invested in the process and the project as a whole. Working with an artist can in some ways unburden the contributor of the sole responsibility for sharing their story alone, and the consent form is the moment in which trust in that filmmaker or artist can be assessed by analysing this agreement for "red flags". A contract makes explicit and formal the power imbalance between a maker and contributor, and brings this relationship into focus for both. Other comments on the document discuss a formal vs informal approach of the filmmaker, and suggests that there is some protection in the more formal presentation of the consent form and/or contract because it "might make it easier to challenge things without making it feel like you might upset the project leader".

Ultimately the group concludes that there is enormous value in having a shared document that communicates at the beginning of the project its ambition and boundaries, that can also serve as a record that both parties can return to, but that additionally this document must remain in some ways flexible and amendable. This is summarised by one participant as the difference between a 'plot' and a 'plan'. A plot is the future desires or designs of one person, into which the other is employed or entrapped. A plan is formulated by this speaker as 'dynamic', a way for one person to share their desired goals and how they think they might get there, but one that does not prohibit a change of course down the line or the constructive input of the consenting party.

SLEEC have already themselves thought deeply about contracts and have designed a supplementary or alternative document that they use when sharing the work of others, or when they are asked to share work by other organisations. As a group, we look over the SLEEC

document and make comments. The first comments are about the name of the document which is titled 'Agreement'. This document positions itself even in title as a way for two parties to reach consensus, rather than one party making demands to which another consents to⁴². Reflecting some of the group's comments, this document is also relatively formal, but deliberately does not use overly complex language or formatting. The 'agreement' template, which is geared toward a publisher/author relationship, interestingly leans *further into* the format of a contract rather than away, despite deliberately abandoning the term in its title. SLEEC's agreement document has the express intention of listing for the benefit of the contributor the obligations of the publisher, and through this aims to redistribute power in this relationship. The agreement becomes a way for the author to hold the publisher to account if they fail to uphold their obligations, which include communicating with the author the date they plan to publish, pre-discussion of any excerpts they might choose to embolden or highlight from the text and to ensure the author has the choice of which name to be published under, their own or a pseudonym. It also includes space for discussing fees and establishing the non-exclusive nature of the relationship between author and publisher - the rights to the work and ideas remain the author's.

The workshop time was weighted toward thinking through the media or journalistic consent form and its alternatives, and spent considerably less time on university ethics approval documents and consent forms in that context. The interactive document included a number of University ethics guidelines lifted from various universities websites. These guidelines err considerably more toward protecting the rights of participants, rather than overtly protecting the research or researcher. A key difference being the right to remove one's contribution from a study at any time being a staple of much research design, unlike media consent forms which aim to protect the inclusion of the contribution, even if a contributor chooses to leave a production or filming. Although we do not spend a lot of time discussing this difference, I leave the document editable for the participants post-workshop, and encourage them to add any more notes if they think of them.

Subsequently, a number of notes do appear in the document, illustrating that some participants did go back into it to add their thoughts. The examples I provided in the document discuss

⁴² In latin, consensus means to 'come to an agreement', and is the past participle of latin root of consent; *consentire*. (Online Etymology Dictionary, n.d. -d).

additional ethical concerns when working with 'Vulnerable Participants' who are deemed unable to give 'competent or unfettered informed consent' including; adults with learning disabilities, adults with mental illness and additional concerns about research which refers to 'highly sensitive topics' including; race, ethnicity, spiritual beliefs, sexuality, abuse and personal violence, criminal activities, and mental or physical health. After the workshop, next to this section, appears this comment:

This following section shows how these ethics agreements come from a place of "power over". Every identity marker that is mentioned below is associated with someone who is marginalised. And the irony is that the people checking if a project is ethically safe are usually power holders. So the only way for them to ensure the safety would be by them actually double checking with the "participants" and contributors personally. People who share a lived experience with these vulnerable groups should have to assist with determining the ethics of a project but even the term "highly sensitive topics" just shows that the power holders just want to cover their asses in case something goes tits up - nothing to do with ethics really.

It's clear that this writer considers the approach of the university an overstep. The university grants itself authority to decide the ethical suitability of a study or work which includes people, it is implied, who may experience marginalisation due to any one of the listed identity markers. This author believes that those with lived experience of marginalisation are far better placed to assess the ethical quality of the proposed work than a university ethics board, who do so from a position of power or "power over". One which, this commenter suggests, also ultimately serves the same self interest as the example of journalistic consent - to protect the academic and the institution from an accusation of abuse or unethical practice when a project goes "tits up".

The main outcome of this workshop was an understanding of the importance of shared information, enabling a shared perspective or common understanding between documentary maker and contributor. It is commonplace that a consent agreement in a university context would be supported by a 'participant information sheet' but it was stressed in this workshop and particularly by the above comment that the purpose of that document was not merely to

assure participants that the work was deemed ethical by a university body. The information document had to provide each participant with enough information not only that they could give 'informed consent', but that they could also assess the ethical quality of the work themselves before agreeing to take part. It had to describe not only *what* would happen, but *why* and *to what end*.

It also was evident from this workshop that this project's answer to a 'consent form' could not be a static, one off agreement signed by a contributor, and held by myself the maker, but was required to be a "dynamic" "conversation starter". It must be flexible and editable, yet concrete enough for both maker and contributor to refer back to if things go "tits up" and "includ[e] for the inevitable that something might eventually go wrong". This version of a consent form and associated information sheet is one in which the maker provides a "commitment" to support the contributor if and when this situation does occur, a document where both parties commit to a project, and a plan of action to which the maker too can be held "accountable".

In response to this workshop, I drafted both a 'With These Hands Project Deck/ Information sheet' and a 'With These Hands Consent form', both can be viewed in appendix ii and were approved by university ethics approval board 28/07/2022. In the information sheet, I provide information about what '*With These Hands*' is; a 7-15 minute VR documentary, and why I am making it; a brief summary of my PhD including critique of the 'empathy machine' rhetoric. I also include a second page of information in the form of two questions; 'What am I asking from you?' & 'What am I offering to you?'. This approach was to make explicit my commitment *to* them as a collaborator, as well as being clear about what it was I was requesting *from* them, highlighting the relationship as one of exchange rather than purely extractive.

The 'consent form' itself is relatively traditional in format, and consists of a table of questions with two columns beside which allow for a yes / no response. However, it opens with the following passage;

This form can be completed digitally or we may read the form aloud and discuss the questions verbally. This conversation can be recorded so we both have a record of what has been agreed. Please let me know your preference.

Space has been left in the form to accommodate further consent statements you want to add. We can make changes to the statements if necessary. Your answers on this form are not final. We can reassess your consent at multiple points across production, whenever you want.

If you do not feel you can sufficiently answer yes or no to a question at this point in production we can leave it blank.

Through this project I learned that while participants can be very enthusiastic and active, they do not necessarily want to do the work of editing themselves and may be hesitant to do so for many reasons; missing out on the ongoing conversation, fear of ‘messing up’ the document or just a general resistance to a tech based interactions which feel separate and less dynamic than the oral conversation. According to collaborative filmmaker Kat Cizek, some contributors “want to be involved in the creation of media, but have absolutely no interest in picking up a camera, recording or editing” (Wiehl, 2017, p.39) and the same could be said of editing a shared document. I developed through this workshop an understanding that working in a ‘collaborative’ way does not necessarily mean that everyone must work equally on everything nor that there is inherently more equality in a project without structure and defined role. One workshop attendee in fact points me to the Jo Freeman (n.d.) essay *The Tyranny of Structurelessness* that dissects the infeasible and potentially disingenuous pretence of presenting structurelessness as equality in feminist practice.

My role in many of the moments of collaboration across this project was to take ownership and responsibility for the structure of production events, including editing a document based on live discussion and feedback, even if it were possible that other parties could also edit if they chose. Learning from my experience of the workshop document, I decided that I would digitally ‘share’ an editable copy of this consent form as a google drive document with each collaborator. Google Drive saves every edit each user makes to a document. This meant that the contributor and I would both have a record of each change that was made, when, and by whom. Although I anticipated, as with the shared document from the workshop, that it would

be most likely my responsibility to edit the text of this document, this would happen in front (either literally or in 'share screen' mode if meeting online) of the collaborator.

Workshop 3: Story Sharing with Men, a contradiction in terms?

Anne Oakley's (1981) paper *Interviewing Women: A contradiction in terms?* is an influential illumination of the 'masculine paradigm' of the social research interview, and its fundamental incompatibility with feminist inquiry into the subjective experiences of women. She notes that the 'methodology textbook' conception of 'the interview' is a one-way data extraction exercise conducted by the interviewer upon the interviewee. Any social interaction between the two is at best inconsequential to the research data, and any reciprocal questioning from the interviewee to interviewer should ideally be evaded. In opposition to the textbook objectification or datafication of the interviewee, she proposes "a different role, that could be termed 'no intimacy without reciprocity'" (Oakley, pg. 49)

SLEEC's courses for men have been running online since 2021 under the title *Dismantling Male Violence and Rape Culture: A Survivor-Led Course For Men*. SLEEC describe the course on their website as:

shaped to give men the tools and knowledge to understand, unlearn and actively challenge rape culture, male violence and misogyny, while also creating a space to unpack their own internalised patriarchy and the impact of sexism on themselves.

We want it to be a place where men can ask difficult questions that they may not have felt comfortable asking elsewhere, to those who have direct lived-experience of rape and sexual violence. This kind of deep connection breaks down barriers that block real understanding of complex experiences (SLEEC, n.d.).

Our workshop was attended by 8 'graduates' of the SLEEC course, and shared a similar format to the previous 'consult survivors' group, beginning with a short round of introductions from workshops leaders; SLEEC, myself and guest host Lewis Wedlock.

Lewis is an activist, academic and social psychologist who works as therapist and mentor to young Black and people of colour in Bristol, as well lecturing in schools and universities on self development, mental health, masculinities, patriarchy and misogyny. It had felt important to SLEEC and myself that there be a male workshop leader in the space. SLEEC had previously worked with Lewis and suggested he would be a particularly good fit for the project as he takes an intersectional approach to the discussion of masculinities, patriarchy and male violence, including the impact of race and class which is missing from much mainstream discussion.

As with the previous workshop, SLEEC wrote the questions, and Wedlock and SLEEC guided the discussion, whilst I focused on note taking. In reflecting on the successes and failures of 'consult survivor' workshop, which had happened the previous evening, SLEEC and I had collectively decided to remove the necessity for the attendees to interact with the live document. There had been a sense during the first workshop that the interactive document had not worked and was not useful, as attendees did not engage with it live and preferred to speak. Although the prior workshop's interactive quality had not felt like a success in the moment, it did in hindsight provide a visual accompaniment to thoughts raised in the lively workshop. This also created a material outcome that captured the dynamism of that workshop and provided a repository to which some attendees did in fact return to add thoughts. Reflectively, I wish I had provided a similar space for this workshop, as my on-paper notes do not capture a multiplicity of voices as clearly and, even more than the 'consult survivors' group, this group may have benefited from a space to return to privately, after the fact. The following responses are therefore lifted from my hand written notes.

Prompts shared with the group proposed questions like; 'What are the barriers that prevent us being able to support those around us that have caused harm?' and 'Can sharing experiences of those who have caused, perpetuated or witnessed harm help people identify with their own contributions of harm or upholding violence?'. This workshop was much quieter and attendees needed much more encouragement to voice their ideas. Discussion focused much more on reiterating a problem, than posing any solutions. The 'consult survivors' group, for example, had been able to easily discuss words such as 'consent' 'contract' and 'ethics' and articulate multiple definitions of the terms. They were also able to describe the impact of this language on their perception of a documentary maker's intentions, or a creative project's quality.

This group, on the other hand, took language from the prompts such as ‘What does accountability..look like’ and noted ‘accountability’s ‘non-specificity’ without being able to propose a definition or preferable alternative. They expressed many feelings of confusion and ‘not knowing’, and ‘not feeling good enough’ to know answers to questions. They also suggested that it is possible to present ‘faux’ knowledge, whilst not really understanding or believing one’s position, and the feeling that sometimes it’s ‘easier to not know’. Lewis described this confusion as the ‘patriarchal fog’ that prohibits open conversation between men about consent and assault. I had a sense in the workshop that the group’s general resistance to defining words or profering solutions was in part a response to a fear of being judged by SLEEC and myself. For example, one reading of a participant’s suggestion that accountability was “to be held accountable to the experience of survivors” could be read as men alone not feeling they are in a position to define accountability. That they, in essence, wanted to be told by SLEEC or other survivors, what accountability would be in a given situation. To an extent this position is understandable, as SLEEC are educators, and attendees previously engaged with them in that capacity. However both SLEEC and Lewis reiterate that perceiving rape and sexual assault as a ‘womens issue’ or ‘survivors issue’ in fact perpetuates violence against women, infantilises men as being unable to understand or take responsibility on their own, and also places an undue burdon on women and survivors to be the architects of their own equality.

Perhaps even more complexly however, “to be held accountable to the experience of survivors” is not only to say that men may not be capable of independently defining accountability, but also not capable of independently defining a rape or sexual assault. Beneath this statement is possibly the suggestion that it is the *subjective experience of the survivor as being raped or assaulted*, that *defines it as such*, and therefore that speech act is required in order to engage in accountability, or as another participant suggests “admitting to harm, beyond intention”. These comments propose the interesting but troubling inference that until an accusation of harm or violence has been made against someone, there is no grounds to intervene in predatory or abusive behaviour. The workshop concludes with questions about the purpose of story sharing, particularly ‘perpetrator’ stories. Wedlock proposes that “sharing is not absolution” but is part of a wider community practice which requires empathy and compassion

and an understanding towards 'perpetrators' as well as survivors, with an acknowledgment that "we don't all have the same resources" both in the monetary and social sense.

There is a prominent history of 'story sharing' as feminist praxis, and as the main tool of 'consciousness raising' in feminist movements. Collective story sharing sessions in which women openly discussed their personal life was a primary tool of the women's liberation movement. These sessions aimed to raise awareness to the common oppressions which shape 'the personal' in the lives of women as an oppressed group, and through this understanding, conceive of political solutions and community action (Sarachild, 1973). This is the period of second wave feminism from within which Oakley's research emerges. As Oakley terms it, the 'reciprocity' of a sharing, listening and identification with her research subjects was a far more effective way of gathering more richly detailed data about these women's lives than methods born out of 'masculinist fantasy' which champion individualism, objectivity and emotional detachment (Oakley, 1981).

On reflecting with SLEEC at the close of the workshops, I mention I am a little disappointed perhaps that the discussion with the men was not as rich as that with the survivors. Although they agree, they suggest that this is more likely an issue of the format. In their own workshops with men, which they run in a series over either a couple of days, weeks or more recently as a monthly drop in, the conversations do become more open and require less guidance from them as hosts. Over a more extended time, the group comes to trust one another and the hosts, and participants feel more able to share their experiences without the judgement or fear of 'not knowing', which was palpable in our workshop.

Lewis suggested in the workshop that "fundamentally the process of sharing is 'anti-masculinity'", and I reflect on this in combination with the Oakley text. Whilst it is no doubt illuminating and necessary to use feminist research methodologies to explore the subjective experience of men, particularly their experience of masculinity, patriarchy and misogyny, it should come as no a surprise that the result suffers an inherent friction. Although the tools of feminist praxis may well be the best place to deconstruct the 'fantasies' of masculine social vantage point - objectivity, detachment (Oakley, 1981) it is understandable that it might be

difficult to *describe the lived experience* of the heteronormative masculinist paradigm through such methods, particularly within just a 2 hour workshop.

It was apparent after this workshop that to speak openly or ‘story share’ narratives of sexual assault was a far more difficult task for the men than the survivors. Many of the survivors had already submitted texts to SLEEC’s blog, and therefore self identified as a survivor or victim, and wanted their writing and story out in the world. It was understandable that the men would have more complex relationships to the term ‘perpetrator’, and to publicly identifying as a figure proximal or a friend to a perpetrator. There would be further risk for these attendees if they contributed to the work more complex or uncomfortable narratives; of ‘not knowing’ or perhaps not believing an accusation of abuse made against a friend⁴³. Rather than requiring or requesting any of these attendees write something original for the work, a different approach to ‘story sharing’ had to be taken, which is detailed later in this exegesis.

Revision of Technical Proposal for *With These Hands*

Ahead of my first workshop with SLEEC I had made a visual storyboard in order to communicate the user journey of *WTH* with reference visuals. The influence of various periods of production activity, including the pre-production workshops, can be traced through the adaptations to this document. I updated this document regularly to reflect creative and conceptual development of the artwork, and frequently shared it with SLEEC and other contributors and collaborators for reference, ahead of any concrete material produced for the work.

Based on my knowledge of SLEEC’s work, and the kind of texts featured on SLEEC’s blog, the original visual storyboard I shared had included more than just the hand embodiment mechanic. Since the work’s original conception, I had further narrowed the technological and installation aspects of the work in line with the more advanced hand tracking capabilities of the new Oculus Quest 2 headset (Meta, 2022).

⁴³ Another uncritically repeated maxim of ‘consent culture’, along with ‘no means no’ is ‘believe all survivors’. This phrase intends to highlight that women and other survivors’ complaints of sexual harassment should be taken seriously, and permitted due process in a way which they historically have not either culturally or in the criminal justice system. This phrase however has often been misappropriated or interpreted as suggesting that all allegations of abuse should always be believed without due process. This reading of the phrase is then weaponised against the #metoo movement (Graves, 2020).

An installation around the work would facilitate a private viewing space. Although this was not described in any detail at this point in practice, it felt important that audiences would feel unobserved in a work featuring such sensitive material, inside and after the piece.

The internal space of this installation would include a table and chair, at which the audience would sit during the experience. The table would also be virtually represented in the headset, acting as the visual and physical anchor between the 'real' and the 'virtual' world. Touching this real world object with the virtual hands would increase the audience's experience of virtual embodiment (see Kilteni et al, 2012) and also act as a stage upon which the virtual assets appear in an otherwise void virtual environment around the user. This rather instinctual creative decision on my part had distinct practical benefits - it limits the amount of assets and animation required to the relatively small surface area of the table, saving not only asset fabrication budget but also headset processing power. It further served a conceptual purpose.

By utilising an almost theatrical spotlight like vignette of animation and activity, the work would counter the problematic conception of VR documentary as a 'simulation' of a contributor's experience, and resist providing a 'full picture' of events. The table would be a 'window' into their narrative, but not the kind the audience can go "through" completely to "the other side, in the world, inhabiting the world" (Milk, 2015).

At this point in the production I also had a relatively clear idea of the way in which the hand representations could be made. Although I am not a 3D artist, nor a coder, based on my understanding of how 3D assets are processed by the games engine Unity, I felt it would be possible to turn photogrammetry of a contributor's real hands into 'textures'. These textures could then be applied to the hand 'models' the Quest 2 already used in its existing hand tracking capabilities. Photogrammetry as a medium also has a quality that both references and undermines 'realness' as an objective. As explored in my description of *The Last Goodbye*, photogrammetry references the 'real' object it scans, but the experience of photogrammetrically produced objects is often a little uncanny. Particularly the quality of photogrammetry that I would be able to achieve on my small budget. These textures would be far less 'realistic' looking than the kinds of computer generated hand models and textures used

in a game like *The Climb* for example. There would undoubtedly be visible glitches and errors in the scans that would also work toward the ambition of undermining any idea of creating a 'simulation' of an experience, not an accurate or 'total' representation of a contributor, whilst simultaneously referencing the 'reality' of the 'real person', who has allowed me to document their hands.

The Quest 2' headsets's ability to accurately 'track' both the users' hands is provided by a number of front-facing cameras embedded within the headset. This technological development in the Quest 2 relieves the need for a user to hold controllers. Instead, the headset could be operated through a limited number of hand gestures, such as pinching or tapping of index finger and thumb. These cameras also, as a byproduct, facilitate 'passthrough mode', in which users can see their real environment and their own hands, overlaid with virtual content. This availability of the tech provided opportunities to create a moment in which audiences could be reminded of their own embodiment, by looking at their own hands, during the *WTH*. The intention was that in referencing or drawing attention to their own identity 'beneath' the skin of the contributor, I might be able to induce the kind of reflexive or self reflective experience I had after *The Climb*. In my experience of *The Climb*, hand based embodiment had allowed me to 'perceive freshly' my own first person perception in the real world, after the experience, suddenly 'queered'. My ambition was that this moment of passthrough would encourage users to consider themselves and their perspective a-new, and their own embodiment alongside their embodiment-as-other in the prior scenes. Particularly, I was interested in audiences seeing themselves from the same perspective as they saw these 'others', within the visual world and language of the work. I intended that this might encourage them to see themselves as 'alike' the contributors, but in ways other than typical 'empathy machine' content. Potentially that the audience and contributors are 'alike' in their choice to engage or participate in this documentary experience, albeit from different positions and at different times. A moment of passthrough might also challenge a voyeuristic experience of the work by drawing the users attention to their act of looking at or in this case 'inhabiting' another, by encouraging them to see themselves and their own embodied presence within the same context.

Although not completely novel to the Quest 2, the headsets inside out tracking (not needing external sensors or wires attached to the headset), hand tracking and passthrough capabilities

were a notable advancement for a headset at such a commercial price point. When I had first experienced hand tracking however, it was the novelty and responsiveness of the hand models that had inspired me, over any interactive capabilities. I was not interested in using a gesture based interaction mechanism proffered by the Quest 2 and had a strong feeling from my years as a VR host that it would add an unnecessary level of complexity to the user experience that would detract from their engagement in the work. Instead, all the interaction I had envisaged would be 'collider' based. A collider is a simple kind of interaction instruction in which the headset tracks the position of the 'object' of the hand, and interactive change occurs when this object 'collides' with another.

With this in mind, the 'user journey' text of the storyboard leaned into the tactile quality of the hand tracking experience. Accompanying text in the storyboard describes that users are encouraged to feel the desk and touch their own hands together, while seeing their hands in various 'skins'. First as generic 'representational' hands, then re-skinned 'as' the hands of the contributor. Finally, they see their own hands via headset passthrough which in the Quest 2, is limited to a grainy grey scale. There was at this stage certainly an understanding that users would feel 'embodied' within these virtual hands, however this tactility was equally informed by the use of self touch and tactile consideration of the body from the history of phenomenology. The idea being to encourage audiences to phenomenologically attend to this experience of embodiment, and consider its ethical implications *within* a VR documentary.

Beyond the physical touch of real world objects, the virtual interactive elements suggested in this early storyboard were quite vague. They are described as the ability to manipulate virtual objects, which might respond with different forms of real world physics. For example, moving one's hand through grass that parts in response, or glowing particles hanging above the table and around the user, which one might be able to brush around as if suspended in water. These mechanisms were influenced by a short scene in the BBC produced VR documentary *Is Anna OK?* (2017). In this scene the user is surrounded by shards of floating shattered glass, visually representing the voice overs description of time slowing down in the moments after an accident. By waving the controllers, which are represented by a pair of somewhat cartoon-like hands, one can gently redirect the trajectory of these glass shards, sending them slowly flying in another direction through a collider based interaction. This scene was particularly memorable

for me as a moment of interactive pleasure, in a piece otherwise typified by an uncomfortable style of game-like interaction in which I was required to 'do' things in order to move the narrative forward.

Interaction and Consent

As a VR host at events which sway toward a more arts and culture than game literate audience, interaction dependent artworks have often proved difficult to manage. There is an established language of game design which introduces 'interactive' objects -- particularly objects that *need* to be engaged with in order to move forward - such as having them glow or pulse, or having other non-playable characters gesture or even provide a verbal prompt toward them. If one has played games before, one understands to look for these cue's, particularly in moments where the game play has slowed, implying an action needs to be taken. However, these cues are not necessarily naturally understood by an art, cinema or theatre audience. In cinema, for example, a shot may linger on some mise-en-scene which might help the audience understand a subtext or plot point sooner than otherwise, and perhaps will linger longer depending on how integral to the subsequent viewing experience that knowledge might be. The film will not, however, completely halt until the connotation of that shot is understood by the viewer. The viewer is *allowed* to not completely understand the meaning of a shot, and the film nevertheless continues. However, one sometimes finds in an experience of a gamified VR narrative that the whole experience slows down to a halt if you have failed to fully understand. Moreover, this *understanding* is not a conceptual or empathetic one, but often is merely a device to move from one scene to another and seems based on the assumption that the VR audience wants or needs to constantly interact with objects in the world in order to be 'engaged' with the story.

I personally find these types of VR interactions uncomfortable, and in the context of a documentary, profoundly ethically challenging. I experience the work itself as expecting me *to do* something, and I feel a pressure to act because I want to continue the narrative. This pressure might be exacerbated by a pseudo social pressure if there are other characters in the scene with me. I feel the need to move 'us' forward as we stand in an awkward silence in the middle of a documentary experience, which may well be about a serious and emotional event that a character or voice over is relating to me. For example, *Is Anna Ok?* tells the story of a real pair of twins, one of whom experiences a brain injury following an accident. The VR narrative

recounts how this changes their relationship, and users choose which twin to 'follow', as the story is told through one or other of the twin's memories of the recovery process. Often there is only one action to perform e.g. pick up an object, and a few changes this could make to a narrative e.g. pick up one object, go to one scene, perhaps pick up a different object, go to a different scene. So in fact, there isn't a 'choice' to interact in a world at all, but one or perhaps two prescribed actions I am instructed to perform in order to move the narrative forward.

The word 'Interaction' means "mutual or reciprocal action or influence" (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). The related term 'agency' is the sensation that one might feel (or not) when able to interact - a feeling of freedom or "the satisfying power to take meaningful action and see the results of our decisions and choices" (Murray, 1997 p. 126). The prescriptive conception of forcible interaction is always an uncomfortable feeling to me, it doesn't feel 'meaningful', and certainly does not align with the promise of the word. I cannot 'influence' and I am not 'influenced' by the interaction, I am forced into this 'interaction'.

In some narratives, the actions themselves are also ethically uncomfortable. To continue with the example of *Is Anna OK?*, there is a moment in which the audience is required to 'interact' with objects in the twins bedroom, and on picking up the 'correct' object - a snow globe - the attending character describes how this object relates to a memory she has, and the story progresses into this memory. However, for me personally, it is not natural to stand in someone else's bedroom and pick up objects that do not belong to me. This action does not feel respectful, but I am forced to perform it in the VR in order to allow the attending twin to continue telling her story. When showing this experience to audiences, I would find other users also had trouble in this scene. I would often have to use my voice to prompt users I could see were idling in this scene to look around and find the snow globe and pick it up, despite their being both audio and visual cues inside the work to do so.

The early conception of the interaction in *With These Hands* was a response to this idea of prescribed interaction and of simulative representation. I had imagined that the virtual objects with which the audience engaged would be relatively abstract, and would 'inter-act' with the viewer i.e. visually respond to their choice to engage with it. Crucially this interaction would not be *required*. It would permit the audience to see their actions leave a trace in the world,

indicating they are not merely invisible voyeurs. However, it would not influence the pace or narrative of the contributors words, nor would it be so engaging or entertaining that it distracts or would encourage a 'turning away' from the contributors story.

As *WTH* develops conceptually, the visuals and the interaction within the work become two separate elements. The interaction in the work is further developed to more closely attend to the concept of consent, and consensual 'inter-action' between user and experience.

4.2 Production

Image 8. - 'On the App' Chris's 'Peeled' Skin Diffuse Map, August 2022

Peeling Skin

Before my first production meeting with Khora in March 2022, I had sent over a storyboard, which included how I envisaged the hand assets of contributors being made. I met with Khora CEO and Co-founder Simon Lajboschitz on zoom to discuss how much time Khora could give to the project, given the budget, and think through using photogrammetry of real hands to create textures for the Quest 2 hand tracking.

“I think that won’t work,” he said.

“Well, it could work, but it will take a lot of work - maybe too much work on our side - to rig the hand model that comes from the photogrammetry, so that you can actually use the hand and move the fingers and joints”.

He raises his own hand to the camera and wiggles his fingers to illustrate his point.

“and usually, unless you’re working with a professional studio, the photogrammetry you can do on your own is pretty rough and won’t make a nice model. You’d be better off looking through catalogues of existing pre-riggeds hand models online. CGI one’s that people have made, and finding a nice one that fit with the stories and just buying them. There’s lots of places online you can find them”

I am slightly perturbed by this suggestion, as to me, to make the virtual hands from the real hands of the contributors⁴⁴, is the work.

I also think he has slightly misunderstood me.

“Yes” I reply “I understand that making the models with the photogrammetry wouldn’t work but what about if we just made the textures with the photogrammetry, the skin of the hand and sort of wrapped it around the model already in use by the Quest? Could we not do that?”

I hold up my hand to the camera and gesture wrapping it, as if with an invisible roll of tape.

⁴⁴ If that’s what they have chosen. In the ending work, both Chris and Naroa chose to use their own hands.

He looks off into the air, thinking and smiling.

“I suppose we might be able to do that? I have never ever heard of that done before. I like the way you think because yes, if that works, that would be a very cheap option! It might look very weird though, if the texture doesn't fit. We will just have to try it out but yes, if you can make the textures - maybe we can use them like that. We will send you a template of what shape the textures will need to be like. Like a flat folded out version of a hand”.

He gestures around his own splayed hand, as if he's peeling his skin off.

The following chapter section is dedicated to the production of *With These Hands* artefact, and describes key creative decisions made during this process.

I have begun this chapter section with an account of my first discussions with Khora, the VR production studio I had chosen to work with. This research and development phase of production was facilitated by securing further academic funding to both develop *WTH* and attend a research residency at the Centre for Sexology and Sexuality Studies at Malmö University in Sweden, which is only a 30 minute train journey away from Khora's studio in Copenhagen⁴⁵.

Even in the earliest storyboards of the project, it was suggested that *WTH* would include 3 'stories' or first person narratives, and an 'intro' and 'outro'. In my experience, VR work longer than 20 minutes feels 'too' long even if very engaging and well made. In early deck's I proposed *WTH* would be 7-15 minutes duration. In the end, the work runs just over this at 17 minutes and indeed includes 3 contributions of original writing and performance from contributors.

In the following chapter section I will describe the production of each of these three narrative scenes and the 'voice over' scenes as four separate but related creative activities. Where appropriate I will also draw out from each subsection a technical aspect of production best illustrated in the work for this scene. I then conclude with a summary of the final assembly of assets with Khora.

⁴⁵ Please see appendix for more details on project funding streams.

The visual storyboards I made across the timeline of *WTH* production allowed me to quickly communicate to my collaborators how I envisaged the work to look and feel using evocative text and images. In storyboards made before participants agreed to have their name attached to the project, efforts were made to anonymise them and the stories only referenced in brief. I have included relevant pages from storyboards made across the production period in order to aid the reader.

Image 9. - 'On The App' Storyboard 1, March 2022

Image 10. - 'On The App' Storyboard 2, August 2022

Image 11. - 'On The App' Hand Scanning Process, August 2022

Image 12. - 'On The App' Final Scene, November 2022

Chris' Story: *'On The App'*

Because of the event that caused me to seek out SLEEC in my personal life, and an aspiration of the project to present a diversity of perspectives and attend to the most 'unheard' narratives, SLEEC and I thought it important the project include a male perspective story. However, in response to both the workshop with attendees of SLEEC's *'Dismantling Male Violence and Rape Culture: A Survivor-Led Course For Men'* and through discussion with SLEEC about the priorities of a survivor centred work, it was deemed beyond the scope of the safeguarding capacity of this production to speak with someone themselves accused of a sexual assault⁴⁶ or feature a story from that perspective⁴⁷. Rather, we were interested in the stories of those men *around* the accused, and exploring the experience of confusion that was palpable in the feedback from workshop attendees or the "patriarchal fog" as Lewis had described it.

There was no pre-existing narrative from this perspective on SLEEC's blog, and responding to the workshop, it felt inappropriate to request that any of the attendees write one. The workshop highlighted the feelings of confusion, and inability to speak or reflect clearly on these experiences, and the social risks of speaking in a way that might be interpreted as 'wrong' felt by attendees. Unlike the survivor group, who felt that anonymity was often forced upon them, and prohibited their speech or their ability to be seen and heard as an individual, it appeared that anonymity might support the male workshop attendees' in freeing their speech in a way that was perhaps not available to them in the workshop.

Spoken word artist and poet 1990s Chris was brought into the project to write and perform the piece that would present this 'proximal to perpetrator' perspective. Chris' work explores themes of masculinity and working class identity, including the ways misogyny and homophobia are enmeshed in the most harmful expressions of these. Chris speaks on these issues as an LGBTQ+ working class man himself, but his practice also incorporates contributor interviews, from which verite extracts are lifted. The themes of Chris' existing work, and his interview-led practice, made him a particularly appropriate collaborator. Chris and I had also spoken in a

⁴⁶ For legal and ethical reasons.

⁴⁷ For reasons of user and collaborator safeguarding.

personal capacity about the experience of being friends with someone accused of sexual harm, as this was something Chris had also experienced in his personal life.

With SLEEC's support in a fixer capacity, Chris released a call out through both SLEEC's and his own social media, seeking men who had experience of being close to someone accused of sexual assault, and who might want to discuss their experience with him in an informal interview. From the response, Chris chose 4 men to work with. Any verbatim extracts from these interviews that became part of the poem were anonymised through their inclusion in the singular fictional, but representative narrative Chris devised and therefore are completely anonymous in this research and the final experience⁴⁸.

The plot of Chris' piece '*On the App*' follows the broad trajectory of my own experience, and Chris', as well as all the men Chris spoke to. Written in first person, the poem follows the first person emotional response of a man who sees an accusation of harm made against his friend while scrolling through social media. The audience are privy to his train of thought and responses in real time. By virtue of the real-time theatrical conceit, it is implied that Chris is performing a character rather than speaking as himself, and this sets this piece aside from the others inside the work as a 'docu-fiction' or 'theatre verite' experience.

The piece opens with an astute description of the experience of using social media as a young man, and the cognitive dissonance between the tolerance of casual misogyny or sexually suspect behaviour in mainstream culture, and the felt gravity of an accusation of harm;

I open Instagram
See what Dan's up to
Bet he's bought a boat
Or a subaru
Or decided to move to Australia
Or slept with someone
That we all know from school

⁴⁸ The 4 people that Chris chose to interview were provided with the WTH information deck, however they were not known to me, and I had no contact with them. As such Chris interviewees were not subject to the same iterative consent protocol developed through the consult survivor workshop.

nobhead

I can't see anything

He's not posted for like a week

I get another message from Jack

Telling me 'just go on insta mate'

I say 'I can't see anything'

Sam's like 'just watch your stories'

And I do

They go from my mates doing karaoke on Spanish holiday

To an infographic about white supremacy

a meme about Leonardo Decaprio only dating women under 25

To someone's new cat

And there it is

A screenshot of someone's notes app

Black text on a white background

And it's about my mate Dan

In line with learning from workshop 3, the lead character has a sense of being watched and judged as saying and thinking the wrong thing, even in his own internal monologue.

It's that, surely

She's just decided

To call it that now

I dunno

That sounds

A bit

Yeah

When I say it like that

Like

it doesn't sound good

But I mean

It's not that I don't believe her

*More that I can't believe it about him
You know
He's a good lad
I would have noticed
Wouldn't I?*

The piece concludes even more concretely with the character reflecting on how he will be perceived in relation to the accusation.

*Then I think about
All the people
That must know
How you can't take something like that back
You can't get people to unknow that
How it must look that I'm meeting him here
That I'm the only one meeting him
In this pub that we always go to
I think about cancelling
But I already told him
That I was on my way
I can't deal with this right now
What am I supposed to do
Bet he thinks I already knew
Everyone must know
That I think it's fine
And that's why I'm meeting him
Nah
I can't have that
What would people think
I decide to text Dan
Start writing out the message
"Somethings come up - Sorry mate"*

*Before I press send
He says
Can you come to mine
I need someone to talk to
I swallow
look at my shaking hands
And press send anyway*

When I speak to Chris about the interviews, and how they influenced the work, he says the men he spoke to all actually felt differently about the accused in their experiences. Some believed the accusation, some did not, some stayed friends with the accused, some did not, but all the stories had this moment in common - the moment of 'finding out'. What I think Chris' piece does particularly well is illustrate that this moment of 'finding out' is attended with both reflections on perhaps ways this revelation is pre-cursered by other behaviour and yet also feels in complete contrast to how we might perceive this friend - *"slept with someone. That we all know from school. Nobhead"* - *"He's a good lad. I would have noticed. Wouldn't I?"*.

Another commonality Chris drew out from all four interviews was the way in which the interviewees couched their personal feelings on the accusation in relation to how that response might be perceived by others. "Masculinity is all about how you're seen by others, way more than anything internal. It's all about how you want others to see you" Chris says to me after he shares the piece with me for the first time.

Chris recorded his own sound in Bristol, and sent it directly to the sound designer to edit. When I asked Chris how he imagined his piece to look, he sent me an image he had taken on his phone of meeting a friend at a pub table. Although this did feel more literal or 're-creational' of the experience described, this did also feel like the most logical setting for the piece of work. This was also an exceptionally easy scene to DIY capture photogrammetrically, using just a pub table, a beer mat, a pint and a phone.

Experiments in Hand Photogrammetry and Texture Creation

An opportunity arose to work with CAMERA (Centre for the Analysis of Motion, Entertainment Research and Applications) studio, a research centre inside the University of Bath. I was aware the studio had photogrammetry capabilities, and were offering qualifying businesses 12 hours of free support⁴⁹. After some initial meetings, I was invited to the studio for a morning to learn more about photogrammetry, and we were joined by Chris in the afternoon to generate some assets. We experimented with two different kinds of photogrammetry. The first was a rig set up with multiple cameras that would take a number of images in unison - a more traditional photogrammetry approach. The second was an Artec scanner - a mobile, laser based device that is traditionally used to create detailed models of objects. Both methods were capable of producing a model and a corresponding texture.

The photogrammetry rig was set up primarily to capture a whole person, and heads and faces in particular. The CAMERA team were unsure of how accurately the rig could produce a hand model + texture, as a hand was a much smaller object, and a more intricate shape than the rig was set up to capture. We did not, due to time constraints, have the ability to construct a 'hand specific' rig. We assumed, however, that because the camera's were of relatively high quality, the texture created would be superior in this set up than the Artec scanner, which is not strictly designed to create quality textures at all and has a relatively low quality 'camera' element. We also deemed that because the camera rig would take pictures in unison, that the posing of the hand would be more accurate. The Artec required that Chris hold his hand as steady as possible upright from the table, while a CAMERA engineer walked around him operating the scanner. We knew that it would be very hard to keep the hand completely still across this 3-5 minute scan time, and this might result in model anomalies (See Image 11).

However, the results of the scan session were surprising. The photogrammetry rig produced a particularly 'noisy' model whilst the Artec produced a much smoother coherent model (See Image 11). Although we were not interested in utilising the model produced because, as Khora had previously stressed, to functionally rig a hand model of each contributor would be far outside the bounds of this project's timeline and budget. However, we *were* interested in generating a normal map, which would provide the illusion of more 3 dimensional detail to the

⁴⁹ As a partner on the Bristol + Bath Creative R&D network.

textures which could then be 'wrapped' around the more simplistic models already within the Quest 2's existing hand tracking. Due to this, it was actually the smoother model produced by the Artec that generated the better quality normal map and, despite the relatively low quality camera, produced a sufficient quality of texture image. Using the Artec generated texture did however result in some unintended effects in-headset.

As we had assumed, some of Chris' fingers had drifted position over the course of the scanning and this created a kind of doubling effect (See Image 8). When wearing the hands in an early in headset build provided by Khora, the lower resolution quality of the images didn't affect my reading them as hands, in fact the warping of the tattoos and what I could tell were errors in the scan actually added more of a 'realism' to the hands than unexpected. They did not look or feel like 'hyper-realistic' skin, as a CGI asset might. However the legibly 'photo-textural' quality of the skin, including the blurring effect on areas where Chris fingers had moved mid-scan, implied the material I was in contact with was photographically made, and therefore referenced the skin of a 'real' person.

Image 13. - 'Blueberry Muffin' Storyboard and Creative Assets, March - November 2022

The hands change again. Now you have Nina's* hands.

We are now in a dark space with thousands of dancing lights around us like fireflies, we can scoop them up in our palms and they vibrate and hang in the air wherever we push them.

She talks about how she does not want her rapist to go to prison.

PLACE YOUR HANDS BACK ON THE TABLE TO PAUSE

Image 14. - 'Blueberry Muffin' Final Scene, November 2022.

Narora's Story: *'Blueberry Muffins'*

When SLEEC and I decided that any survivor narratives should be taken from their existing 'disobedient Survivor Blog', one piece of writing stood out to me immediately. I included reference to it in an early storyboard (see Image 13) in the hope it might also become part of the final project. It also happened to be the first piece on the site which wasn't written by SLEEC themselves.

This piece, titled *'Blueberry Muffins'*, was written by Narora. It spoke directly to issues with media representations of survivors and perpetrators of sexual harm. It also presented a perspective on policing, prisons and personhood which, although evidently informed by abolitionist discourse, was largely a result of her own lived experience. As such it was a particularly relevant narrative for the aims of this project, and indeed represented a 'disobedient', 'unheard' and more complex survivor perspective. It was also well written, with humour and gravity.

I allowed myself to fully grieve when I realised that I do not want my rapist to go to prison.

When I tell people this, they often look at me like I'm naïve. This pisses me off for two reasons. Firstly, it is my rape we are talking about. Other people's opinions of my lived experience are frustrating to hear when it undermines my ability to reach my own conclusions. Secondly, most rapists aren't in jail anyway – the incarceration rates are so low that almost every rapist in society is out and about and was possibly behind you in the queue at Tesco today

-

My grief includes knowing that society dehumanises him and others rather than giving them the healing they need.

When I think of my rape, the most painful part was looking into his eyes and knowing that he didn't recognise me as a fellow human. Of course, the physical assault was awful, but the memory of his eyes looking into mine was what really broke my heart. His brain has been socialised to see me as a mere object; a means for his pleasure; a tool

for him to feel powerful. Putting him in an abusive oppressive institution for raping me will not teach him that rape is wrong.

It's been two years since I was raped. On the anniversary, I eat a blueberry muffin. Not for any particular reason – I just like blueberry muffins.

Sometimes I wonder if he likes them too.

Extracts from the original 'Blueberry Muffin' text Shared with Naroa's permission.
(*Disobedient Survivors Blog*, SLEEC.net, 2022).

After receiving my ethical approval for the *WTH* participant information deck and consent agreements from the University of the West of Scotland ethics board in July 2022, SLEEC agreed to connect me with Naroa. In early August they shared with her the following statement from me about the project.

Hi Naroa,

My name is Tessa Ratuszynska. I am a documentary maker and PhD student living in Glasgow but I am from Bristol.

*For the last 5 months I have been collaborating with SLEEC on the preparation of a Virtual Reality documentary I am making, 'With These Hands', about the difficulties in discussing sexual assault and the importance of listening to survivors. I understand that it is imperative that only survivors tell their stories, in their own words. This is why I am reaching out to the SLEEC blog contributors for existing writing from survivors to become part of *WTH*. Please read more about the project here [Link to the ethics board approved project information deck] and you can also see how the project might look with this storyboard [link to storyboard].*

Right now the stories, images and sounds included in the storyboard are stand in's. I am reaching out to you because I was really moved by your piece of writing featured on the SLEEC blog and wondered if you would be interested in collaborating on this project with

me. Myself and this project come from an abolitionist perspective, and a belief that if we are to move beyond prisons we need to be able talk more openly about life after a sexual assault for both the survivor and the person responsible. I think your writing does this beautifully and powerfully and I would love to feature an audio version of it in WTH.

The fee would be a minimum of £250 for your time and a £50 licensing fee for your writing. You will retain writing credit and you will be free to remove yourself and your contribution from the project at any time. We will have regular check in's to discuss how you want your words to be represented within WTH and you will have a chance to feedback at every stage of production. Please see the information deck for more details.

My project has quite a tight turnaround, and a deadline of November, where a version of the work will be screening at documentary festival IDFA in Amsterdam. If you would like to discuss the project in more detail please email me @ [my email] or we could zoom, text or have a phone call @ [my number] whatever works best for you. The deadline to agree to be part of the project or not would be late august.

Looking forward to hopefully hearing from you, Tessa

Hi Tessa,

*Wow I feel so honoured to have received your email. Thank you for getting in touch- having looked through your plans for the documentary it looks beautiful and powerful. I looked at the storyboard image for my section and laughed because I was just saying yesterday how fireflies are one of my favourite animals - it felt like too much of a coincidence!
I'd love to have a zoom call soon to discuss what comes next in more detail and I'll be permanently back in Glasgow late august/early September so I'll be able to travel easily to you.*

Love & solidarity,

Naroa

Narora's response came back the same day that SLEEC sent her my request, and the tone of her reply was indicative of Narora's enthusiasm and generous commitment to the project, as well as almost kismet connection between her and I. SLEEC are a Bristol based organisation however, much of SLEEC's work, especially since the pandemic, was based online. As such, submissions for the Disobedient Survivors' Blog came from across the UK and internationally. When I had suggested *Blueberry Muffin* as the writing and author I would most like to work with, SLEEC revealed to me that Narora was in fact Scottish and currently an undergraduate student studying in Glasgow. This meant that over the course of production, Narora and I were able to meet many times in person and this was incredibly beneficial in terms of building rapport. It also allowed me to share with her some influential VR experiences such as *Make Noise* and be present during both her voice over recording and photogrammetry sessions. In hindsight, it would have been incredibly difficult to work with another contributor who was not based in Glasgow⁵⁰.

Navigating Contributor Consent within Collaborative Production

In one of our early creative meetings, Narora and I meet in a cafe. The cafe has crayons and colouring books on each table for customers with small children. Spontaneously as we discuss the piece Narora suggests using the crayons, and we both draw the environment as we imagine it, as a way of making sure we are understanding each other⁵¹. I draw a table, with a scene on top of it, which I eventually turn into a photoshop image which is shared with photogrammetry and 3D artist Saturn Akin, and Khora (See Image 13).

Narora draws a much wider scene than the tabletop format of WTH will actually permit. Her drawing includes a foreground of a woodland scene, but with open fields in the distance. There is a river that runs through the forest, and she describes how the water changes the sound and the lighting, throwing shimmering reflections around across the ground. The space she outlines feels very deliberate in construction, and there's no hesitation as she draws. She mentions a therapeutic practice that involves imagining a place to visit, that can be mentally returned to in

⁵⁰ SLEEC did also connect me to another author from the blog. However, due to time constraints for the other author and Narora's enthusiasm for the project, I decided to focus on bringing Narora's writing into the project. The other author said they were happy to be contacted in future, if I were to make another larger version of the work.

⁵¹ We have already had a creative meeting prior to this in which Narora has described a woodland setting for her scene to me.

times of stress, flashback or anxiety. I don't know if this is Naroa's 'place', and she doesn't tell me that specifically. I ask her if it's ok if I take a picture of her as she draws.

In my first meeting with Naroa online, I shared with her the consent documents as well as the payment structure I have in place. I would pay her £50 to licence her writing, and £50 in cash or vouchers of her choice for every meeting we have to either create an asset e.g. recording voice over or the hand photogrammetry, and every check-in session we have about the piece. During every check-in we would go through the consent document. This document is a series of statements designed to be read aloud, that facilitate a conversation between Naroa and myself and allow us to assess if Naroa consents to the next stage of the production process, and feels she has enough information to do so.

This is a virtual, editable shared document and at points in time we leave answers blank or make addendums to the wording. For example, when we did not know exactly how we would conduct the photogrammetry of Naroa's hands, seeing as she was in Glasgow and CAMERA studio who worked on Chris' hands were in Bath, we left the statement "I agree to be 3D scanned and have had this process sufficiently explained to me" blank.

At another point, Naroa requests I change the statement;

'I agree that the researcher, Tessa Ratuszynska, can use images and sound clips from my contribution in publications, lectures & educational materials'

To include the caveat;

'With 1 week informed (24h minimum) of location, audience, context, time & date. With details of what excerpts/images/sounds would be used'

The consent document that could be edited, left blank, changed and returned to was deeply informed by the first workshop with the Consult Survivors group (of which Naroa is a member, but did not attend) and worked well in this project where we began the creative process with many unknowns. By the conclusion of the project Naroa and I had had 6 check-in's. Naroa

chose to receive her compensation in a combination of cash and in voucher's for a trauma informed massage practitioner in Glasgow.

To aid in creative sessions with Naroa, I create another interactive shared document that allows Naroa and I to repeatedly go through creative questions as prompts across the production process, in a similar way to the consent document. It allowed us to explore together how she imagined various assets in the piece, but also gave us some creative statements which we could reflect back on, and review assets against as they were made.

The document is split into 5 headings;

SHARING, LISTENING, SENSING, FEELING, CONCLUDING

SHARING was an extension of the consent based questions, and is where I asked if I could record the session either in audio, or with photos or just as notes, and if she was happy with me sharing those with the wider production team on a case by case basis. Sometimes she allowed me to send a copy of notes I made as we spoke to collaborating artists. Sometimes she allowed me to CC her into email discussions, for example with the 3D designer Saturn Akin, and she was able to give her feedback and thoughts directly to both of us.

LISTENING is the section in which we discussed translating the written text of *Blueberry Muffin* into audio. It was also the section in which we discussed how Naroa thought the work would sound - if she would want to voice the piece herself, or if she would prefer we used an actor. From the beginning, Naroa wanted to use her own voice and own hands, as the work felt so personal to her. I suggested that the 7+ minute timespan of the *Blueberry Muffin* spoken aloud would make the overall runtime of the VR experience a little long, based on my experience of watching and hosting VR. I also asked her to consider how she would choose to convey the same message if she were speaking it aloud and to consider a listening audience, rather than reading one. Ultimately I asked if she felt comfortable editing the work to be more 'listenable', with support from SLEEC as editors if she wanted. I also stressed however, that ultimately, if she felt she wanted the text to remain as it was, we would keep it that way. Naroa agreed and worked with SLEEC to edit the piece down. Ultimately, through edits to the writing, and then some further cuts made after sound recording, the piece was abridged to 5 minutes.

In SENSING, creative prompts encouraged Naroa to consider the environment of the work and the sensory experience of the user. This would inform 3D asset creation for the 'setting' of the work, but also would influence the sound design. From the outset neither Naroa or I envisaged the VR to be a simulation of any of the experiences Naroa describes in her piece, i.e. standing in line at Tesco. These questions were designed to encourage Naroa to consider where she felt she wanted audiences *to be* when they listened to her work, and that that's what we might be able to recreate inside the piece. These questions sought her thoughts on both the environment within the VR, and also the wider exhibition environment in which one would encounter the VR:

What kind of space is this story set? [Outside/Inside, Day/Night, Private/Public]

Dusk. About to get dark. Very private, completely alone. Sat down on grass or moss.

What kind of space is the best place to listen to this story in? Is it a different space?

It feels darker, but it should be displayed in a lighter setting.

The sound design was also envisaged to support listening, rather than simulation. It would not relate to events described in the writing, nor directly the woodland setting Naroa described for the piece.

The sound designer I chose to work with, Fossilised Frequencies, creates mostly modulated sound, based on Sufi understandings of sound vibration and wider listening practices (Savvy Contemporary, 2021). Their work mixes voices; sermons, interviews and academic readings within abstracted sound design, creating textural soundscapes which facilitate deep, attentive listening. As part of their practice, they had asked if Naroa could answer some more expansive questions about the senses; colours, smells and textures, that might inform the more abstract elements of the sound track. Naroa's answers to these questions also proved very useful in ascertaining the atmosphere of her VR scene as she envisaged it.

What can you taste? [Iron, sweetness, bitterness]⁵²

Something cinnamony. The taste of cold winter air, it smells and taste fresh. Like an anticapitalist world would taste with no shit everywhere. Like a memory of someone, its a bittersweet memory. Like in a movie before the final credits roll.

-

It's feeling less like cinnamon and now, it sounds more like victory, if victory was a taste.

In this extract from the document there are two reflections from Naroa, one from the first creative session, and one from a later session, after Naroa has just recorded her voice over. This shows not only the iterative process of our making, but also Naroa's narrowing of her vision over time.

What emerged from these sessions was Naroa's desire to create a sense of moving toward what she describes as 'freedom' by the close of the scene, from a carceral and claustrophobic environment - "Like a window needs to be opened" - to one that felt more open, fresher, cleaner and more natural - "Really fresh air - no pollution. Just that feeling of cracking quality air". In terms of more concrete 3D assets, Naroa described a mossy, woodland floor for her tabletop setting. This is relatively simple to create photogrammetrically. 3D designer Saturn visited some local Scottish woodland and sent us a collection of forest floor scenes, from which Naroa chose her preferred. Naroa also specifically asked if daisies could be part of the final scene.

Is there a change between the beginning and the end - do we start one place and end up another?

It gets slightly darker. And a patch of daisies whatever happens please. Dark wise big fat trees that feel very wise.

The most joyous moments - when babies are born, you kiss someone for the first time. All

⁵² Prompts are used here to illustrate just how abstract Naroa's response can be. It's clear from her reply that she has no problem thinking abstractly.

this energy goes into the ground and that's where daisies come from and I always try to stand in them. So I want a patch of daisies.

Unlike the forest floor, the daisy assets would have to be made as 3D objects. From early discussions with Khora, we had assessed that interaction with 3D objects individually - like the moving of fireflies in the original storyboard - would not be possible with the limited developer time supported by the budget. Similarly, we would not be able to animate photogrammetrically made assets to any great extent, unless they were laboriously 'rigged'. However, to be in a completely fixed, unanimated scene for the full 5 minutes of voice over felt opposed to Naroa's description of the freshness and vibrancy of being in nature, or the atmospheric transition of the scene. Naroa and I discussed that the transition between claustrophobia and fresh air could be generated through a change of tone of scene lighting: a relatively simple task from a developer perspective. We also decided that instead of the animated fireflies, and in line with Naroa's feelings about daisies, as her piece comes to a close a crop of daisies could 'grow' on the forest floor. This would also be a relatively easy coding task. By creating 3 or so variations of 'daisy' 3D objects, and then coding 2 or 3 'waves' of these daisy objects placed within the scene to scale transform⁵³ in unison, from non-visible to 'lifesize', we could generate a sense of 'growing', despite not animating the objects themselves.

FEELING prompted Naroa to describe how she wanted the audience to feel. Naroa responded to the question with more thoughts about cognitive and emotional feelings, rather than sensoral ones.

How did you want the audience to feel?

I would want an audience to feel curious. Challenged. To feel open and empathetic, regardless of what they think. And respectful.

What message would you most like people to take from hearing your story?

⁵³ A coding term denoting the coded resizing of an asset.

I want them to wonder if he does like blueberry muffins or not. Or what other normal human things he likes and dislikes.

In CONCLUDING I presented Naroa with a list of credits that someone in her position might have in a creative work; collaborating artist, contributing writer, experience designer. It gave us an opportunity to discuss crediting conventions in film and documentary making, and their ethical significance. In the credits to the final work Naroa requests 'Contributing Writer and Artist'. The section closes with the question:

"At what point would you like to have this conversation again?"

We found that the answer to this question was often quite natural - it would be upon receiving the results of a production activity. For example after a cut of the voice over was made, it would be sent to Naroa, and we would then meet to discuss it and review it in relation to the creative document, and then plan the next phase of activity.

Image 15.- 'Hands Around A Coffee Cup' Storyboard and Creative Assets, March - November 2022

The VO asks you to contemplate your position in this story.

It asks you to remember these stories when you next look at your hands.

VO encourages you to move the hands and touch the surface of the table, grounding you back into the real world.

WTH is around 7-15 minutes long, consisting of 4-5 scenes, including one which is just a view of the users hands through the video passthrough of the Quest.

SLEEC's Story: *'Hands Around A Coffee Cup'*

In early storyboards of *WTH*, a moment of camera passthrough had been incorporated into the outro of the experience to produce a self reflexive (and reflective) moment (see Image 15). In this scene, the audience would see their own hands in the same context as they had seen those of the authors of the previous 'stories'. This perception of their own hands, or a 'seeing the self seeing' would be accompanied by some text I would write around VR embodiment and the phenomenological queerness of the moment, and ask the audience to "contemplate your position in the story"; as audience, witness, voyeur or ally (See Image. 15). However, after the first workshop with SLEEC in which I had introduced the hand embodiment, and they had explained their own feelings about the proliferation of hand imagery in support services, this idea shifted substantially.

SLEEC already had a very reflective and critical piece of writing about hands, identity and survivor images in media that seemed a far more interesting accompaniment to this scene than as originally drafted in the storyboard. After I connected with Naroa, commissioned Chris and drafted a schedule of practical works ahead of IDFA, it also felt much more achievable that the third 'story' of *WTH* in fact be a text written by SLEEC themselves.

When I asked SLEEC how they felt about me using the text, they agreed but requested the opportunity to re-write. The original writing had previously existed as an instagram post caption, posted a few years earlier, and they felt it needed some adjustment to reflect their current position and to work as an independent text. Once they produced a version of the text they were happy with, we considered it in combination with the other two pieces of writing.

The piece was written in a collective first person, as 'we' and 'us', and also made reference to 'you' the reader or viewer.

What imagery do you think of when you hear the words rape victim?

- Pause -

How you might view victims and survivors of sexual violence (and how we see ourselves) is determined hugely by how we are represented in media. The images we see of us are disempowering, dehumanising and embarrassing.

We are reduced to shadows and silhouettes, faceless figures, often the only part of us shown is our hands.

Towards the end of the piece, this distinction between 'we' and 'you' becomes slightly antagonistic. The 'us' and the 'you' of the text are placed on opposite sides of a divide.

Why are you so afraid to show survivors and victims as real people?

- Pause -

Why are you so uncomfortable when survivors don't meet the victim narrative?

Why do you feel we don't deserve support unless we look like we need rescuing?

The stereotyping of survivors is a part of rape culture and you have a responsibility to question the way you view us, to challenge these toxic narratives when you see them.

Next time you see imagery related to rape and sexual violence or a representation of a survivor we invite you to explore why it has been chosen and what harm does it cause us.

The collective voice, and direct address of the writing, though powerful, felt incongruous with the other two narratives within the work. After some deliberation, I wanted to ask SLEEC their thoughts on changing the address of the piece, as well as challenging the antagonism of including an 'us' vs 'you' conclusion to the work. On the one hand, approaching SLEEC to make these changes felt justified, as to define the audience as apart from the collective survivor voice of the text, positioned the work solely as educating or speaking to non-survivors. This felt

like it was not in alignment with the aim of the work to centre a survivor *audience*, as well as survivor contributors. It also wasn't aligned with the very real issue, which SLEEC and I had frequently discussed, that even as a survivor, one does not sit outside of culture. One might also find oneself victim blaming or upholding rape culture in other ways *even as a victim*, survivor or indeed an educator and advocate.

However, to request a substantial re-write from SLEEC, on an interpersonal level, felt a difficult ask. SLEEC are writers, but not script writers or performers. Asking them to re-write the work from a collective to a singular first person perspective to be performed as such felt like asking them to work considerably outside their area of expertise and also perhaps 'too much' to ask of a contributor, especially as they had already presented a text which they felt represented their perspective and 'voice'. I decided to raise my thoughts with SLEEC, as well as my discomfort in doing so. They responded in a way that felt to me quite surprising, considering their dedication to survivor autonomy in written work. Meg said "it's really nice that you are so concerned about changing the text. But we also understand that this is your piece of work, not ours" referring to the wider work of *WTH*. As such, Meg said that she and Bryony had trust in my opinion as a maker, and would be OK with me passing the piece on to another writer to experiment with a singular first person narrative address, if I felt that would work better for the piece as a whole. So long as, they specified, that writer had lived experience that aligns with the project and with the writings themes e.g. lived experience of support services. I did indeed have a writer/ performer in mind who I considered appropriate and, with SLEEC's permission, that writer did rewrite and perform the text as an individual first person piece.

However, on sharing that script back with SLEEC for feedback, they said it did not particularly resonate with them. They were happy, if I was, for it to be included in *WTH* with a credit that reflected it's multi-author origins, but as a text itself, it would not be something they personally would publish on their blog. For them, it did not meet the criteria of feeling like an 'unheard' story or subject position. This was an interesting observation, as the 'beats' or points of the writing had remained the same between SLEEC's original and the singular first person rewrite, and there were even large sections of text that remained verbatim. However, I also agreed that something about what had felt so arresting about the original text was lost in this re-writing. In the end, it was perhaps the collective position of the text which was what made it feel like a

new, or 'unheard' narrative and one which was particularly 'disobedient' to the limited image of a survivor.

In the collectively voiced text, survivors were positioned not as individuals failed by support services and health care providers in a particular moment or instance, but as a portion of the population regularly failed by these institutions and government bodies more widely. The issue of stereotypical survivor representations in media and the perpetuation of a one dimensional image of a 'real' or 'worthy' survivor is elevated by the collective voice text to be a systemic problem, with systemic failures in care as a result, affecting a wide array of individuals in different ways rather than an individual in individual ways. It also repositions the 'survivor voice' from that of one disenfranchised and tokenised individual, to a varied, non-homogenous community capable of self organising and advocating. Through this experimentation with individual vs a collective address, it became clear that although it made the 3 'stories' of *WTH* less congruous, the original SLEEC text was the much more interesting form for this narrative to take and therefore became the final 'chapter' of the piece.

SLEEC did agree however, to change the closing of the text to incorporate the audience in a collective 'we' of culture, rather than a 'you' of non survivors.

Why don't we show survivors and victims as real people?

- Pause-

Why is it so uncomfortable when survivors don't meet the victim narrative?

- Pause -

Don't we deserve support unless we look like we need rescuing?

SLEEC did not wish to perform the text themselves, but did have strong feelings about what kinds of voices and vocal performances, like images, that they felt tired of hearing in survivor focused media. Voices which were overly soft, feminised or could be read as 'soothing' or

‘pitying’ felt over represented and limited in dimension in much the same way as images of “shadows and silhouettes, faceless figures...hands around a coffee cup”. After much deliberation on casting, SLEEC felt that they knew someone personally who, although not a performer, had the kind of voice they felt would work best for the piece, and also shared the regional accent of Meg and Bryony, which we all were interested in representing⁵⁴. This person being based in Bristol also allowed SLEEC to record this audio themselves, and therefore direct the performance as they saw fit.

3D Tabletop Asset Production

SLEEC understood that this scene would not have their ‘hands’ as other scenes. This was advantageous because Meg and Bryony had not been interested in being represented inside the work and did not want their hands included. It also made sense with the nature of the text as not sounding like a single individual that the audience should or could ‘embody’. However, it did feel necessary that this scene not be solely passthrough of the installation, but incorporate some ‘table-top’ elements, otherwise it might be at risk of seeming too ‘apart’ from the other two *WTH* narrative chapters.

I discussed with SLEEC what they thought could work as a table top asset, and we considered reproducing some real support service pamphlets to corroborate the ‘image’ of a survivor to which the original text responded. However we considered the potential legal issues with naming and reproducing pamphlets for particular services in the work. Moreover, this version of the text was being used to speak more broadly to the nature of survivor representation *in general*, in support services media but also wider representations in culture, film and documentary. Ultimately this piece of writing was being used to encourage the audience to reflectively question the choice to represent survivors with only their hands *within this work of VR documentary itself*. As such it was decided to more generally re-create a stereotypical ‘image’ of a survivor as a photogrammetrically produced asset. Saturn was provided some images taken from support service pamphlets, and given remit to 3 dimensionally re-create the image of ‘hands clasped around a coffee cup’, which is also referenced directly in the text.

⁵⁴ We had all, from early on, stated that where possible the work should include only regional accents in an effort to speak to the classed quality of the prototypical ‘deserving’ survivor or victim as a white, cis female from a middle class background.

This assets inclusion within the scene had some surprising and unintended effects in VR which worked to the scenes advantage. The asset Saturn made featured a glitchy representation of some 'feminine' hands around a coffee cup. Deliberately, Saturn had not included a face to this figure, and they appear to fade into darkness as if lit by a tight spotlight. The effect of viewing this asset in the headset however, placed on the table opposite the user, created the sensation of being seated *with* someone at the table. Although the combination of text and image makes it apparent this is a recreation of the kind of generalised anonymous representation of a survivor which SLEEC are interested in challenging, the asset does also induce a sense of co-presence and a feeling of 'being -with' a collective, represented by this singular voice and figure. I will return to this effect in my concluding reflections.

Image 16. - 'Place Your Hands in Mine' Storyboard and Final Scene, March - November 2022

You look down at your hands on the table, which are abstract line drawings.

VO encourages you to move the hands and touch the surface of the table, grounding you to the space and slowly introducing you to the experience.

As you look at these hands they slowly morph into much more realistic hands, but ones you do not recognise....

The Voice Over: *'Place Your Hands in Mine'*

From my earliest conversations with Khora I understood that the assets of the project could not be interactive in the way the early storyboard imagined. These assets, which had since been narrowed to Naroa's woodland with daisies, Chris' pub table and phone, and SLEECs 'other hands', were part of the fixed scene that would appear on the table top, and there was not the time or budget to facilitate they respond to hand-tracked hands of the user in any way.

Early designs had incorporated, however, a more analogue form of 'interactive' asset - the users own hands, and the table itself. The table - an easily sourceable Ikea one-man dining/writing table - would exist in both the real installation and be represented inside the headset as a 'line drawing'. This line drawn table would continue to be visible throughout the experience, with other scenes fading in and out on top of it. Each scene - essentially made up of one photogrammetrically produced asset from Saturn, would remain semi translucent, so that the white outlines of the table would remain visible underneath. In early storyboards of the project, the introduction scene to WTH was as follows:

You look down at your hands on the table, which are abstract line drawings.

VO encourages you to move the hands and touch the surface of the table, grounding you to the space and slowly introducing you to the experience.

As you look at these hands they slowly morph into much more realistic hands, but ones you do not recognise....

This kind of interaction - a sensory engagement with the table - would still be possible within the limited budget and time I had with Khora. In fact, it didn't require any additional work from them, save the construction of the line drawing table asset to the dimensions listed on the ikea website. It was not within the project scope for the headset to 'recognise' the real table and align this with the virtual one automatically, so the table and the headset would have to be aligned manually in set up. This is a fiddly, but not impossible task for a VR host.

When I began to consider this scene as an introduction to the themes of the work, and as laying the groundwork for a more phenomenological sensory engagement with the hands and the table, a new avenue for the interactivity in the work emerged.

Onboarding and Offboarding in VR Design

'Onboarding' and 'offboarding' is a much speculated area of VR research, particularly in the creative industries, yet one without concrete definitions of best practice. Some reduce this process to a VR host taking "steps to avoid friction at the beginning and end of the experience" (Bennett et al, 2021) for a user, however others have acknowledged that a body of research in onboarding and offboarding audiences in immersive theatre experiences shares considerable overlap with XR, and therefore it is not only VR's technology that requires the lubrication of onboarding and offboarding, but also its 'immersive' qualities and this is a process the work itself can take up (Whittaker, 2023). Audiences must "become attendant" a process in which a "reciprocal, sensual relationship [is] established between self, space and other bodies in the space" (Machon, 2013, p. 55). In her framework for onboarding and offboarding in VR, audience anthropologist Laryssa Whittaker (2023) further describes this effect;

"The self must relate to two spaces: on one hand, the physical environment in which one's body is situated; on the other, in a virtual world in which the self is enveloped, which has its own aesthetics and rules" (Whittaker, 2023).

From my own experience of hosting VR, I have a first hand understanding of the necessity of onboarding and offboarding. A well hosted VR experience can indeed reduce the 'friction' of the technology of the headset itself; showing how it's fitted, how to adjust it for comfort, and how to use the controls. Beyond this however, the VR host 'watches over' an audience member during a VR experience - in both a practical, and perhaps a more emotional sense. They are the first person seen when leaving a VR experience, and therefore the first opportunity to express feedback, feelings or even perhaps seek comfort. Alternatively, in some instances it is more appropriate for the host to avoid interaction, save the necessary, with audiences, and the role requires the social tact to understand when this is the case (see Josh Constine's (2015) article describing exiting Rose Troche's *Perspective; Chapter 1: The Party* (2015), in which participants are placed 'behind the eyes' of young, male rapist).

Something I am also acutely aware of from my roles as venue manager at VR festivals, is that the hosts responsible for onboarding and offboarding audiences at some of the most important film festivals in the world, and therefore for some of the most serious VR documentary content that has been made in the past 10 years, are usually volunteers. Many times, volunteers working in the 'immersive' portion of a wider festival might have never tried VR themselves. With this in mind, I wanted to ensure that the installation and the in-headset experience of *WTH* itself, do as much of the emotional heavy lifting of onboarding and offboarding as possible. Ensuring that the sole responsibility of centering survivors in the introduction to the work, and giving them recourse to express themselves afterwards if that's what they might need, was not left to a volunteer.

The introduction and 'outro' of *WTH* might be described as the onboarding and offboarding of the experience, and the space in which audiences 'become attendant' to the experiences 'aesthetics and rules', and content.

Trigger Warnings VS Becoming Attendant

At frequent intervals I would go over the *WTH* storyboard with SLEEC, and discuss existing assets, writing and sound for feedback. This role was aside from their creative work on the project, and was to facilitate the project's regular attunement to the 'survivor centred design' approach. SLEEC, speaking with lived-experience expertise, would flag any assets or qualities of the work that they felt were not meeting the necessary requirement of 'survivor centred design' which places the rights, wishes, needs, safety, dignity and well-being of the victim/survivor at the centre of all design and content decisions (*IASC Definition & Principles of a Victim/Survivor Centred Approach*, 2023). From the beginning, it was apparent that the introduction and 'outro' of the work would have to serve a number of functions, not least ensuring that a prospective survivor audience was appropriately supported and accounted for in the work. I had discussed with SLEEC what they felt it important that this voice over include, and I specifically asked them about the requirement for 'Trigger warnings'.

Trigger warnings, like (and related to) increased discussions of consent, have become a much debated issue 'on the ground' in schools and universities, but also in pedagogy research

(Appleman, 2022; Carter, 2015). Trigger warnings are also becoming more commonplace in arts, theatre and exhibition venues (Akbar, 2024), in line with a broader approach to and definition of access and inclusion (Moon, 2024. See also Carter, 2015). As a 2023 meta-analysis defines and summarises:

Trigger warnings, content warnings, or content notes are alerts about upcoming content that may contain themes related to past negative experiences. Advocates claim that warnings help people to emotionally prepare for or completely avoid distressing material. Critics argue that warnings both contribute to a culture of avoidance at odds with evidence based treatment practices and instil fear about upcoming content. (Bridgland et al, 2023, p. 751)

Perhaps missing from this summary of trigger warning critics would be those that suggest trigger warnings are “whitewashing”s of culture from “snowflake campaigners” (Hoffman & Cole, 2024) which make audiences “too soft” (O'Hagan, 2024). Interestingly, this same meta-analysis concluded there was in fact no evidence that trigger warnings *do* encourage avoidance of material, but notes that although proponents of trigger warnings argue that they “allow those who are more sensitive to these subjects to prepare themselves..and better manage their reactions” (Kate Manne, 2015), in most instances “trigger warnings do not typically describe how to prepare oneself to manage reactions and instead usually describe potential negative emotional reactions that will likely occur when viewing the material (e.g. distress, anxiety)” (Bridgland et al, 2023, p. 754). The analysis concludes in fact that the research appreciable result of trigger warnings is to reliably increase ‘anticipatory affect’, a negative apprehension about oncoming content, and therefore “should not be used as a mental health tool” (Bridgland et al, p. 769).

Although trigger warnings relate to a wide array of media and subjects, they first emerged as a concept in feminist internet forums specifically relating to sexual trauma and their growing use is paralleled by increased awareness, understanding and gravity attached to sexual assault and misconduct within the ‘national conversation’ (Vingiano, 2014). As such it would not be unusual to discuss the potential inclusion of trigger warnings in a project with the content *WTH*, with or without a survivor centred approach or the consultation of SLEEC. However in this particular project, the meeting of SLEEC and I’s informed perspectives of the issue of ‘content’ or ‘trigger’

warning in relation to an interactive medium such as VR, and the process of scripting the onboarding and offboarding, resulted in a profound shift in the projects approach to interactivity, and reoriented me once again to the concept of consent.

When Meg and I meet on zoom to discuss the intro and outro scripting, I use the phrase 'trigger warnings' to describe the language and information the introduction might include that would insure a prospective audience, who may or may not be a survivor, are able make an informed decision about engaging with the work. I ask her to describe how SLEEC might introduce a group attending a workshop, or the ways SLEEC might set up a virtual or in person workshop as a 'safe space' in which accounts around sexual assault might be discussed.

"Well firstly, we don't ever really use the word 'trigger'" Meg suggests. She goes on to explain that a traumatic 'trigger' can be something very personal, it could be something very specific; a smell, a taste, a texture, an object and it may indeed be something the person themselves is not aware of until they come into contact with it. As such it is not possible to either warn a group of all the potential triggers that might be encountered in the following space or content because it's simply impossible to know the triggers of others. Similarly, it is not possible to suggest a text or piece of media has no 'triggering' content or therefore that a space is completely 'safe'. This is something, Meg says, that is beyond SLEEC's control when they run an event. What they do feel is part of their role is to encourage an attitude of self reflection in attendees, to respect their own feelings when content becomes 'triggering', and to take whatever steps they feel are necessary in that circumstance, including leaving. In other words, 'become attendant'. Meg outlines:

Mostly what that looks like in our spaces is we try and describe what the session might look like, when we will take breaks, when people can ask questions, and also let the group know they are free to leave whenever they feel like. They don't need to feel like they have to stay in a meeting or conversation that's not working for them. They can feel free to go and take a minute and come back, or leave all together that's fine. We can't say to people we know exactly what they need to do to not feel triggered or to manage a trigger, because we don't, but we also want to empower people with the knowledge that *they* probably know what's best for them...we also understand that

some people don't always know what they need and that's ok as well, but the first step is to pay attention to yourself and your feelings. (Meggan Baker, Personal Communication, October 2022)

Consent as Interaction

Based on this conversation, we conclude there are some essentials that the onboarding section must cover, including a basic description of the experience; how long it will be, how many stories or voices they will hear, and a broad summary of the content.

We also deem it important to state “there won't be any explicit or detailed descriptions of sexual violence”, as none of the stories involve describing the event of an assault. Due to the prevalence of VR being used to ‘simulate’ the experiences of others, and put audience ‘in the shoes’ of contributors, the idea that the work might include descriptions or even recreations of an assault experience might not only be a common assumption of the work, but a distinctly frightening prospect for many audience members, particularly survivors. Due to the embodied nature of the work, the fear that a simulation of someone's assault experience might not only be represented visually, but that the audience might be themselves cast or embodied as either the victim, or in this work, as *the perpetrator*⁵⁵ was a prospect that we wanted the introduction to dispel as quickly as possible. In doing so, negating as much as possible negative apprehension of the work, without attempting to present the content as ‘not triggering’, which we could not know or suggest.

Another task of the introduction was to ensure that audiences felt empowered to leave the experience whenever they wanted, and knew how to do so. It is a misconception that all audiences would be comfortable simply removing a VR headset at will or that this is an ethically uncomplicated solution to an audience consenting to engage with content. As suggested by Kate Nash (2018), there is an ethical complication in a piece of work that encourages an audience to turn away from a contributor's representation during testimony, and to be required to do this as a manner of exiting triggering content is similarly ethically complex. Additionally,

⁵⁵ Press materials for the project referenced the male perspective within the work and discussed representation of perpetrators. This could cause some prospective audience members to believe that they will be at one point embodied ‘as’ a perpetrator.

just as with SLEEC's zoom meetings, although it might be relatively easy to 'leave' a zoom in a technical sense, there is a certain social convention that might stop someone doing so unless expressly invited to or informed it's 'allowed'. The additional complexity of the headset, which is such an inaccessible object it is often required to be fitted by a host during onboarding, implies it as a technology not easily removed. As such it was the task of the introduction to inform the audience that they *are* able and capable to remove the headset whenever they want. Beyond this however the attendance to sensation, particularly indications that one might need to leave or take a break from content, could be combined with or rather *are not separate from* the attendance to embodied sensation within the VR itself. In other words, allowing the audience to know *how* to leave is potentially more important than trying to forewarn them about *what might make them want to leave* and to have control over one's engagement with the content could become an interactive mechanic itself, one that could further elaborate on the works themes of consent.

Consent, in both documentary and sexual contexts as previously discussed, is sometimes positioned as the event of either asking for, or 'giving' a yes or no response to a request. Contemporary consent discourse has elevated the consent standard to 'ongoing and enthusiastic' consent. In other words, not simply not a 'no', but through either verbal or physical indications, an 'enthusiastic' yes response prior to the initiation of contact, which is reiterated at numerous points in time, particularly perhaps at points of escalating contact⁵⁶.

In previous conceptions of the ethical triad between Documentary Maker, Contributor and Audience, to acquire the consent of the contributor is deemed if not an ethical responsibility of the documentary maker, at the very least a legal formality (Ruby, 2005). This requirement however, is not extended to the documentary audience. The documentary maker has journalistic or ethical integrity responsibilities towards the audience; documentary content must aspire to be 'truthful' in ethical documentary making. However, the documentary maker is not

⁵⁶ Despite the ongoing and enthusiastic consent frameworks being introduced in the first instance to protect against perpetrators being able to claim misunderstanding or confusion in defence against a rape accusation, this framework does introduce it's own 'confusions'. Not least by introducing the idea that some sexual contact is 'more' sexual contact than others, requiring its own consent, and the therefore implied compartmentalisation of sex into a series of separate 'acts'. The idea of sex as a series of 'escalating acts' is a concept laden with ableist, heterosexual and cultural bias about what is 'real' sex or 'more extreme' sex. More recently attention has also been paid to dissolving a separation between sexual and other forms of contact, and expanding acts that require the 'ongoing and enthusiastic' consent framework to include platonic touch and forms of verbal contact (Rosman, 2018).

required to consider the consent of the audience to view the work. It is deemed self-evident that an audience can simply choose to view the work or not, and is at liberty to turn or walk away from the content at any time in its screening. The established triad of ethical responsibility between documentary maker, contributor and audience is complicated in a multitude of ways by VR works (Rose, 2020), not least because this ability to ‘turn away’ is profoundly ethically complicated by the 360 environment. In line with my discussion with SLEEC about the ability to leave the work at will as they facilitate in their zooms, and the natural interactivity of the users hands with the table, a concept emerged for consent based interaction.

The work was originally intended to encourage audiences to ‘feel’ the hands of the contributors they embodied, inspired by my own experiences inside ‘The Climb’ game, and also as a meta critique of the ‘empathy machine’ rhetoric. In the early storyboards, there was an idea of the physical table as ‘grounding’ the work, by providing the audience an anchor or linking object between real and virtual worlds. This concept was easily adapted toward becoming a more literal ‘ground’, ‘anchor’ or passageway object between the real and the virtual experience, becoming *WTH* answer to an ‘exit’, rest space or consent to continue listening.

A ‘collider’ in Unity is “component that defines the shape of a GameObject for the purposes of physical collisions” (*Introduction to Collision*, n.d.) or a more layman definition might be that in Unity, although two objects may appear visually, without other instruction, two objects can easily inhabit the same virtual space or pass through one another without ‘collision’. For example, in *WTH*, my hand, ‘as’ Naroas hand, can easily brush through the woodland scene and I can hover my hand ‘through’ a daisy. There is no physical or visual feedback resulting from this - no inter-action. By introducing a ‘collider’ to an object, one provides the instruction that *something should happen*. If we were to use the collider to recreate real world physics, in which two solid objects cannot inhabit the same physical space at the same time, Naroa’s daisy would have to move or bend to accommodate the introduction of my hand⁵⁷. A collider can also be used to provide other kinds of instruction. In the case of *WTH*, there was no need to replicate real world physics, as the material table aligned with the virtual table provides this table a touchable surface. A collider could however, be used to turn the real world physical touch of the table into a Unity instruction, one which could pause the experience, thus

⁵⁷ This is an over simplification for the purposes of example, as the act of ‘bending’ in relation to collider instruction, or deciding what kind of objects bend to others is a much more elaborate coding process.

providing the audience the ability to take breaks from the work at will. Conversely, this would make all other engagement with the work 'consensual' or chosen, as opposed to merely a consequence of being in the work.

More extensive 'collision' with the table, e.g. holding one's hands down on the table for a more extended time, could be used to cause a change of scene. In the case of *WTH*, if one places both hands on the table or 'in' the collision zone briefly, the experience pauses. If they hold this position for 10 seconds, the experience would restart, returning the headset to the 'neutral' opening scene which has no voice over. This was deemed a more 'ethical' scene from which to remove the headset, in the sense that it would not require the audience to pull the headset off whilst a contributor is speaking.

The Voice Over

As indicated in the early storyboard, the script for the intro and outro scenes should "encourage you to move the hands and touch the surface of the table, grounding you to the space and slowly introducing you to the experience" and at the close "asks you to contemplate your position in this story" (See Image 16).

In line with the conceptual development of the project as a whole, including the table -pause - consent mechanism, the role of this scene was expanded to do the following;

- Introduce the work; including its survivor centred approach and the nature of the content - it's duration and description.
- Bring the audience to 'attend' to both the phenomenological act of self touch and also their own relation or response to the work, including if they might need to leave.
- Introduce the interactive conceit of the work; that one can pause or leave the experience anytime.

In order to write this script I employed some dramaturgy support from Chiron Stamp, a live artist and activist whose work explores themes of gender, transness, the body and power, particularly in relation to mental healthcare services. Our work together was iterative, with me writing and presenting scripts to them for feedback.

The first draft of this voice over took the form of more or less explicit instruction;

This is a collection of stories told by artists that discuss sexual assault, shame, recovery and hope. But not necessarily in that order.

This is a space for them to speak, and for you to listen, it is not a simulation.

The experience lasts 15 minutes, but you are in control of how long you spend here.

Look at your hands on the table in front of you. Feel the table beneath your fingers. This is how you control the experience. When you lift up these hands from the table, the experience will begin.

If you place your hands back down on the table, the experience will pause.

If you want to leave the experience at any time, remove the headset.

(pause)

If you are ready to listen, lift up your hands and look at them.

This introduction attempted to introduce the survivor centred approach by limiting the audience's perception of their agency. They are *just* a listener, to the survivor voices who *must* be heard as an instruction. This demand of the audience is reiterated by stressing that the work 'is not a simulation', meaning, the audience will not get to do whatever they like in the experience, or that this is not an experience of self expansion as-other. I also attempted to preempt some of the more limiting conceptions of survivor narratives, in particular the idea of 'linear healing' and that the stories included would reflect this growth arc from shame to hope with the line "not necessarily in that order".

However, Chiron, taking into consideration the orientation of the project toward consent and consensual relations between maker, contributor and audience, pushed me to reconsider the use of direct instructions. Instructions are essentially, Chiron reminds me, non-consensual. Instructions do not encourage a contemplation of one's own desires or attention to one's own limits in relation to a range of possibilities. Rather, they lay out a limited number of actions possible and foreclose on the kind of 'attunement' that the consent interaction is supposedly dependent on. We also discussed the 'voice' of the instructions in relation to consent and power. To rely on a disembodied voice to present instructions appears antithetical in an experience which critiques institutions, such as support services, the police and prisons, for their power-over *modus operandi*. It similarly appears anomalous in a work that aims to, at a production level, redistribute power more equitably between documentary maker, contributor and audience. Despite the work proposing to present less limited representations of survivors, the seriousness and dourness of the instructional tone does little to work against one's expectations in these opening moments. In this introduction, the work states itself as 'not a simulation'. However the word 'simulation' connotes a high-tech vision of what VR is, and reasserts its inscrutability to an audience, who also may well not be aware of this word as a critique of VR. Additionally, if this is not a simulation, then who is this voice that is speaking to me? What does a disembodied instructional voice denote more than that this *is* in fact an illusionary space with therefore less consequences and less ethical responsibility on the part of the audience to the Others represented therein.

On a practical level, the instructions in this intro are also a little vague and rely on the audience holding their hands down on the table whilst listening to the full introduction. This cannot be relied upon, especially as they familiarise themselves with new aesthetic rules of the environment. What would happen if the audience lift their hands too early? Would the introduction be cut short? This introduction had to facilitate learning about the 'aesthetics and rules' of this virtual environment, including the look and feel of hand embodiment, and the interactive quality of the table. In this version of the instruction, the first time they will ever try to pause using the table is, in theory, once they are already feeling the need to pause. For it to then not to work at that moment is a failure of not only the mechanic, but the mechanics safeguarding ability. If they choose to pause a story to merely explore the mechanic, this presents the mechanic as a 'turning away' from content to purely explore interactivity, and

against the ethos of the project. Allowing opportunity to practise the pausing, in a form that would be less high stakes and lighter emotionally for the audience, would be imperative to limit the negative anticipatory effect the interaction itself is designed to alleviate, and to be in line with the ethical ambition of the project.

Through further iterative development, the final version of introduction built on the first, but addressed these invaluable critiques and feedback from Chiron. Once inside the headset, the audience sees the table in front of them. On top of the table are the outlines of a pair of hands. The users own hands are represented as semi translucent hand models, something that feels very unremarkable in VR, almost neutral, or 'invisible'⁵⁸. Above the two outlines of hands on the table a text based instruction reads;

PLACE YOUR HANDS IN MINE TO BEGIN

Once the audience has acclimatised enough to the environment to notice and comprehend this instruction, they move their 'invisible' hands into or on top of the outline of the hands on the table. On the 'collision' of their hands with the surface of the table (both real and virtual), the audio track of the space shifts and the 'invisible' hands are transformed into 'line drawings' of hands.

A voice over begins:

It's a little bit like we're touching isn't it?

These are my hands, but you have hold of them.

Except this is not you holding my hands, but more like, having my hands.

Borrowing them for a time.

Take a good look at them. Feel them from the inside.

⁵⁸ Invisibility is often indicated in cinema, not as the absence of body or body parts, but as similarly semi translucent.

These aren't my real hands of course. They are just the hands the headset automatically gives you. Not like human hands at all. The symbol of hand really.. a gesture toward a hand.

If you rub your fingers together, or bring your palms to touch you can still feel with these hands, but you're feeling yourself, not me. Here in this VR, you can only touch yourself. Hold yourself.

Before the experience even introduces the idea of documentary contributors, or embodying their hands, it begins to undermine or challenge the concept of knowing (through the metaphor of 'touching') as the de facto result of embodiment-as-other in VR. Simultaneously, it draws attention to the phenomenological experience of embodiment through self touch.

I was drafting the script and casting the role of the Voice Over at the same time. This allowed me to, when thinking about how to undermine the authority of the 'Voice Over' as a 'voice from nowhere' or 'no one', lean into the creative presentation of the work as in-construction. By bringing attention to the casting of a real person to portray this voice, I was able to draw attention to the means of VR production reflexively, in order to engage the critical attention of the audience. Based on SLEEC's critique of the survivor media voice as soft and feminised, I had put out an open call for voice performers whose voices were more 'masculine', although the call did not stipulate the gender of the performer. Of all those who applied, Len Goatzee's voice stood out the most.

Len is a transmasculine performance artist who's practice involves exploring 'the queer' in ways similar to queer phenomenology, as revealing the 'disorder' beneath 'order', and as non-alignment. He had at that time been making work that specifically explored the queer through speaking and singing; "they inhabit this topsy-turvy with their voice in all its transitioning variety. Their trans voice becomes a carrier; a vector sharing a story within a story and worlds within worlds" (Royal Scottish Academy, 2022). Len's voice was particularly interesting because it had an ageless quality, as both the voice of someone in their 40's, but also a voice that was newly being formed. Their voice felt in some ways comforting, perhaps parental, but also very youthful and playful. Len's voice sounds fun, because Len is fun, but also

because Len is heard to be having fun with his voice. The casting of Len allowed me to borrow of Len and his practice to 'personify' the voice over;

This is my real voice though. In real life I'm a singer, but right now, I'm a Voice Over Performer.

Hearing my voice is a kind of touching, as my voice vibrates your eardrums.

But holding a voice...holding a person whilst they speak is different. Holding requires listening.

Listening with a quiet within yourself, without distraction, and without trying to fix or to sooth.

In this experience, you will hear 3 other real voices.

These voices will discuss sexual assault, shame, recovery and hope. But not necessarily in that order.

There won't be any explicit or detailed descriptions of sexual violence.

These are real people's words. They will speak about their own experiences, feelings and perspectives. What they speak about and the words they use may be uncomfortable to listen to or even hard to understand.

In real life, It is hard to hold onto someone's hands and listen. In real life, you may have to take a pause, take a moment, take a breath to continue.

Listening is a choice.

Sometimes you will not be able to listen, and you might just have to leave.

Sometimes we don't really know what we need, and that's OK.

In this VR, that choice is within your hands. Our hands here.

This VR is around 17 minutes long, but you are in control of how long you listen. If you need to take a break you can place your hands down on the table and the VR will pause. If you want to leave, continue to hold your hands on the table and the VR will end and you can take off the headset.

We can do a little test if you like.

I'm going to sing a note, and when you want to pause my voice, place both palms flat on the table. When you are ready to listen again, lift them up.

At this point Len sings a long impressive operatic 'Aaaahhhh'. This held note allows audiences a moment of low stakes practice in interrupting a voice with the table pause mechanic, before entering into the contributor narratives in which this would be less appropriate.

The entire passage of the introduction is aimed towards priming the audience's attention to their phenomenological experience of embodiment, including the overlapping of the senses - hearing as a form of touch for example. This attention is also used to draw the audience to attend to their social responses - the reflex to sooth while another speaks for example - as a precursor to 'listening' to both the contributor speaking, and their internal sense of what they feel ready to listen to, if at all, and the introduction of the pause mechanism.

After the audience pauses Len's note⁵⁹, Len stops singing, and introduces the next 'voice';

Ok. Do you feel ready to listen? The next voice is about to speak.

⁵⁹ As is common in VR, if the audience fails to pause the note, the note will end after a set time, and transition to the following scene which begins with Len's last line. This moment in the work also became an essential tool for hosts, as I will explore in the exhibition section.

Working with Khora

The work of a producer is often to be a communicator, sharing ideas between different parties of a production. This requires a shifting use of language, using symbolism and often gestures to communicate ideas where I lack the technical language to do so, as is apparent in my early discussion with Simon. It also often involves imagining the most simple way to do something, that might bypass the more complicated 'proper' way, which the technologist or developer is almost always thinking about - for example, matching a hand texture to a corresponding hand model as a matter of course, rather than attempting to mix and match.

Despite it being my suggestion to use the photogrammetrically produced hands textures of contributors to 'reskin' the Oculus Quest 2 Hand Tracking models, I am not a coder nor a photogrammetry artist or 3D designer, and could not make these assets myself. Luckily, I had the opportunity to work with very accommodating collaborators on the photogrammetry in the project, including CAMERA and Saturn Akin, who were able to interpret my understanding of the process and then communicate directly with Khora's developers to generate the required assets.

Following facilitating Khora's connection to other technical members of production, my main work with Khora became iterative feedback. The assembly of the WTH sound and visual assets happened very quickly, over the course of about a month in October, before the exhibition at IDFA in early November. This feedback was almost entirely remote. Khora would send me builds, which I would load onto my own headset. This process is mildly technical, and beyond what I could reasonably ask any of my collaborators in Glasgow or Bristol, meaning only I saw the work in-headset, and others only video capture from inside the headset.

Video capture from inside the headset is a particularly poor way to assess the feeling and atmosphere of a VR experience, as it's only read as a flat image. For example, early WTH builds used a uniform flat dark purple colour to 'fill' the environment, as implied by the storyboard document. They also included a flat, universal lighting for the whole 'space' of the VR scene. This *looked* fine in the video capture from Khora, and aligned with the storyboard. However

upon receiving and viewing this first build in the headset, this space *felt* oppressive, as without distinguishable walls or floor, one could not get a sense of the scale; it felt simultaneous as if the space extended to eternity but also was pressed up close upon the eyeballs. The uniform colour, in combination with the flat lighting, also read as childlike. It is often that a VR space reads as something, without fully understanding why or being able to completely describe the effect. In this instance, I am not sure if the childlike quality was in relation to colour; as objects for children traditionally have these flat 1 dimensional colours and the colour of the space was what might be described as 'Barney' purple, or because the scale of the room was so large or indefinite that the table felt small and childlike in comparison, and thus cast me as a child because the table was the appropriate size for me. In either case, the sensation was negated by the use of spot lighting effect on the table, and the introduction of a black or very dark purple haze in the environment. This produced a sense of not being able to see out into the virtual distance beyond the spotlight, and defined a space around the table without requiring any creation of walls or other architecture.

During early production application stages I submitted the project to International Documentary Fund Amsterdam's research and development fund⁶⁰. In June, partway through research and development I received confirmation that this application was successful, which meant the project would premier at IDFA 2022 in November. Although this provided additional funds to the project, it also necessitated a deadline and an audience ready piece of work, rather than merely a work-in-progress. Khora had already in June scheduled their developer time on the project to happen in October, which created a very short window for the technical build of *WTH*, between 1st of October and the first week of November.

Due to the timeframe, feedback to Khora had to be delivered quickly. This meant that any requests for changes from the collaborating artists; Fossilised Frequencies, Naroa, Chris and SLEEC, based on these in-headset video recordings had to come back to me within 24 hours or less, and feedback emails I sent to Khora included a lot of information. This expedited production period created a bottleneck in the feedback process, and some changes from contributors, particularly Naroa, were not implemented as she wished. There was often the feeling that more equitable relations between different creatives on the side of the project that I

⁶⁰ In collaboration with the Massachusetts Institute of Technology

managed were not in fact compatible with the way a professional studio like Khora is set up to work. There was certainly a friction felt in transitioning from the more sensitive and reflective mode of production the *WTH* team had been operating under up-until this point, with the fast pace project management style of the Khora, which was also necessitated by the deadline.

This is most apparent in the sound and lighting design. As a matter of course, Khora had used a sound library to embed diegetic sound into the woodland and pub scenes, which were not removed once the sound design files were provided. This diegetic sound was not in the script nor in the sound design as Fossilised Frequencies had envisaged it and was somewhat at odds with works ambition toward non-simulation. Similarly, Naroa's notes on carceral or prison-like lighting and atmosphere in the beginning of her piece were interpreted by Khora more literally, as flashing blue and red police lights and the sound of a police siren. Despite a note from Naroa to remove this lighting and sound, the quantity and speed of feedback and changes Khora were implementing meant that these changes to audio were, presumably, de-prioritised on Khora's side, in favour of more urgent tasks. This was a difficult reality of essentially handing over responsibility for the order of work to a producer on the Khora side at this point of production.

4.3 Exhibition

Image 17. - With These Hands Installation Design and Final Installation (Image Credit Jurre Rompa), November 2022

User Testing Session at CSSS

In the last week of production with Khora, and as a conclusion to my research exchange within the Centre for Sexuality and Sexology Studies (CSSS) at Malmö University, I shared a late stage prototype of *With These Hands* to students and colleagues from the department and the universities wider immersive arts and media departments. In doing so I hoped to understand what further adaptation to the work might be required for the IDFA installation, including changes to the in-headset content, the surrounding exhibition installation, and onboarding and offboarding required of the host.

My colleagues at CSSS presented a particularly interesting user testing audience as many of the academics from the school would be first time VR users, but familiar with the discourse around rape and consent, survivor identities, and alternatives to the incarceration of sex offenders to which the stories of *WTH* refer⁶¹. In multiple senses this made them an ideal audience to test the interactive mechanics of the work, as, with no prior VR experience as reference, their ability to use the work smoothly would be indicative of only the internal onboarding proficiency. It would also be reasonable to assume these academics, due to their being situated within sexology research broadly, would be less likely to experience apprehension around the work's topics of sexual harm. This makes them a more ethical group with which to test the touch based pause & consent mechanism within the work.

I also invited other academics from Malmö University's K3 department (the school of arts and communication). These were Susan Kozel; a dancer, choreographer and researcher deeply informed in phenomenological practice based research with interactive and immersive technology, and Maria Engberg and Joshka Wessels; both eminent researchers working with VR technologies, with expertise in discourses around VR as an Empathy Machine from their backgrounds in media theory, and documentary and anthropology respectively. Their combined feedback offered a more materially focused, but equally insightful perspective as the CSSS researchers⁶².

⁶¹ Many academics were working with sexual assault survivors, including male survivors of childhood sexual abuse and the high propensity for histories of sexual abuse in the female prison population. Others were researching BDSM practices and women's pain during intercourse.

⁶² Notably, this entire test audience were women. I did also receive some feedback separately from men on the project, including my supervisor, and the team at Khora who were all male save the producer. I also invited 2 male friends to view the work also in Malmö.

To broadly summarise the feedback of the user sharing sessions at CSSS, those more familiar with the technology gave feedback on the material qualities of the work; it's sound design and user journey, academics more familiar with the content made comment on the nature of the stories represented, and on VR as a novel tool for sharing this kind of testimony in a way that demands more 'attention'. I will draw on specific elements of their feedback within my reflections on practice, however there were elements of the feedback that were particularly influential to the IDFA exhibition design.

Are you sitting comfortably? User Observations informing design

As a means to assess the technical onboarding provided by the in-headset introduction, I gave minimal in-person onboarding to the CSSS audience, save ensuring the virtual table asset would be aligned with an in person table in the makeshift exhibition space. I found that only 1 of the user testing audience (around 13 in total) had any difficulty managing to operate the pause mechanism during the 'test' portion of the intro. This indicated to me that the onboarding of the work was sufficient in a technical sense.

I also observed that using the headset directional audio speakers embedded in the headset strap was preferable to plug-in over-ear headphones. This audio output made the voice overs and ambient sound design particularly clear to the user, whilst pushing the Khora implemented diegetic sound 'to the back' of one's hearing⁶³. All these sounds were then mixed with the sounds of the exhibition space - the noise of the chair, or the contact of one's hand on the table. This felt most appropriate to the phenomenological aspirations of the work, as it did not cut the users off from their sense of surroundings. Additionally, using the headset audio provided useful information for the host. Len's held note is loud enough to be clearly audible to a host a few feet away. If this note extends after the user places their hands on the table, this indicates that the headset (and virtual table) is out of alignment with the in person table. Although in the instance when this occurred, I did not interrupt the user's experience to correct the issue, I was able to adjust the headset calibration before the next user.

⁶³ This was the best way to navigate the inclusion of this diegetic sound which was not originally in the script and, partly in response to this feedback, not removed from the experience.

I further used this sharing as an opportunity to get feedback on the sound design, particularly the additional diegetic sound, the siren sound and red and blue flashing lighting in Naroa's scene. Interestingly, when asked audiences either did not notice the woodland or pub diegetic soundscapes, or if they did, they said this helped them to understand 'where they were supposed to be'. Most interestingly of all, when I asked participants about the flashing red and blue lights of Naroa's piece and the siren sound, not a single participant recalled hearing or seeing these. Based on the feedback that these sounds and lights appear to be imperceptible to audiences, Naroa consented to screen this version of the *WTH* at IDFA if changes were not actionable by Khora in time.

One of the most frequent comments from audiences was the feeling of awkwardness of holding one's hands above the table. This was surprising to me as personally, the appeal of touching the hands was such that I had made the assumption this would be the same for other audiences. The natural position for me testing the work myself was to place my elbows on the table and hold my hands together close to my face, rubbing or touching the hands over the course of the experience, and sometimes reaching out toward virtual objects. Although some users did find their way into this elbows-on-table position naturally, others preferred to sit back with their hands in their laps. A sat back pose would also not interrupt the experience through unintentional pausing, although it was clear that these audiences were focusing more on audio, than on touch and the hand assets. Some other users, however, tried to hold their arms up in front of them during the entire experience, which would prove uncomfortable over the 17 minute run time. Interestingly, the introduction gives no indication that this is required of a user, merely making brief reference to touching and looking at the hands. Additionally, if one were to sit at a table and listen to a purely audio piece, I do not believe that most people would choose to do so with both hands palm down on the table in front of them - which is the only position prohibited by the pausing mechanism. Furthermore, only one user described this awkwardness as a negative in the work. Many users felt that the awkwardness of wondering how to position their hands was a result of the work asking them to consider their own body's sensation, and the voice over requesting they consider their potential discomfort *with content*, which was then felt as this bodily sensation, a point I will return to my reflection. The one user who found this experience negative was in fact the one user who I had attempted to direct physically.

After receiving the same feedback about the discomfort around hand placement a few times, I wanted to test if more explicit instruction on physical positioning might either alleviate this effect, or perhaps generate new sensations and reflections. For one audience member, I asked explicitly if she could place her elbows on the table to begin. When she exited the experience, she commented that this elbow position had eventually become uncomfortable and had distracted her from the narrative overall. What I gleaned from this was that if the position of the audience was over directed, then that audience member becomes less reflective about their discomfort, and merely assigns it to the physical cue of the host rather than an effect of the work.

By the end of this first sharing I had finalised a staging of the work in which the prospective host would offer the user a seat by pulling it away from the table. In response, the user would, upon sitting down, naturally draw the chair closer toward the table. Starting the work closer to the table allows the audience to either sit back with hands in lap or forward with elbows on the table, without either position being expressly instructed by the host. Additionally I understood that the installation itself should provide prompts to ensure the user is not only sitting 'comfortably' in the work, but facing directly forward, to give the virtual and real assets the best chance of naturally aligning.

Making room for Speaking as well as Listening

It was evident after the sharing at CSSS that the work sparked discussion, and personal reflection. This is in part because *WTH* does indeed present somewhat challenging, 'unheard' and to some, counterintuitive perspectives, much feedback also was about being challenged by the content. For example, although not surprising to SLEEC, myself or the academics from CSSS, Naroa's assertion that her experience of the police was worse than her assault was often surprising to male audiences, such as the Khora developers⁶⁴. Other audiences commented on feeling annoyed or frustrated by the actions of Chris' character. The in-headset experience however, does not provide any recourse or channel for voicing these thoughts or responses.

⁶⁴ It is also noted by Kent Bye in his reflections on the work after it's screening at IDFA (Bye, 2022)

Time and budget with Khora did not permit that any form of voice input from users could be included within the work. However, it was possible to incorporate a QR code in the exhibition materials at IDFA that would allow audiences to respond in audio form. The ability to receive comment from IDFA audiences was not intended as a form of qualitative data collection for my research, but the only available option for an artistic intervention which would permit audience 'speaking' as well as 'listening' opportunities in the interest of making the work more reciprocal. This also felt more in line with SLEECs practice of holding space for survivors and men to speak freely about their experiences in response to each other's testimony.

I scripted the final scene of the work to introduced this as a possibility;

Inside this VR you hopefully had a chance to listen, but there wasn't space in here for you to speak.

This VR is part of a wider research project about listening, empathy, documentary and VR. If you have thoughts, feelings or feedback about this work you can leave it as a voice note on the project page online.

If you feel ready to do that now there is a QR code on the table that will take you to the link.

I was particularly interested in these responses coming in audio form, rather than merely written feedback, to further draw parallels between the audience and contributor experience. The only workable method found, prior to IDFA exhibition, of providing this opportunity was through a QR code link which opens a webpage. This private webpage then invites audiences to open a WhatsApp chat in which they can leave a voice note.

This required consideration around data privacy, as WhatsApp would record the telephone numbers of the audience members who chose to respond. It was also deemed necessary to mention the wider research setting in which this work, and therefore collected responses, would sit. Once following the link and consenting to message the WhatsApp Business

number⁶⁵ audiences would receive an automated reply informing them of how long their data (their message and phone number) will be held and how their response might be used within my research⁶⁶.

The complexity of the multi link process, and the necessary formal additions to the script regarding consent and data privacy did appear to somewhat limit feedback. As a result, at the close of the IDFA exhibition I only receive feedback from four individuals, three comment on the work via text and one is a more personal response in a series of voice notes.

Installation Design

The inclusion of the work at IDFA meant that the installation surrounding the headset and table had to account for a more public style of exhibition. At IDFA, the work would be housed in a larger room with a number of other XR pieces running simultaneously. The booking system due to be implemented was a gallery time slot process, which limits the number of audience members moving through an exhibition space at any one time, but does not dictate specifically which pieces audiences choose to experience within their time slot. This creates an ad-hoc cue system for each experience, which is managed by the individual projects hosts.

This style of exhibition means at any one time a number of audience members are wandering the exhibition floor, and watching other audience members inside works. For *WTH*, it was important first and foremost that the installation around the headset provide privacy for the audience member inside. At the same time, the installation had to invite interest from the outside audience, and set an atmospheric tone for the work which would help prospective audiences make an informed decision about whether to view the work. Influenced by an intuition that there may be some user trepidation around entering the work based on its themes, the installation design approached these two requirements; privacy and fear reduction⁶⁷ as paramount.

⁶⁵ This is a private number, unrelated to my personal number, that I have access to on my personal phone through the whatsapp business application. This number ceases to function when I deactivate my whatsapp business account.

⁶⁶ Please see Appendix for more details.

⁶⁷ Although I am broadly using the term fear here, this fear could relate to a number of aspects of the work. Fear could relate to concern, as previously mentioned, about the work featuring scenes in which the audience are embodied as either victim or perpetrator in a simulated sexual assault. But one might also 'fear', especially as a

The most simple means of producing ‘seclusion’ or ‘privacy’ in a public exhibition space is to ‘curtain off’ the exhibit. Sensorially speaking, a curtain encloses the audience within a discrete ‘story’ space, beyond the gallery setting. This visual separation between inside and outside is accompanied by *an illusion* of sound and vibration dampening, although the curtains actual effect on these is negligible. The gallery space at IDFA was a repurposed theatre stage, with a high ceiling and a lighting rig. In order to utilise spot lighting from above to mimic the virtual spot lighting inside the VR experience, the *WTH* installation was a box frame with one partition ‘wall’, leaving it open on 3 sides and on top. Carpeting the footprint of the box texturally designated inner space from outer, and also enhanced the illusion of dampened sound. Pairs of curtains enclosed the space on the three open sides in a way that felt both private, yet permeable and inviting. From the outside, the 270 degree of visibility of the wandering gallery attendees was reduced to only glimpses of the audience members within. Opening the curtains indicated the project was free, attracting approach from prospective audiences. Once inside, the curtains could be drawn, serving as a signal that the experience was ‘occupied’.

Beyond the practicality of the curtained box, it also facilitated a visual communication of the tone of the piece. Influenced by SLEEC’s conscious use of vivid and vibrant colour in their social media and photography, and Naroa’s desire that the installation be ‘lighter’ than it’s content, I proposed a bold colour scheme drawn out from the work itself. The ‘space’ of the virtual environment of *WTH* is dark purple. A small carpet within the installation booth was a corresponding purple, the curtains were deep orange and the walls a pale mint and lilac. A conversation with the installation supervisor at IDFA helped me understand the value of this colour scheme. He expressed surprise as he had been expecting something more ‘sombre’ and ‘feminine, maybe dark reds and pinks or black’. The surprise induced by the bright colours of the installation in relation to the content was intended to interrupt preconceptions of the work as ‘sombre’ or ‘for women’, and perhaps therefore apprehension or anxiety about the content.

Based on feedback around the regional accents from the academics at CSSS, and in response to the multilingual audience at IDFA, as well as for access reasons, I decided the work should

survivor, experiencing a work which is condescending, or which you feel plays into stereotypes. One might feel fear about experiencing a work that you think might not have been made ethically. Certainly I have this kind of fear response around lot’s of VR documentaries, fear that it might make me angry, rather than frighten me.

also include in-headset subtitles. The subtitles were colour coded in line with each speaker, and these colours also corresponded to the set design to build further congruence between the virtual and physical assets.

The installation also tried to facilitate as much 'onboarding' as possible in its design, in order to further relieve the burden on the volunteer host. Text in the form of wall decals served both to prime audiences to engage with the work, and also to support or prompt the attending host.

The wall text read:

WHEN YOU ARE READY
FOCUS ON MY VOICE
AND PUT ON THE HEADSET

MY VOICE

The intention of the signage was to encourage the audience member to take pause before entering the work. The wording deliberately avoids, however, the word 'comfortable', as through discussion with SLEEC, I understood that to require or dictate an audience feel comfortable as a condition of entering the experience around sexual harm might be an overstep. It might well *not* feel comfortable to engage with content of this nature, and that's ok, as long as the audience feels 'ready' or prepared for discomfort. The reference to voice served a dual purpose. It sought to prime audiences to perhaps rearrange the primacy of 'looking', and primed attentive listening, as well as a bodily attention or 'focus' in line with the works phenomenological method.

The first 3 lines of the text were higher up the wall, the final line of the decal - 'my voice' - was positioned to be directly ahead of the user. This was an attempt to have the user facing the wall directly, square on, with their head raised when they put on the headset. If the piece was unattended by a host, this would give the work the best chance of naturally aligning virtual and real tables. Ideally, a host would encourage the audience to look at 'my voice', whilst aiding them to fit the headset.

Audience Reflections: “Thanks for the touching experience”

There are three main audiences who experienced *With These Hands* and gave feedback, either directly or through WhatsApp. These are the academics from Malmö University, the IDFA audience and finally the project collaborators; Chris, Meggan and Naroa. In order to premise my reflections on practice, I have grouped all these audiences' responses thematically.

Discomfort

As previously noted, audiences often commented on their physical feelings of discomfort in the work. However, in most instances this was considered as an effect of their attention to their own embodiment. One audience member likened this to the feeling of becoming conscious of being photographed, and ‘not knowing what to do with one's hand and somehow everything you try feels unnatural’. This discomfort felt like a result of becoming conscious to embodiment, through both the audio instruction and as ‘inside’ the hands, which was a particularly interesting effect of the work.

A further related frequent comment was about Chris' ‘dirty’ hands, and a noticeable physical response among some audiences during the shift from Naroa's scene to Chris' that spoke to discomfort. The ‘dirt’ audiences were referring to is the ‘doubling’ of Chris' thumb texture, from his moving during the scanning process. When I view the work, I see this very clearly as a ‘shadow’, and as referential to the photographic production of the asset. The frequent reference to this as ‘dirt’ or ‘gunk’ rather than an ‘error’ or other word is perhaps due to some cognitive bias towards seeing a mark on a hand as dirt. However the noticing of the ‘dirt’ was often accompanied with associated words like ‘disgusting’ or as another user put it ‘it felt a little bit alien to have male hands that were also a bit dirty..you feel something, I'm not quite sure what it is’.

Because Naroa's piece ends with the contemplation about the life and experience of her rapist: “I just like blueberry muffins. Sometimes I wonder if he likes them too”, I considered if this disgust is a response to the conscious or unconscious belief that these new male hands will be his perspective. In fact, when I shared the work with Chris himself in person, even though he knew the content of the work, he made a comment to this effect himself;

I was very on edge for a moment... But also because of the way that first piece ends, it did make me really think about that person as a human. Because I thought about them as a human, I was like 'oh, this could be them', and I thought that was really powerful actually. And even though it wasn't, it still contextualised this person as that a little bit. (1990s Chris, personal communication, December 2022)

It's possible that there is a negative association to wearing the male hands in a work in which one might, consciously or unconsciously, think those male hands are those of the rapist in the Naroa's story. This feeling of having something 'on' your own hands, this skin of this character which you do not want to 'touch' or be associated with becoming associated with something 'dirty' stuck to one's hands.

However, as one contributor notes that Naroa's piece resists presenting her rapist as something disgusting - 'If you make someone a monster then they can't be held accountable, if you are human, you must be accountable. He is not a monster'.

Body-Sharing & Consent

Another common reflection was a critical contemplation of the self/other hybridisation encouraged by, but simultaneously critiqued within the piece. Unlike the common reflections heard by audiences on emerging from VR, particularly in embodied VR or VR in which the user is cast as a character, none of the users spoke of the contributors or narratives of the work as 'I' or 'Me'. Although they had first person reflections on the work evidently - 'I was touching the flowers', 'I liked the fact that I can also close my eyes and focus on the voice' - this was also always accompanied by the acknowledgement of 'the voice', 'her voice', 'her hands', 'his decision' etc. Users made comments about being 'with' Chris and Naroa rather than as them in scenes, whilst simultaneously feeling drawn to compare themselves or align themselves physically to the characters through the hands; 'they were interesting because, these are definitely a man's hands, but they are smaller than mine' or 'her nails were painted this very cute blue and it's a bit chipped and it made me a bit emotional actually. I remember painting my nails like that'.

I also receive a text message as feedback that simply reads “thank you for the touching experience”. It is not clear if the sender intends the possible pun around themes of touching in the work. Either way, I enjoy the possibility of this either conscious or unconscious choice of words.

Particularly in my conversation with Maria Engberg and Susan Kozel, they reflected on alienation as a tactic of the work, as the work’s inhibiting your feeling completely comfortable or allowing you to ‘relax’ into a role or character. The work almost ‘refuses’ that audiences suspend their disbelief and this is experienced as a kind of ‘truthfulness’. Susan Kozel likened the experience to Brechtian theatre. The work makes an attempt to keep the audience involved in two worlds, not completely alienated from the VR but neither completely ‘immersed’, simultaneously ‘playing with’ and ‘dismantling’ the experience.

In our conversation Maria Engberg noted the propensity of VR experience instructional voice overs to request the audience automatically ‘trust’ the process of the work, sometimes utilising phrases like ‘just trust me/us’. In *WTH*, because the VR voice over draws attention the the way it has been made - “*of course - these aren’t my real hands. They are just the hands the headset automatically gives you*” - the voice over does not ask for trust but provides this evidence of its truthfulness or trustworthiness.

They both also note that much, especially linear, narrative VR content does not acknowledge that the user can leave. They often give an impression that one has to ‘strap in’ and see the project through to the end. In contrast *WTH* presents as ‘inviting’ the user to participate rather than ‘being subjected to it’.

Listening

Despite the relatively long runtime of the experience in VR terms, I do not receive any feedback that the experience is too long. This is potentially a result of the lack of visuals and the permission to ‘not look’ - as one user noted ‘I can also close my eyes and focus on the voice, because there’s not a lot that I *need* to pay attention to all the time visually’. Although much of the feedback rather attributed this to the ‘listenable’ qualities of the voices as ‘pleasant, and

very real' and the stories themselves - 'there's a lot of emphasis on voice...and for that reason you want to hear more'.

In the text based feedback from the IDFA audience however I did receive the comment that "the visual possibilities of your project are not really used. So, there should be more visual material to show. Now it was, apart from the three impressive stories, nothing or very little to witness". From this and other feedback, it's apparent that the lack of visual environment for some audiences is also experienced negatively or perhaps further, brings on some feelings of discomfort. I found this particularly apparent in the feedback I received from influential VR journalist and podcaster Kent Bye who seemed to feel pulled between the listening and the visual and embodied experience. His thoughts on the work are recorded on our interview featured on his podcast:

Well I wanted to talk a bit about my experience of this piece because it has a way in which you're embodied into these hands and you're listening to the story but you also see the subtitles that are in front of you. So I'm kind of reading along and listening and projecting myself into there. I'm not sure if I'm still listening but because I'm embodied in their body it gives me this interesting like, who am I? In this scene?...Because of the hand tracking aspects if you put your hands by your side then your hands are no longer being tracked. And so I wanted to see the hands because it felt like that was a part of the experience. But then I ended up having to put my hands up for you know 10-15 minutes however long the experience is which gets a little fatiguing because of the constraints of the tracking technology, I ended up kind of like leaning back and putting my hands on my stomach and then still at different moments during the scene just remind myself of the embodiment because I felt that was a part of the experience, but I guess I was really struck by embodying other characters and it made me see my own hands through that black and white low-res mixed reality pass-through camera of the Quest 2 kind of reflecting in my own embodiment in a way. And almost to the point where I was like really focusing on my own body more than I remember what the third section was about. (Bye, 2022a)

However earlier in our conversation, he clearly references the narrative of the piece which he felt he could not remember;

There's a part of this experience where there's a certain expectation of what you expect the survivor to say or do and to some extent there's certain narratives in this piece that were directly from the survivors that were not what I was expecting and I think that's maybe part of the point of the disobedient aspect (Bye, 2022a)

What I find particularly interesting in terms of the original aspirations of the project is not the conclusion that Kent comes to, that he did not listen to the third section. Clearly in an unconscious way he did listen and understand SLEEC writing and message, as he is able to somewhat summarise it. What I find a more compelling reading of this passage is that he becomes very self conscious to both his own embodiment, and his act of listening, so much so that he is experiencing the pull of embodiment and listening as in competition, and to some extent experiences a fear about not listening - "I'm not sure if I'm still listening".

Speaking

The first thing Meggan says after I share the work with her, to my relief, is "I realise how important it was for us not to put the "you" in". This is in relation to my request to change the 'you' to 'we' in SLEECs piece. This reflection feeds into further thoughts about the conversation or community building that could come after the work. Meggan describes the piece as the beginning of a conversation, but as not providing any appropriate space for this to continue, and the intervention of the WhatsApp was evidently insufficient. She further suggests;

What would be really cool is like, down the line, is the idea that you watch it collectively or you go into an environment where a discussion about it can be had...It's quite secular [sic], your just in your little world but with all these ideas..and then you take the headset off and I guess there is something about wanting a place to put all that stuff. Not in a way that's like trauma dumping, but in a way that's constructive and has a purpose that is actually maybe we could explore collectively now we've all gone through this experience... I do think there is something about people who want to talk..inevitably people do want to talk, or some people want to talk but don't know just how to yet and

would join this conversation and just listen. (Meggan Baker, personal communication, December 2022)

When I show the work with Chris, I also discuss with him the WhatsApp feedback I received. I tell him I feel that the outro feels a little academic and unfinished, and did not set the work up to receive the most interesting feedback from audiences. Chris challenges me on this:

I actually think it's really good because it fits in with the narrative of everything else, it's like, we're all working on it, we're all working through it. I like it because it invited me in to engage with it...It made me think about this as a 'practice', and there's no real place that we get to practise these things, at all, so it felt really valuable in this sense. (1990s Chris, personal communication, December 2022)

Emotional Responses

The work, though necessarily a sensitive subject, never aimed to engender emotional responses and crying from audiences. Much of the feedback I receive comments on the work as 'thoughtful' in terms of its ethical position and one person describes the work as an 'ethically airtight experience' that made them conscious of when other works had made them feel 'ethically alone in the work'. The concern with the work's ethics apparent to this audience member was felt as a form of co-presence, or 'not-aloneness'.

Only two audience members (that I witness or am aware of) become emotional in the work. One person becomes emotional and hugs me, but says they feel emotional not because the work encouraged them to do so, but because they could feel the care that had been put into it. They even say that they had previously been worried that the experience would feel exploitative, and were afraid to experience it, but that the installation, particularly the privacy of the curtains, had made them feel comfortable enough to try it.

The most emotional response is the one from a survivor who leaves a voice note. Due to the nature of the voice note format, this person is cut off multiple times as they speak, which is deeply regrettable. Their feedback is audibly occurring while they are in a busy environment, which I imagine to be the exhibition site of IDFA itself, possibly still inside the installation. The

person says they have just come out of the experience, and gives a little detail that they are also a victim of sexual violence, and that “it happened the same as the first victim as well”. Their voice starts to become more emotional, and they continue:

Um and I wanted to see, when I saw the exhibition, how was portrayed and um, I feel, I felt, super related with it and how people behave toward you if you don't behave as your life has just ended. (Anonymous audience feedback, November 2022)

English is not the person's first language, and their voice is also breaking as they speak. What I feel is more clearly conveyed in the audio, if not in this verbatim transcription, is that this person wanted to see the work because they had apprehension about how survivors of sexual assault would be portrayed. The rise in emotion in their breaking voice during “I feel, I felt, super related with it” comes across as relief or a release, which I interpret as a relief that the content is something they do in fact, relate to. In particular they relate to Naroa's views on the police.

So I am really glad you are making this project and I really hope people can empathise more and act more normal toward us. After 6 years I can be very open talking about the topic without feeling it, or then you start forgetting things. It gets better obviously. Then it doesn't matter, it's fine. But it's the authorities *laughs* are the ones that I have still problems with [sic]. (Anonymous audience feedback, November 2022)

I am very grateful to this audience member for taking time to respond to the work in such an emotionally open way. I find particularly their use of the term ‘empathise’ as important in conjunction with ‘act more normal towards us’. This implies that for this audience member, to ‘empathise’ is less about feeling moved by a story, or to feel that you understand ‘what it's like’ for the contributor, but to acknowledge contributors as ‘normal’, as possessing personhood *beyond* their trauma.

5 CONCLUSION

Image 18. - With These Hands Press Material (Image Credit Ned Pooler), November 2022

“I always felt I was working for you”

The person it felt most important to share the work with was Naroa, and sharing the piece with her felt in many ways like the conclusion of the project.

After setting her up in the headset, I leave her to experience the piece alone. I come back into the room when I hear the work is ending.

The first scene she talks about is SLEEC's. Although she has already seen video recordings of the work, as all the artists have, this doesn't accurately capture the passthrough effect, and so unlike the other scenes, this one feels fresh to her. She says “that's something I needed to hear today”.

I'm glad she feels uplifted by this scene which was in many ways the hardest one to get tonally right. This feels like a real success. I ask for her feelings about her own scene, and the work in general. “It feels a lot more self reflective to wear someone's hands.. It's more intimate than just watching someone, it's more vulnerable in a way...if I had made a video of me speaking, it would be like, a fixed point in time. It wouldnt reflect who I am forever... But my hands are me. It's the permanent view you have throughout your life. It is fixed, but in the right way, because it's the most personal view”

We have spoken often about time across the creation of the project. About how it feels to return to writing from a different point in your life and ‘voice’ it. About painting her nails before the hand scan because she wanted that and her jewellery she's wearing at the moment to be included, even though she knows that what jewellery and nail colour she likes will probably change over time.

We decided to read and listen together to the audience feedback - something I have been putting off since the IDFA exhibition a month or so ago. We start listening to some audio feedback. We quickly realise that this voice note is from someone who is very emotional, speaking immediately after seeing the work. It catches us both off guard⁶⁸. We look at each other and continue to listen.

⁶⁸ This is the same voice note as quoted in the previous chapter.

The speaker talks about Naroa's piece and how much it resonates with their own experiences with reporting an assault to the police, and how happy they are that this work has been made. When I first hear the emotion in the speaker's voice I feel worried - perhaps I should have listened to this ahead of time? Or let Naroa listen alone, or warn her in advance about the content of the message? After the voice note ends I apologise to Naroa. I say that perhaps us listening to that together for the first time wasn't the right thing to do. She says it's OK, it's interesting to see the different kinds of feedback and although she's also surprised to hear this emotional response, she's glad this person felt like the piece of writing spoke some of their own feelings aloud. Perhaps that's the point of writing these things and sharing them.

We start talking in general about my responsibility to her across the project. I say I hope that she feels I did her work and creative ideas justice, and that the end result is as she wanted it to be.

"It's interesting that you see it that way" she says smiling "that you were trying to make something for me. I felt like I was making stuff for you. I always felt like I was working for you".

She doesn't say this with any undertone of critique or judgement, merely surprised that our perspectives are so different. She evidently feels positively about this dynamic as she sees it.

Reflections on Proper Distance(s) in *With These Hands*

Much emerged from the making and exhibition of *With These Hands* which, taken together, can provide insights that answer my three practice focused research questions. With attention to the subject of sexual assault, came a deeper conception of and attention to consent in sexual ethics and consent in the documentary making process. This had an impact on a reconceptualising of 'proper distance' itself. Not only did I consider how proper distance is maintained between audiences and content through VR design, but also within the production process, between maker and contributors.

Reflecting on Theory: Proper Distance in the 'Face to Face'

In this section I return to my fourth research question 'What description of Empathy (if any) is useful in assessing proper distance in VR documentary?'. In order to consider 'proper distance(s)' as they appeared within my practice, I must first reflect on my personal definition of a proper distance and in doing so bring into question the appropriateness of the Levinasian ethic of 'infinite otherness', and its rejection of 'reciprocity'. In this reflection I proffer a reappraisal of the face-to-face by Simone de Beauvoir as outlined by Ellie Anderson. By using this reconceptualisation of the face-to-face, and with further attendance to Anderson's phenomenology of consent, I propose the ethical form of 'empathy' made possible through VR can be described as "feeling-with" the Other.

Throughout my work with SLEEC, it occurred to me that their critique of representations survivor and 'perpetrator' in media could be seen as somewhat at odds with the critique of Empathy Machine VR content from which this research was developed. Although, as discussed, 'proper distance' is a negotiation between sameness or proximity and strangeness or distance (Chouliaraki & Orgad, 2011), the predominant critique of 'The Empathy Machine' conception of VR is that it brings audiences 'too close' to documentary subjects, claiming a proximity, through simulation, to the subjective experience of the represented contributor that is 'improper' or unethical. SLEEC's position, as outlined by their discussions with me and appreciable in their own and Naroa's writing, is that there is *too much* distance generated by media representations of survivors and perpetrators. Survivors and perpetrators of sexual violence are presented as strangers, so Othered that many cannot recognise themselves in these depictions. This stands in the way of both adequate support for survivors and paths to acknowledging harm, responsibility and reform for perpetrators. Naroa's piece suggests that it was her relegation to object, and subsequent lack of recognition of her common humanity in the eyes of her attacker that was the most painful part of her assault, and she further insists this must not also be performed on her attacker. From working with SLEEC and Naroa, it seemed apparent that the *maintenance of personhood* is essential in order to support both survivors, and perpetrators of sexual harm.

Critiques of Empathy Machine VR content such as Nash's (2018) and Bollmer's (2017), do also indeed suggest that the contributor's personhood is what is compromised by the 'too close'

proximity of the empathy machine genre. They both (for Nash 2018, by way of Silverstone 2003, 2007) proffer the Levinasian ethic of the face-to-face, in which the personhood, as 'existential alterity', of the other must be maintained as ethical imperative. In other words, to ethically protect the complete 'otherness' of the Other. In the Levinasian view, failure to protect this 'infinity of alterity' is the ethical problem with the proximity produced within 'empathy machine' content, and the key to maintaining 'proper distance'.

Crucially, Levinas rejects any conception of 'reciprocity'; that I might imagine the other as perceiving me as I perceive them. For Levinas, this reciprocity is based on an illusory 'sameness' between myself and the Other which I cannot claim (Anderson, 2019 p. 5) and that any 'face' of the Other must remain an "infinite and absolute Other" (Anderson, p. 2). In the non-interactive medium of flat documentary, to appeal to this formation of ethics seems perhaps reasonable, as the representation of that other is so inaccessible - I am not 'inside' but 'faced' with this represented Other. However in exploring immersive and interactive work, my own and others, the concept of reciprocity seemed to emerge as a necessary ethical facility within the work, that stops audiences being able to fully 'extend' into or rather 'be extended by' their interaction inside it. In these works, which feature more literal or conceptual reciprocal interaction between audiences and represented contributors, users are no longer encouraged to 'explore', and potentially 'turn away' from contributors in order to consume all the visual and sensual experience possible within the work. 'Reciprocal interaction' is a more vulnerable and considered form of inter-action, in which only in turning toward (in the case of *Make Noise*, this is a 'speaking toward') the contributor's contribution, does that content reciprocally move also toward me, as an exchange⁶⁹. This seems fundamentally incompatible with Levinasian ethics. In the Levinasian ethic, the Other is 'infinite retreat' (Anderson, p. 12). However, alternate descriptions of the face-to-face in feminist phenomenologist Simone de Beauvoir describe that "the movement toward the other to entail a reciprocal movement from the other toward the self" (Anderson, p. 12). As such, it is Simone de Beauvoir's description of the face-to-face, and therefore 'proper distance' that is proposed here as a more useful guiding ethic of VR production.

⁶⁹ Although not an exchange which is represented as like-for-like. My voice in *Make Noise* is never implied to be 'just like' the kinds of protest of the suffragettes.

There has historically been a feminist critique of Levinas, which originates with de Beauvoir, that warranted further examination if the Levinasian Face-to-Face were to be taken as the basis for 'proper distance'. De Beauvoir is famous for her contributions to feminist thought and particularly a description of 'Otherness' as exemplified in the experience of women in patriarchal society. 'Otherness' in de Beauvoir, or what Anderson dubs 'sociopolitical alterity', is the systematic oppression of a group by presenting them as 'Othered', reducing them to things, and their self consciousness denied. De Beauvoir separates this from the 'existential alterity', an ethical imperative to acknowledge the freedom and independence of any Other as possessing 'personhood'. For de Beauvoir, these two kinds of alterity are in fact mutually exclusive. In existential alterity, the other's subjectivity is necessarily 'inaccessible', but nevertheless one takes the other as 'another subject' in 'reciprocal recognition' (Anderson, p. 6). De Beauvoir posits that sociopolitical alterity is in fact the failure to acknowledge reciprocity. Thus de Beauvoir takes against Levinasian ethics that positions women as 'the essence of alterity' 'without reciprocity' as an unjust denial of the subject-position of women - "woman thus appears as the inessential who never returns to the essential, as the absolute Other, without reciprocity" (de Beauvoir, 1997, p. 173). As Ellie Anderson writes "Levinas leaves no place for womans' own subjectivity- and, by extension, for a relation of reciprocity to man" (Anderson, 2019, p. 10). Levinas, in positing the feminine as the ultimate incarnation of Other without interiority is for de Beauvoir "the paragon of the patriarchal philosophy that relegates woman to the status of other through the oppressive denial of her subjectivity" (Anderson, p. 10).

The key difference between Levinas' face-to-face and de Beauvoir's is that Levinas holds that reciprocity is a form of reversibility, suggesting a complete equivalence between myself and Other. De Beauvoir suggests that although *reversibility* is ethically suspect, this does not foreclose on reciprocity. Reciprocity, in de Beauvoir writing, inherently speaks to "an inescapable asymmetry in our relations" (Anderson, p. 11). De Beauvoir further suggests this is best exemplified in the erotic or sexual encounter as shared touch illuminates "the ambiguity of human condition: that is, one's being subject and object at once" (Anderson, p. 13, see also de Beauvoir, 1997, p. 417). As Anderson concludes;

Acknowledging that a relation to an other is rooted in one's own first person perspective need not amount to treating the other as a function of oneself. Despite the fact that

Levinas purports to take this acknowledgement as the very foundation of his ethics, he reduces the other to the same precisely by making the other so transcendent that she is denied the position of sameness from which a relation could emerge. (Anderson, pg 17)

As previously mentioned, in the history of Phenomenology, 'Empathy' is the preferred term to describe the direct perception of another *in their humanity*. Rather than implying that one has access to the single subjective perspective of another, nor a sense of their interiority or content of their feelings, empathy is instead the basic sense of recognising another person as another body-consciousness. The person I perceive, despite appearing in my perceptual field as object, is also subject. In perceiving them as 'object-that-is-subject', I observe that I am co present, or 'feel with', a foreign embodied consciousness (Anderson, 2022, p. 12). Ellie Anderson (2022) suggests that this conception of 'feeling-with' a foreign body consciousness can be drawn upon in a phenomenological description of sex and sexual consent.

In latin, *consentire* refers to an 'agreement' "in sentiment, unity in opinion" (Online Etymology Dictionary, n.d. -d). The traditional reduction of consent in contemporary discourse is that this is 'an agreement' to 'do something' or 'do something to someone' (Oliver, 2018). Anderson (2022) suggests that etymologically, *consentire* rather implies a feeling (sentire) - with (con) (Online Etymology Dictionary, n.d. -d). This 'feeling-with', akin to phenomenology's empathy, involves the recognition of both self and other as embodied subjects, with different feelings and motivations, engaged however in shared perception. In the case of the sexual encounter, of a shared sexual acts. The sexual encounter is typified by, not a self-sameness with the other, but an ambiguity - "erotic experience..most poignantly reveals to humans beings their ambiguous condition; in it they are aware of themselves as flesh and as spirit, and as the other and as subject" (de Beauvoir, 1997, p. 423) and thus sex is "the encounter with that exceeds and undoes the subject's fantasmatic sovereignty" (Berlant & Edelman, 2014, p. 2). For de Beauvoir, ethical encounters, such as the ethical sexual encounter, are never about 'taking on another's point of view' and yet there is an awareness of both being subject and object within the encounter. Therefore one must also acknowledge that one's own freedom and the freedom of the other must be interdependent and mutually affirming. Kristina Arp describes de Beauvoir's view as 'almost mathematical' in the way fractions are dependent on one another (de Beauvoir, 2004, p. 241).

Ellie Anderson (2022) suggests that to redefine consent as “feeling with”, akin to phenomenological empathy, requires “recognising self and other as embodied subjects of desire for one another and for sharing an erotic experience” (Anderson, p.14). Further, this is a sense that can be developed - “this involves working to unlearn toxic social scripts..feeling-with another person requires recognising one's own positionality in power differentials” (Anderson, p. 19) including an awareness of the ever present possibility of sociopolitical alterity. Conversely, “lack of consent would be a lack of feeling-with-one-another” (Anderson, p. 21). As Anne Cahill suggests “a fundamental part of the violence of rape is that intersubjectivity becomes a one-way street, rather than the dynamic engagement that embodiment calls for” (Cahill, 2001, p. 132).

Consent here is defined as a ‘feeling-with-the-other’, an extension of phenomenological empathy, which demands the recognition of self and other as embodied subjects, but with an awareness of asymmetry. This asymmetry is exhibited in how much I can perceive the other - I can only perceive that to her I am object to her subject. This awareness is developed, however, through shared, asymmetrical, reciprocal action which is “intercorporeal”. Our irreducible difference is “two sided” (Anderson, 2019, p. 3)

Although the full articulation of Anderson’s philosophical position is beyond the bounds of this research, I believe it is this version of consent, phenomenological empathy and asymmetrical alterity which should inform proper distance in interactive and immersive documentary. This definition paramounts contributors personhood (their perception as objects-that-are-subjects) through reciprocity in design that is palpable in *Testimony*, *Make Noise* and, I propose, *With These Hands*. Contributors are not presented as objects to be ‘felt into’ or to reflect on ‘truths about the self’. In each of the works there is a mechanic of reciprocity that reminds me of the humanity of the documentary contributor *in relation* to myself and my embodied interaction with the work. However this relation is never claimed to be symmetrical, it is asymmetrical. The works do not suggest that she, the contributor, ‘is just like me’ or that I ‘feel what she feels’, nor is there a suggestion she is completely inscrutable to me in such a way as I can only ever reflect on my own feelings, and not stretch myself to listen to hers.

Reflecting on practice: VR Design & Proper Distance through Reorienting, Surfacing & Ant/agonism

Having now established that my measure of proper distance is not a Levinasian call to an 'infinity of alterity', but an existential alterity based on asymmetrical reciprocity and an acknowledgement of the contributors personhood- presenting her 'as human' in SLEECs words⁷⁰. This proper distance stresses that she, the contributor, *has* interiority, whilst not claiming that this is experienceable to the audience through the work. Nevertheless the ethical force of her subjecthood is 'felt-with' through 'intercorporeal' interactive experience. This reflection section is a response to my 2nd research question 'What methods of VR design can support 'proper distance' between audience and content?'. I present here three themes or effects within the work that I propose facilitate 'proper distance': Reorienting, Surfacing & Antagonism. These terms, which I draw out from existing feminist and decolonial documentary practice, installation making and phenomenology, are built upon within *With These Hands*. I suggest how VR can present novel applications of these existing conceptual methods of 'proper' or 'ethical' distance for nonfiction creative media.

Reorientation

This term relates to both Ahmed (and Merleau-Ponty's) 'Disorientation', but brings this into dialogue with Trinh T Minh Ha's 'Speaking Nearby'.

Within *Queer Phenomenology: Object, Orientations, Others* (2006), Ahmed frequently returns to disorientation as a queer experience, but also as a physical experience that simultaneously 'blocks bodily action' and permits us to see things 'slantwise'. She also outlines how orientations toward objects and others also reveal what we are centred around.

To approach a VR project with the express intention to disorient the audience might perhaps possess some revelatory potential - as the blocked bodily action that results from disorientation might resist critiques about virtual spaces "that can be navigated at will, in contrast to the lack of mobility experienced by the real-life people whose lives are the material for developers" (Nakamura, 2020, p. 54). Simultaneously it blocks or halts their 'extension' into or through the

⁷⁰ I believe this is also what is meant by the voice note feedback's description of empathy as "act more normal toward us".

project; the 'orthopaedic' extension of their empathic abilities (Bollmer & Guinness, 2020). However disorientation might also be experienced as a form of nausea (Bollmer & Guinness, 2020), bringing the audience's attention to their own physical sensation above or instead of attending to the Other in her personhood. In this sense encouraging a 'turning away' from the contribution of the contributor. Insofar as disorientation might produce effects of self-estrangement, it might further engage in 'improper distance', as Chouliaraki's 'irony', suggesting that the VR can only present to us "truths about ourselves" (Chouliaraki, 2011, p. 373).

By 'reorientation' I am referring to the choice to place the audience 'inside the skin' of the contributor. I propose that *WTH* audience position as 'inside the skin' does not allow the audience to imagine themselves *in* the others position, or suggest one is sharing their subjective perspective. However, it enforces a position *alongside* the contributor in an orientational sense. Speaking to the audience and contributors 'intercorporeal' experience of the world. The contributor and the audience share the same orientational centre, and thus attention to their perspective on a shared world is highlighted without ever implying that the audience can feel or experience what they, the contributor, feel or experience.

Although it is repeatedly drawn to the audience's attention through the voice over that they are not feeling-what-the-other-feels, the aesthetic potential of 'sharing' the skin of contributors, is that they are feeling - the environment, the table, their own hands - symbolically 'with' the hands of the contributor. Self touch is presented to both undermine any idea that the audience might feel what the contributor feels - "here, you can only touch yourself". Simultaneously the self-stranging through touch, of becoming object and subject, is analogous to the experience of 'feeling-with', of being both subject and becoming object through contact with the Other reciprocally.

Reorienting can also, I believe, interplay with Trinh T Minh Ha's 'Speaking Nearby' (Trihn, 1990). Speaking nearby is posed as an alternative to 'speaking about'. Orientationally speaking, when you 'speak about' you are oriented toward. When you speak nearby, you are orientationally alongside, as near, but not exactly on the same spot, acknowledging "the possible gap". "Although you are very close to your subject" Trihn suggests "you're also committed to not

speaking on their behalf, in their place or on top of them” (Balsom, 2018). Unlike the 2D media as Trihn is speaking of, this prompt taken into a VR context could be read as suggesting makers neither present representations of contributors which audiences face or meet - which would be representationally ‘speaking about’ - nor claim to show what it is to be them or claim shared experience - which would be representational speaking over or on top of them. To place audiences inside the skin of the contributor, feeling-with them, is perhaps a way a VR documentary could ‘speak nearby’ its contributor.

Similarly, this speaking nearby might permit forms of listening nearby. Which might be a form of ‘open’ listening where one does not consider that all meaning is communicated. Or, as Lisa Lipari terms it, ‘listening being’:

I don’t have to “feel” what you feel, or “know” what it feels like to be you. What I do need to do is stand in proximity to your pain. To stand with you, right next to you, and to belong to you, fully present to the ongoing expression of you. Letting go of my ideas about who you are, who I am, what “should” be. I let all that go, and stay present, attending, aware. (Lipari, 2010 p. 351)

Surfacing

Here I am not only referring to the use of photogrammetry to produce textures or ‘surfaces’ for the hand models but further draw relation between this and Laura U Marks’ (2000) visual surface of a media as ‘haptic image’.

In utilising the visual themes of ‘the outline’ (of the table and the hands) and then the ‘re-skinning’ of hand in *WTH*, the work draws the audience’s attention to the material qualities of its own production. The photogrammetrically produced ‘skins’ and table-top environment appear ‘as’ they are - an applied visual surface. In this action the work resists being read as a ‘window into the world’ that an audience might go through. This world is just surfaces or skins.

In presenting the user’s representation as a ‘skin’, the skin and touch can be drawn upon to further encourage audiences to think of themselves in ‘intercorporeal’ relation with the represented contributor. As the voice over suggests, there are not such fixed distinctions

between hearing and touching as we might imagine - and in the act of hearing is the 'touch' of soundwaves vibrating the eardrum. Similarly, or in relation, the skin is only an imagined border between the 'I' inside, the 'Other' and the world outside. As Ahmed (2006) puts it "skin that seems to contain the body is also where the atmospheres creates an impression" (Ahmed, 2006, p. 9). These atmospheres, like the cold bringing on goosebumps, leave 'impressions' on the skin. She also describes the skin surface as a 'paradox' "which appears to contain us, but is where others impress upon us" (Ahmed, 2004, p. 24). These inferences align with the kind of 'ambiguity' that also appears in the sexual encounter that "undoes the subject's fantasmatic sovereignty" (Berlant and Edelman, 2014 p. 2) and presents as a 'feeling-with' the Other.

In *The Skin of the Film*, Laura U Marks (2000) outlines a method of 'haptic visuality', in which filmmakers draw attention not only to sensory images of flesh, skin and touch, but also present the material qualities of film in such a way as they themselves might be read as a 'skin'. Through montage, distressing footage or using extreme close ups, the film appears more as a texture or as a surface, rather than legible as an image. Alternatively, they might be presented as 'haptic'; as in motion, such that the audience can 'feel' their looking, becoming aware of their own eye's movement across the surface of the image. This draws the audience's attention to the embodied experience of 'the gaze' or gazing. In doing so, Mark's suggests, they undermine looking as 'visual mastery' "in which the viewer isolates and comprehends the objects of vision" (Marks, 2000 p. 184) and replace this with an opposing 'ideal relation' between the viewer and the image as "one of mutuality". When vision becomes like touch, the object might "touch back" (Marks, p. 184). Haptic images therefore create a reciprocal relation between viewer and viewed. As Marks outlines "haptic visuality implies making oneself vulnerable to the image, reversing the relation of master that characterises optical viewing" (Marks, p. 185). Although Marks is referring to 2D cinema, in *WTH* the visual qualities of the photogrammetry as a surface, and the additional attention to 'touching' what is only 'visual' in the re-skinned hands, speak to this conception of haptic visuality. In haptic visuality, "the relation between perceiver and perceived as one of mutual embodiment, dynamic rather than destructive" (Marks, p. 193) offering representations of objects or others to the viewer "on the condition their unknowability remains intact" (Marks, p. 193).

Finally, in aligning touching and listening, the work further undermines the concept of a 'full' portrait of a contributor, or indeed undermines the concept of coherent communication between contributor and audience. As Ahmed suggests "thinking of speaking and hearing in terms of touch might allow us to challenge the very assumption that communication is about...the transparency of meaning, or pure exchange. Communication involves working with 'that which fails to get across'. (Ahmed, 2000 p. 155). She further outlines:

An ethical communication is about a certain way of holding proximity and distance together: one gets close enough to others to be touched by that which cannot be simply got across...It is through getting closer, rather than remaining at distance, that the impossibility of pure proximity can be put to work, or made to work. (Ahmed, 2000 p. 157).

In drawing attention to the 'not' touching of the material representation of the contributor - "all they can achieve is to become skinlike" (Marks, 2000, pg 192) - the work reflexively draws the audience's attention to this same potential of listening, which does not require full understanding.

Ant/agonism: Antagonism & Agonism

A key critique of the 'empathy machine' rhetoric is that it endows work with an 'orthopaedic' quality to teach users to empathise with others (Bollmer & Guinness, 2020). This further implies that by generating empathy and good feelings of connection we necessarily lay the groundwork for a 'feel good' forms of social cohesion and solidarity. Here I build on both Claire Bishop's 'antagonism' and Lille Chouliaraki's 'agonism' to present 'Ant/agonism' or 'discomforting' as a method of sustaining 'proper distance'.

Art critic and theorist Claire Bishop (2004), discusses the genre of 'relational' artworks that emerged between 1990 - 2010 that purported to develop democratic relations in audiences, allowing them to "learn to inhabit the world in a better way" (Bourriaud, 2002, p. 13). She suggests that in their 'convivial' 'microtopian' aspirations, many of these artworks did not adequately investigate the *quality* of the social relations engendered by the work. Artists within the Relational Aesthetics movement and their advocates suggested their artworks are

'immersive' spaces in which audiences can have "an impressive experience of togetherness with everybody" (Udo Kittelman quoted in Bishop, p. 68). They act as stages of 'micro utopian togetherness', and their requirement of viewer participation makes them inherently democratic, and capable of "producing positive human relationships" (Bishop, p. 62). However, Bishop urges a more critical appraisal of the relations encouraged within the work, and the resulting concept of democracy (as 'togetherness' or 'oneness') they uphold. To illustrate her point she unpacks more fringe artwork of the movement that, rather than addressing an imagined (and fantasy) 'everybody' in 'togetherness', actively illustrates the economic and social realities of the art market, and speaks more directly the audience's own position in the work. This work is typified by its production of feelings of unease and discomfort, non-reconciliation and sustained tension for audiences, which Bishop suggests are more aligned with an actual 'democratic' experience.

Bishop cites the political theory of Laclau and Mouffe (1985) who suggest that a democratic society is not one in which all antagonisms have disappeared, but where relations of conflict are sustained and acknowledged. She explains that "without antagonism there is only the imposed consensus of authoritarian order - a total suppression of debate and discussion, which is inimical to democracy" (Bishop, p. 66). To discuss antagonism in relational artwork, Bishop uses as example Santiago Serra installations made with members of the public including *160 cm Line Tattooed on Four People* (2000) and *Workers Who Cannot Be Paid, Remunerated to Remain Inside Cardboard Boxes* (2000). The hallmarks of Serra's work are a focus on the remuneration of the participants, the value of their labour and the value of art as commodity, drawing attention to the fact his performer collaborators are from lower economic and often immigrant or undocumented backgrounds. Serra's work certainly "does not offer an experience of transcendent human empathy that smooths over the awkward situation before us", rather than a feeling of togetherness, the work highlights "a pointed racial and economic non-identification: "this is not me"" (Bishop, 2004 p. 79). It draws attention to the fantasy of the 'every' 'body', and to the economic reality of the bodies within the work - some bodies are paid to be there, other bodies come to look at them as leisure activity. Bishop argues that in making plain the social, institutional context surrounding the artwork (e.g. immigration, homelessness, minimum wage), without claiming to reconcile them through the artwork, Serra brings the

divisions represented in the work between audiences and the citizen performers into antagonistic dialogue.

She suggests Serra's artwork, and that of related artists, are born out of the 'relational aesthetics' movement, but strive towards the less feel good but more actionable vision of Laclau and Mouffe's democracy. This genre of artworks, which she terms 'relational antagonism' are:

Predicated not on social harmony, but on exposing that which is repressed in sustaining the semblance of this harmony. It would thereby prove a more concrete and polemic ground for rethinking our relationship to the world and to one another (Bishop, 2004, p. 79).

In exploring methods of proper distance when documenting suffering of Others, Lille Chouliaraki (2011) outlines the two predominant paradigms within humanitarian discourse and media as 'Pity' and 'Irony'. She asks the question:

Would it not be possible to imagine a different communication structure of humanitarianism that navigates beyond pity and irony and escapes the arrogant proximity of the former and the narcissistic self-distance of the latter? Is it not possible to produce an alternative vision of solidarity? (Chouliaraki, 2011 p. 372 - 373)

She suggests, building on Silverstone, that 'proper' navigation of distance requires we present suffering, or the Other's vulnerability as "a political question of justice that invites us to relate to the vulnerable other as an 'other with her or his own humanity' (Chouliaraki p. 373, citing Silverstone; see also Silverstone, 2003, p. 4). She proposes a more ethical paradigm, which she terms as 'Agonistic solidarity', that would require the inclusion of the vulnerable Others voice at minimum, but moreover presents her as:

A historical agent - someone who actively strives to manage her life, yet under conditions severely constrained by structures of injustice, global and local...contra pity,

the other escapes the 'universalist' imagery of powerlessness, destitution or hopeful self determination, characteristic of the traditional stereotypes of humanitarian communication. Agonistic solidarity, in this sense, may rely on more complex but also, perhaps, more discomfoting representations of distant others (Chouliaraki, 2011, p. 375).

Agonism, which Chouliaraki draws out from the work of political phenomenologist Hannah Arendt, lays importance on generating 'public' spaces in which differences of opinion and 'the voicing of standpoints' is made possible. By 'hearing the Other in her own voice', Chouliaraki means both literally, but also implies this voice is inherently less 'listenable to' than a figure who "speaks in our own voice" or from a similar perspective to us (Chouliaraki, p. 374). The Others 'own voice' dissolves the universalism of the pitiful victim, or the solipsistic introspection of the ironic model of solidarity. Rather, an agonistic representation platforms the Other(s) in their complexity and plurality, so much that "there may be many definitions of injustice, various manifestations of collective responsibility and multiple visions of social change" presented within the work. Chouliaraki describes:

It is by carving out the communicative space wherein the radical plurality of these standpoints becomes the object of politics – that is to say, the object of public deliberation and collective judgement, that agonistic solidarity may be able to galvanize the sensibilities of Western publics towards other-oriented, rather than self-oriented, expressions of solidarity.

Both Bishop's Antagonism and Chouliaraki's Agonism are about creating artworks that are explicit about the 'struggle'⁷¹ to hear and understand the Other given a specific political and social context. They make plain the asymmetrical reality of the audience's contact with them (the Other and the documentary subject) and rather than encourage pity, present "human vulnerability as a political question of injustice that can become the object of our collective reflection" (Chouliaraki, p. 337). Moreover, they speak to not a monolithic 'Other', but a plurality of perspectives within a cohort of contributors and bring to the surface "discomfoting stories: [that] show us how new media may disempower as well as empower" (Chouliaraki, p. 376). I believe that not only can Bishop's Antagonism and Chouliaraki's Agonism can be read as

⁷¹ The Greek roots of 'agonism' and 'antagonism' are '*agōnia*' meaning struggle or contest and '*agōn*': a group of people brought together (Online Etymology Dictionary, n.d. -a)

mutually affirming⁷², hence Ant/agonism, but that this quality is legible in many aspects of *With These Hands* and is key to its claim to proper distance.

Prominent in *With These Hands* is the contributors' literal 'voice', but more importantly this voice is not edited or drawn out of the contributor by me in interviews. *WTH* represents contributors in their own words, written on their own terms. Moreover the texts of *WTH*, as the media Chouliaraki cites herself as exemplary of agonistic solidarity, discuss within them the question of representation, and are self aware of the disempowering potential of media images of survivors and victims of sexual violence. The stories of *With These Hands* are discomforting, in that they require the audience to consider the ethics of their engagement with them and particularly their experience as 'inside the skin' but yet 'only touching' themselves. Moreover, they present complex representations of individuals, as both Chris' and Narao's stories resist portraying rapists as 'monsters', which would be easier to countenance. In doing so, as an audience member remarked, you are forced toward the more uncomfortable question of human accountability and what can be forgiven⁷³.

I suggest that it is the passthrough scene which exhibits the most profound Ant/agonistic potential. SLEEC's writing certainly presents survivors as a collective who strive to manage their own lives whilst "under conditions severely constrained by structure[s] of injustice, global and local" (Chouliaraki, 2011, p. 375). Additionally, the passthrough and representational 'survivor' figure certainly "do not offer an experience of transcendent human empathy that smooths over the awkward situation before us" (Bishop, 2004 p. 79). On first experiencing this scene I noted:

As a viewer, one feels in the presence of someone else, who is both speaking to and watching you, whilst you see your own hands and the environment around you for the first time inside the work. This scene does not feel confrontational, but slightly uncomfortable. One feels even more strongly than I had anticipated a sense of 'looking at one's own looking' or indeed a feeling of

⁷² I am aware that there is a specific (and contested) difference in political discourse between antagonism (conflict between enemies) and agonism (conflict between adversaries) which is detailed in the political writing of Chantal Mouffe (2000; 2005) among others. In use within the Bishop and Chouliaraki texts however, they both amount to a tactic by which political and perspective conflict between audience and contributor(s) is brought to the surface, as Mouffe (2000) describes it "instead of trying to erase the traces of power and exclusion, democratic politics require us to bring them to the fore, to make them visible so that they can enter the terrain of contestation" (34–35).

⁷³ In contrast to other VR experiences about sexual assault, in which users are encouraged to emotions like disgust - see Constine's (2015)

being caught looking, or 'being seen to be looking' - the looked-at now feels like 'she' is looking at me back. Simultaneously, the anonymity of the figure across the table resists me looking at her. I have the sense that she can see me, but I can't see her.

The work also engages in ant/agonism in its refusal to allow audiences to be completely comfortable, in their embodiment or in their listening. Evidenced by the many reflections on social and physical discomfort in the work, and the 'refusal' to permit audiences suspension of their disbelief. Particularly I believe this is what is apparent in Kent Bye's experience of struggle between listening and embodiment. The work draws attention to both embodiment and listening as not being able to fully communicate, as 'that which fails to get across'.

Reflecting on Production: Asymmetrical Reciprocity with Contributors

In this section I approach my 3rd research question: What methods of production can support 'proper distance' between a contributor and their VR representation? This is the question for which the meaning has shifted most between the beginning and end of this research. Originally, this question was more concerned with the ethical representation of contributors, as relating to feminist documentary inquiry. I imagined it would (and it has) entailed resisting making 'totalising' knowledge claims about contributors, through representational means. However, in the course of production this has developed into a question of how one thinks of, works and communicates with, as well as represents, contributors. I return to the personal reflection with which I opened this chapter, my sharing of *With These Hands* with Naroa, and her suggestion that she always felt like she was working for me:

This comment sticks with me long after our meeting. Is this how she should feel? That she was working for me? This at first doesn't seem quite aligned with the ambitions of equity that I had begun the project with.

Looking back now however, I feel like perhaps this is a way to describe our dynamic. In a positive and healthy co-working relationship, there is a power exchange, but this is explicit and transparently documented. There is an expectation of time and effort given to a project, but crucially, this is valued, reimbursed for and credited. There is both an ownership over personal work, and an understanding that this work figures into a wider whole. The individual worker has

a vested interest in the wider whole, but is also not solely responsible for its outcome, positive or negative. There is an expectation to protect employees in a workplace, but it is not a parental or codependent dynamic. The ability to conduct your role is your manager's responsibility, but you yourself are not your manager's ward. Managing a project is relational, one must be responsive to the needs of employees, however responsibility is clearly apportioned. It's important that a manager, for example, accurately describe to the hire their role and what is expected of them, to make sure the workplace is fit and safe for that purpose, to facilitate the best work from employees. However, workers are independent, able to give feedback on working conditions, and leave their role at any time, without fearing an emotional response from management.

In many ways, working with SLEEC, and making a work that engaged with their vision for survivor representation was about divesting from both visual and organisational constructions which imagine survivors as weak, or unable to advocate or organise for themselves. It also required a reconfiguration of what a care based approach is, if not based on those assumptions. At times in the project I have struggled with imagining this new approach in practice, however I now think perhaps sharing the feedback with Naroa is an example of this. The audio feedback was in fact for Naroa, and about Naroa's work. As such it is not for me to stand between or interpret how best she should receive it. I think now it would have been inappropriate to pre-describe the content in some way to Naroa, as my interpretation and hers will undoubtedly be different.

I think it was important for us to sit and listen to that together for the first time at the same time. As such, we were facing toward the same content together, but knowing we were each feeling something different.

I am certainly not suggesting that a manager-employee relationship is the epitome of ethical relations, nor that it is impossible to have a completely unethical version of this arrangement. However, working through the analogy helped me to consider Naroa's sense of working 'for' me as not completely out of line with the thinking of this project.

This research project did not initially set out to explore or present methods of ‘collaboration’ with contributors. As I have mentioned, the use of that word in this exegesis is not uncontentious. Naroa, Chris, SLEEC, the consult survivors group and the ‘men’s learning’ course attendees did not have significant influence over the format, technologies or exhibition of *With These Hands*, nor over the initiation of the wider research it was a part of. In some senses it was not collaborative and certainly not a truly co-authored work. Yet, adopting an ethics of a face-to-face which I can now more clearly define as Asymmetrical and Reciprocal, required me to not only within the work represent my contributors as having existential alterity and interiority, but do my best to uphold that, or orient around that, within production. I will later suggest that there are practical outcomes of this research project that might be useful resources for other makers, helping them to consider working more consensually with contributors. The description of the workshop process, and the iterative and editable contributor consent document being examples of this. However, the influence of this conception of reciprocity on the project is more nuanced, and its impact on this research question is more profound, and resulted in more than a set of actionable methods.

Working with SLEEC had considerable influence on my conception of proper distance and methods of production. Working with or from their existing organisation methods, and their lived experience expertise, considerably opened up what ‘proper distance’ in the maker - contributor relationship might be. As opposed to any suggestion that *my* methods of production supported ‘proper distance’ between them and their VR representation, I might say that a relation of reciprocity with my contributor (which involved listening, being open to not fully understanding and navigating perhaps ant/agonism) rearranged this question. The new formation might be something like ‘what are your contributors’ requirements for ‘proper distance’ within your production’ or ‘how can contributors influence the production’s conception of ‘proper distance’’. This is not to say that my conception of proper distance within this research was completely dictated by SLEEC as evidently, working with hands as a representational device was not something SLEEC were themselves interested in. However much of the thinking and reflection around proper distance within this research has been prompted or expanded by the experience led knowledge SLEEC. A large outcome of the workshops was that production materials must communicate maker intentions, so that

contributors can make their own assessment (and addendums) to the production's ethical framework and its model of appropriate distances.

Contribution to the field of VR documentary studies and ethics

First and foremost this exegesis and artefact thesis exhibits and recounts an in depth practice based investigation into VR documentary making, in particular one which aims to remain cognisant of ethical relations between VR maker, contributor and audience. More specifically, this exegesis explores production of a VR documentary that is informed by the ethical 'risk of improper distance' as outlined by Kate Nash (2018). Additionally one which applies the descriptive methodology and language from Sara Ahmed's *Queer Phenomenology* (2006) to elaborate on 'improper distances' as they manifest in practice. There is a paucity of similarly detailed accounts of VR documentary practice in academic or professional contexts, and very few that specifically address the material production of 'proper distance' from a maker's perspective. This PhD research presents, therefore, as novel and valuable in this regard.

The practice based artifact of this thesis additionally presents novel use of photogrammetrically produced assets, and prescient application of these in combination with hand tracking and a hybrid VR/ MR/ Installation experience. As a consequence, this PhD research also presents as a timely investigation into the technological developments of the contemporary HMD and it's ability to move between MR and VR modalities in one experience. Developments in XR and headset technology are such that the exact technologies and material production methods detailed in this research will likely be obsolete soon or before publication. It is the analysis of the ethical implications and opportunities of the combination of hand tracking, MR and VR when applied to documentary content that are then key to this thesis claims to an original contribution to knowledge.

Working back from practice, this thesis also links methods (material and conceptual) applied in the making of the artefact *With These Hands* and early investigatory practice, to contemporary feminist phenomenological thought and histories of feminist and decolonial filmmaking.

Most prominently, the artefact and exegesis suggest not only is the Levinasian face-to-face formation of ethical representation - or 'proper distance' - vulnerable to existing feminist

critique, but its dependence on non-reciprocity does not appear to be born out in VR documentaries that illustrate proper distance, in my own or others (Nash, 2020) estimation. Through the production of artefact *With These Hands*, greater attention to contemporary phenomenological description of sexual consent was brought to bear on the artefact and theory of this research. From within this material, Simone de Beauvoir's reassessment of the ethical imperative of reciprocity within the face-to-face encounter is drawn on and presented as a potential alternative to Levinas'. It is both assessed as more ethically viable, and the phenomenological quality of reciprocity, as mutual inter-action, better suited to the embodied and interactive medium of VR documentary. Contemporary phenomenologist Ellie Anderson's ambition to redefine consent within a critical phenomenological perspective, as 'feeling-with', has also been taken as a referent for a VR documentary ethics of 'feeling-with'. Both entail an attunement to the reciprocal nature of consent between two (or more) embodied subjects and place primacy on acknowledging documented Others in their personhood - as alterity with interiority. This is not only presented as a proposed formation for ethical representation, but also as ethical provocation for VR interaction design, and working with documentary contributors and collaborators. This contribution to theoretical discourse around VR documentary ethics is not presented within this research as its main contribution to knowledge, and is certainly not intended to be taken as a normative code of ethics that mitigate the ethical 'risk of improper distance' within any VR documentary. This research has, rather, richly detailed how the interplay of practice and theory within production of this particular piece of work *With These Hands* has led to this theoretical proposition. This proposition provides an alternate reference point for 'proper distance' for future VR documentary makers, particularly those working from a feminist perspective and this is a further contribution to the field.

'Reorientation', 'Surfacing' and 'Ant/agonism' - what might be termed 'material techniques' of maintaining 'proper' distance that emerge in *With These Hands* - are not proposed as failsafe mechanisms of ensuring ethical relations between contributors, audiences, and content. As noted by Silverstone, it is possible that the 'risk' and remedy to improper distance in any project may well be required to be assessed on a case by case basis (Silverstone, 2003, p. 9). This research, inclusive of artefact and exegesis, is a clear description of how I assessed and addressed the specific 'risks' of improper distance as they emerged within my making, utilising the descriptive methods of queer phenomenology. This process, and 'Reorientation',

'Surfacing' and 'Ant/agonism' as prompts should prove valuable to future practitioners.

'Reorientation', 'Surfacing' and 'Antagonism' are presented as descriptions of techniques applied in *With These Hands*, born out of practice and drawn into dialogue with the existing wealth of techniques within feminist, decolonial and queer media making traditions - connecting my practice based artefact to the "shoreline" of knowledge (Brabazon et al, 2022, p. 52). In this way the thesis is also evidentiary of the specific value of practice based research in connecting theory and practice.

Similarly, descriptions of workshopping the production materials, in particular the project's answer to a 'consent form', are not presented in themselves as replicable activities for future practitioners or as a prescriptive 'method' that produces an ethical work. They are however outlined in such detail that the profound influence of contributor perspectives are appreciable and acknowledged in the following research work. The contributions of the collaborators and consultants on this project have necessarily altered the shape of this research and my understanding of it. In this way this thesis is evidentiary of the specific value of forms of collaborative practice in XR production and to documentary ethics research.

It is not possible for me to suggest that I have unequivocally produced an 'ethical' piece of work. I do believe however that the feedback received from audiences and contributors reveals the successes of *With These Hands* in terms of managing 'proper'; ethical, critical and responsible distances between audiences, contributor and maker. I also believe I have communicated how theory and practice have interwoven within this research in a way that is useful and transferable to the work of other practitioners. The project suggests a starting point, if not a fully formed framework, for other practitioners to develop ethical boundaries around their practice, paying particular attention to the affordances and ethical 'risks' of their chosen medium in dialogue with their specific documentary subject. It further examples valuable insights that come from consulting with contributors throughout the research and production process. As such this research project is a valuable contribution to the study and advancement of VR documentary ethics.

Concurrent movements in the field and further implications and recommendations of this research.

As a fast developing media and medium, the VR landscape has changed dramatically since the initiation of this research. In particular *WTH* and this wider research project has aligned with four main developments within wider VR documentary practice. The specific research of this thesis, combined with concurrent insights from the field, propose four further avenues for future investigation.

Queer and Feminist Phenomenology and VR Documentary

Queer and Feminist phenomenology provided an epistemological framework and language through which to describe the embodied experience of VR documentary and its ethical ramifications. It is interesting to note that the same year as *WTH*, 2022, award winning French VR documentary maker Celine Tricart released '*Fight Back*' (2022). Like *WTH*, *Fight Back* is also dependant on the Meta Quest 2 headset's advances in hand tracking, and borrows extensively from feminist phenomenological inquiry into rape.

Fight Back is an interactive VR docu-game which shares non-fiction stories of female heroism, reimagined through a sci-fi mythology, whilst hand tracking embodiment facilitates the audience to also learn self defence moves. Whilst Tricart does not expressly mention specific texts as references for the work, *Fight Back* is, I argue, clearly inspired by key feminist phenomenological writing which seek to understand rape as an experience of an embodied subject, and self defence training as a tool for 'perceiving freshly' socialised femininity. Tricart presents the possibilities of VR hand tracking as encouraging physical re-enactment, and therefore a phenomenological 're-wiring' of the body:

There is a lot of rewiring that we have to do in our own brains and through self-defence - this is something that works really well for rewiring our brain into this, like, new version of ourself [sic]..... I read a lot of study of the effect of self-defence on gender-based violence etc. And I know how self-defense training translates into that many less attempted rape, that many less successful rapes, and that many less murders [sic]...And this is just what I want.... I want women to feel better in their own bodies. (Tricart in Bye, 2022b)

I suggest that one of the texts Tricart is referring to is potentially Anne Cahill's *Re-thinking Rape* (2001) in which a large portion is dedicated to the phenomenological ramifications of self defence training. Cahill suggests that "learning self defence provides opportunities to 'reorganise' the female body from its 'habitus' of 'weakness, fragility and passivity'" (Cahill, 2001, p. 201). There is a counter feminist critique of self defence *itself* as encouraging fear, and codifying the female body as 'rapable'. Cahill, however, refutes this critique, referencing Martha McCaughey's *Real Knockouts: The physical feminism of Women's Self-Defense* (1997). She suggests:

Because McCaughey approaches rape as the experience of an embodied subject, she can understand women's self-defense classes not merely as a social expression of women's victimization, but also as a profound challenge to the political structure that shapes women in the form of victims. Taking feminist theory at it's word - namely..that the feminine body can be shaped into other, more empowered, forms than the ones imposed by patriarchy (Cahill, p. 202)

And further elaborates the benefits of learning self defence that are aligned with Tricarts embodied 'rewiring':

Just as embodied subjectivity accounts for the profound harms rape can impose by stressing that an assault on ones body constitutes an assault on ones possibility for personhood, so it also accounts for the depth of the shift inspired by learning to defend one's self. To change the habits and abilities of one's body - as well as the assumptions and expectations one holds of one's body - is to change one's very self. (Cahill, p. 205)

Tricart, working in parallel with this PhD research, is exploring the potential that developments in VR embodiment bring to feminist phenomenological thinking and vice versa. In particular, using embodied VR as a means to explore embodied gender expression, and utilising histories of feminist and critical phenomenologies to do so. As the potential for hand tracking and body mapping in XR technology expands, so do the opportunities for expansion of this work and further phenomenological research through creative XR practice. In particular, these

developments call for research of a queer, feminist and decolonial inflection, that is attuned to both the emancipatory potentials of XR as a creative medium, as well as the biases and exclusions that are codified into the technology. It is important that XR continues to be utilised towards ends critical of ‘king logos’ - XR design in which the user is positioned as “omnipotent, disembodied and isolated point-of-view” (Davis, 2004, p. 71). XR production that builds on queer phenomenology as a critical framework is well suited to this task, and the work of this research in bringing the concepts of ‘orientation’ and ‘extension’ to bear on creative VR and XR practice might support creatives to utilise queer phenomenology in future making.

The successes of *With These Hands* also suggest the possibility for future XR experiences which further elaborate on the phenomenological experience of sexual consent as outlined by Ellie Anderson. The technical motif of *WTH*, as embodying the skin of others, might easily be adapted to explore themes beyond rape and sexual assault in which upholding the contributors ‘humanity’ is imperative. However, it is particularly well suited to exploring sexuality, as this is the experience where we come into most intimate contact with ‘Others’, and an act which undoes “the subject’s fantasmatic sovereignty” (Berlant and Edelman, 2014 p. 2). An aim of *With These Hands* was to bring into ‘ant/agonistic’ dialogue the reality that if the harm of sexual assault is dehumanisation, then societally, we need to reframe the often dehumanising ways we think of, portray and ‘support’ both sexual assault survivors and ‘perpetrators’. More creative exploration of nuanced conceptions of sexual consent could support, at a more interpersonal level, these feminist, queer and liberationist aims. A piece of narrative, documentary XR work with a similar hand embodiment format to *WTH*, that more closely explores sexual consent as a ‘feeling-with’, might allow audiences further reflection on how enforced heterosexuality, patriarchal and misogynistic culture influences their embodied and sexual experience.

Technological developments in VR and MR hybrid experiences and consent

The previously more novel ability of the Quest 2 headset to merge VR and MR capabilities within a single artwork has become more prevalent, both within creative work and as a promise of the technology itself⁷⁴. This is appreciable in the marketing for Apple’s first offering to the HMD market - the Apple Vision Pro - released in 2024, a full 10 years after Oculus (Apple, 2024). The developing sophistication of spatialised computing within this next generation of

⁷⁴ Prior to the point of *WTH* production, in late 2021/ early 2022 there has been a technological divide between AR and MR headsets such as Google Glass, Hololens and Magic Leap and VR headsets such as Oculus.

hybrid XR HMD units will no doubt prove a rich site for artistic exploration, as well as further ethical interrogation. Particularly, this ethical consideration must contend with the increased inclusion of AI generated content, and these devices' data collection and surveillance potential, as they incorporate more sophisticated biometric data input such as the Apple Vision Pro's eye tracking interface (Apple, 2024). There is therefore, a certain level of prescience exhibited within this PhD research project in working with scenes of passthrough or mixed reality inside an otherwise hermetic VR documentary. If headset development continues in the direction indicated by the Apple Vision Pro, and new MR ready Oculus headsets, we might come to see more work that encourages further blurring of users' own bodies and environments with non-fiction assets and storytelling about the lives of others. This research begins to imagine the ethical ramifications of such acts and intimates fertile ground for future investigation.

This research's consideration of VR documentary ethics in combination with contemporary consent discourse, and the increased biometric and spatial data collection of the headset, suggests a further specific and urgent area expansion of this research. As Mandy Rose (2020) states "we need to recognise the platform as a fourth party" in the previously considered documentary ethics 'triad' of Maker, Contributor and Audience. Although academic (Madary & Metzinger, 2016; O'Brolcháin et al, 2016) and creative (see Callumn Cooper's *Porton Down* as detailed in Rose, 2020) investigation of this has begun, the rapid development of HMD technology urges the continued development of this as an area of attention in research and practice. In particular the ant/agonist provocation of this research suggests future creative works in which the machinations of the headset manufactures data collection *become* part of the 'discourse' or 'voices' that are brought into 'discomforting' dialogue and made apprehendable to an audience. An understanding of contemporary debates in sexual ethics and consent would be invaluable to this work, as future XR makers must grapple with how audiences can truly give 'informed consent' to engage with their artworks, given the amount of intricate data being captured by the headset manufacturers' backend. *WTH* sets a precedent for providing the audience with recourse to consent (or not) to engage with the XR experience as part of the in-headset experience. This research suggests a future work that makes explicit how audience data will be processed by the headset as a form of informed consent, weaving that consent mechanisms into the fabric of experiences.

Consensual approaches to XR interaction

Another emerging theme within this research, and palpable within contemporary XR documentary discourse (and documentary discourse as a whole) are questions around how audiences might consensually engage with work that they may find ‘triggering’, particular work around harm and sexuality. As XR documentary works move away from the ‘orepedic’ model of ‘the empathy machine’ - that the work exists to ‘teach’ audiences about the experiences of others - it is more readily understood that audiences may also have lived experience of documentary subject matter. Contemporary XR makers must develop more consensual forms of interaction design that invite audiences to participate in dialogue with the work, rather than ‘subject’ them to it as a ‘learning’ experience.

A project that can be seen to be exploring interaction as a consent mechanism is theatre company Trial and Error’s *Museum of Austerity* (2021), made with consultation and co-writing from journalist and editor John Pring, along with the families of its main subjects. Utilising spatial computing technology, and Mixed Reality audio and visuals, the project seeks to make visible the “‘grave and systemic violations’ of the rights of disabled people”⁷⁵ enacted by the UK government as austerity measures in the past 15 years. It presents a number of narratives of individual deaths occurring directly as a result of changes to disability support and fit-to-work assessments by the Department of Work and Pensions in 2008.

The work explored the accessibility and safeguarding potential of Mixed Reality headsets, and has been designed to be personalised or ‘filterable’, for example with optional captioning and hearing-aid integrated sound etc. It also allows for the ability to remove certain stories from the work, after an introduction to the content, if requested. The work attends to embodied interaction as ‘consent’ in ways aligned to those explored in this research. The virtual experience consists of life size static dioramas of individuals and the situations within which they died (for example in a hospital bed or collapsed in the street) accompanied by audio of their partners and family. These scenes are geo-located within the exhibition space, and are only visible and audible when an audience physically moves closer to them. If the audience moves away from a story, the visuals disappear, and the audio fades away, permitting one to take breaks from content, or avoid certain stories altogether. This work, in a manner reminiscent

⁷⁵ (*Museum of Austerity Visitor Guide, 2024*)

of *Testimony*, represents a mutual, reciprocal engagement with content. A wider accessibility focused visitor guide indicates the attention paid to making the project as accessible as possible to audiences through a disability sensitive lens. Similar to *WTH*, *Museum of Austerity* does not assume that its audience do not share the lived experience of its contributors. In this case, the work does not assume its audience are not disabled, and therefore does not imply that this work is about building capacity for empathy with an 'unlike' Other. Rather, it positions itself as a historical record of these individual deaths that might otherwise be simply subsumed into statistics, in a format sensitive to the nature of the content and referential to the 'invisibility' of disabled people in society and the fatal implications of government austerity policy in the lives of some citizens.

Museum of Austerity and *With These Hands* as well as older work like *Testimony* suggest alternative models of interaction design in XR, no longer 'storyliving' or 'storydoing', they are rather experienced as a reciprocal relation between user and content. They account for and encourage that audiences with lived experience knowledge engage with the work, and as such anticipate a more dialogical relationship with content rather than educational. This trend or movement in XR work is directly linked to the following 'trend' in XR practice - working collaboratively with contributors. A pivot toward more consensual interaction is both, I posit, an outcome and precursor to this collaborative methodology.

Collaborative XR practice and research

Turning toward more collaborative forms of production in my own research is mirrored by a growing attendance to co-authorship and a restructuring of audience, media maker and 'contributor' relations in many other XR projects produced within this PhD timeline. Most notably, IDFA 2022 also was the launch of the MIT Co-Creation Studio's survey of the "emerging (yet age old) set of practices" of 'co-creation' (*Collective Wisdom, 2022 p.25*). The attendance within the *WTH* project to the lived-experience knowledge and research of Meggan, Bryony and the wider consult survivor cohort could certainly be read as in line with this movement towards collaboration and co-authorship in XR documentary, and wider documentary discourse.

The term collaborative is used loosely in this thesis, as I am aware that *With These Hands* is not an example of truly participatory or co-designed research or practice. One of the issues in proposing collaboratively designed XR work is the relative lack of exposure in the general public to the range of creative technologies, mediums and genres of XR, immersive and interactive artwork as well as the cumbersome, expensive and first-time-user-inaccessible technology required to create it (Cizek & Uricchio, 2023. Pp.125 - 130). In other words, XR technologies cannot be merely distributed to communities to self-produce documentary content, in a way that co-authored video or audio projects can, for example. Never-the-less projects like *With These Hands* and *Museum of Austerity* indicate that an attention to consultation with those contributing their narratives to XR works can have profound impact on not only the content, but the *forms* of the works as they become more geared toward access for a lived-experience audience. This lays the groundwork for more co-designed XR in the future. As more disabled, racialised or in other ways minoritised audiences experience work in which their participation is encouraged and centred, the more exposure to technologies, platforms and mediums, and the more scope for genuine co-designed creative XR works. Communities might begin to imagine for themselves what the benefits or opportunities these media present to their creative or political agendas. To use the specific example of *With These Hands*, before the XR project itself existed, it was very hard to describe any opportunities or ethical 'risks' the medium of embodied VR presented to SLEEC, the workshop groups or Naroa. Having now made *With These Hands*, I have a piece of media, and the reflections from SLEEC and Naroa, which can be used to inform future contributors. By sharing *With These Hands* as a prototype for consensual interaction, I would be able to begin more equitable conversations with potential collaborators about working with the medium. It would provide us more shared language and experience from which a truly co-authored experience could be developed. As such, although this research is careful not to not overstate the collaborative aspects of *WTH* production, this research nevertheless makes an argument and lays groundwork for future makers to employ collaborative and co-design practices in XR making and XR ethics research.

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APPENDIX i - Production Timeline and Funding Summary

2018

November

Test Shooting for Passing WIP

2019

April

Test Shooting for The OH Expedition WIP

August

Test Shooting for The OH Expedition WIP

October

Test Shooting for The OH Expedition WIP

2020

August

NDA early experiments with With These Hands

2021

December

Awarded Scottish Graduate School for Arts & Humanities Saltire Emerging Researcher
Exchange Fund.

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2022

March

Awarded Bristol and Bath Creative R&D Trailblazer Fund.

April

9th -10th - Workshop 1: Knowledge exchange with SLEEC.

13th - Workshop 2: With the 'Consult Survivors' Network.

14th - Workshop 3: Attendees of 'Dismantling Male Violence' Workshop.

May

1st month of research exchange at Centre for Sexology and Sexuality Studies (CSSS) @
University of Malmö.

First R&D meeting with Khora VR in Denmark.

June

2nd month of research exchange at CSSS @ University of Malmö

Awarded IDFA DocLab Research & Development Fund

Applied & awarded 12 hours in-kind development @ CAMERA Studio, University of Bath

July

Hire 1990's Chris, Saturn Akin, Fossilised Frequencies, and production support MollyMae
Whawell.

August

5th - Chris hand scanning @ CAMERA Studio, University of Bath.

11th - First contact Naroa.

30th - Cast Len Goatzee & Script Lock.

September

5th & 6th - Record Len and Naroa's audio.

27th - Naroa Hand Scanning with Saturn Akin.

Receive Chris & SLEEC's self produced audio.

October

3rd month of research exchange at CSSS @ University of Malmö.

Assets delivered to Khora / Khora production.

28th *WTH* Prototype sharing at CSSS

November

7th - Arrive and begin installation @ IDFA venue Cultuurhuis de Brakke Grond.

9th- 20th of November *With These Hands* screens @ IDFA DocLab.

December

9th - Final sharing of *WTH* with Naroa

15th - Final sharing of *WTH* with Meggan of SLEEC

16th - Final sharing of *WTH* with 1990s Chris

APPENDIX ii - Ethics Documents

The following pages are copies of my consent form and participant information deck for *With These Hands*. Approved with conditions (included) on 28/07/2022 by the University of the West of Scotland Ethics Board.

Below is the text received by any audiences who use the QR code at IDFA exhibition;

On webpage;

If you'd like to give feedback or respond to *With These Hands* you can send us a message or voice note by clicking the button below.

After leaving your response to *With These Hands* you will be asked if you consent to your response being anonymised and used in Tessa Ratuszynska's Doctoral Research at the University of the West of Scotland.

You do not have to consent to this to leave a message.

All messages will be deleted after August 2023.

In WhatsApp Auto Response;

Thank you for responding to *With These Hands*. Please reply 'Yes' to this message if you consent to your response being used for the purpose of research for Tessa Ratuszynska's Doctoral Research at the University of the West of Scotland.

This takes the form of written quotes which may be used in a thesis, published paper and in academic and artistic presentations.

We will export your response and delete the original Whatsapp message and your phone number within 14 days.

If you have any questions about how your response will be used you can contact tessaratuszynska@gmail.com.

